

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D4.7 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment – update M32

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Authors	Zainab Mehdi, TRI Niamh Aspell, TRI Su Anson, TRI
Contributors	Hannah Robinson, UANTWERPEN Carla Ventre, SAPIENZA James Rhys Edwards, SINUS Viktoria Adler, SYNIO Neda Deneva, SYNIO Jose Manuel Palma Oliveira, FS Beatriz Rosa, FS Diana Beljaars, SU Sergei Shubin, SU Niamh Aspell, TRI Susan Anson, TRI Javier Lorente, URJC Marina Ghersetti, UGOT Bengt Johansson, UGOT Ioannis Bagkatzounis, KEMEA Anna Tsekoura, KEMEA Ioannis Konstantopoulos, KEMEA

Effrosyni Dima, KEMEA

Reviewers

Niamh Aspell, TRI

Ioannis Bagkatzounis, KEMEA

Anna Tsekoura, KEMEA

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Executive Summary

This report provides an update of D4.3 “*Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment*,” which focused on describing and assessing government response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The report has extracted key findings from the D4.1, “*Baseline Report Governmental responses*,” D4.5, “*Baseline Report Government Responses Update*,” and the complete cohort of WP4 expert interviews conducted by COVINFORM target countries until May 2023. As stated in D4.3, additional insights regarding COVID-19 responses measures, the consequences of the implemented measures, and the legal aspects pertaining to the pandemic responses would offer a more comprehensive government level analysis. Details regarding the updated expert interview guidelines can be found in D4.6, “*Research Design: Governmental Responses – update M26*”. Like D4.3, this report has explored the following five dimensions of government response:

- 1) Pandemic planning and preparedness;
- 2) Economic and social welfare responses to COVID-19;
- 3) COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance;
- 4) Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and response;
- 5) Governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability;

To provide a holistic and temporal understanding of these dimensions, COVINFORM partners identified relevant data within D4.1, D4.5, and WP4 expert interviews with Government Experts and Stakeholders. COVINFORM partners followed a standardised questionnaire to guide the extraction of relevant data within the five dimensions across all the target countries. The countries under study are Austria, Germany, Greece, Belgium, Italy, England, Wales, Portugal, Spain, and Sweden. To explore the government responses overtime, the following time points were considered:

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020

T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination influenced measures

T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022

The information included in this deliverable is complimented by country frameworks which employ Ostrom’s Social-Ecological System framework¹ (Annex 2). The SES framework is an empirically applied conceptual framework for analysing complex social systems.² The analysis approach does not have a methodological guide; therefore, this allows flexibility in how it may

¹ Ostrom, E. (2007). A diagnostic approach for going beyond panaceas. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(39), 15181–15187. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0702288104>

²<https://redox-college.s3.ap-south-1.amazonaws.com/kmc/2020/May/05/ZtqfETsep9eeFPr0fThT.pdf> Accessed: 08/08/2023.

be adapted to diverse contexts. The frameworks consist of nested systems (Resource Systems and Units, Governance Systems, Actor Systems/Users; a description of the Interaction Area and Outcomes). This is connected to social, economic, and political settings and related ecosystems. Therefore, it ‘provides governance solutions to social-ecological problems’ (ibid). More details on the methodology can be found in D4.2, *“Research Design: Government Responses.”*

The current report studies 10 COVINFORM countries: Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Sweden, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Wales, and Austria. The report starts off with an introductory chapter (Chapter 1), followed by an overview of the methods used to carry out the empirical research (Chapter 2). Here, particular attention will be paid to the country reports completed by COVINFORM partners, and the governance framework (Ostrom’s SES framework) adopted to accompany the country reports across all countries. In chapter 3, the country reports will be presented. The penultimate chapter (Chapter 4) will provide an analysis of the country reports in terms of commonalities identified across the COVINFORM countries. The commonalities will be reported within the five dimensions presented in this report. Finally, the concluding chapter (Chapter 5) presents a summary of the key findings in relation to the five dimensions under study. The key findings will be explored in further detail in the D4.8 deliverable *“Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts”* due in M33.

Contents

- 1 Introduction..... 11
- 2 Methodology 12
- 3 Country Reports 15
 - 3.1 Austria 15
 - 3.2 Belgium..... 24
 - 3.3 England 33
 - 3.4 Germany 44
 - 3.5 Greece 58
 - 3.6 Italy..... 65
 - 3.7 Portugal 77
 - 3.8 Sweden 88
 - 3.9 Spain 101
 - 3.10 Wales..... 119
- 4. Analysis..... 128
- Conclusion 156

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
ANPC	National Civil Protection Group
BMG	Federal Ministry of Health
CCS	Civil Contingencies Secretariat
DGS	Directorate General of Health
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EU	European Union
FDP	Federal Democratic Party
FPÖ	The Austrian Freedom Party
IHR	International Health Regulations
KYSEA	Council for Foreign and Defence Affairs
LRF	Local Resilience forums
MSMEs	Micro, Small, Medium Enterprises
NDR	Non-domestic rates
NEOS	The New Austria and Livial Forum
NFP	National Focal Point
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
NHS	National Health System
ÖVP	Austrian People's Party
PHA	Public Health Authorities
RMG	Risk Management Group
SALAR	Swedish Association of Local Authorities
SCG	Strategic Coordinating Groups
SCGs	Strategic Coordinating Groups
SEF	Portuguese and Border Service

SEISS	Self-Employment Support Scheme
SES	Socio-Ecological Systems
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SPD	Social Democratic Party
SPÖ	Social Democratic Party
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This current deliverable provides an update of D4.3, “Analysis: Government Responses to COVID-19 and Impact Assessment,” which focused on describing and assessing government response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This D4.7 report will start off with an introductory chapter (Chapter 1) that touches on the five dimensions that WP4 has explored thus far to best understand governmental responses and impacts in the COVINFORM target countries. The countries under study in this deliverable are England, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Sweden, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Wales, and Austria. This chapter will then be followed by an overview of the methods (Chapter 2) that were applied in this deliverable. The methodology will include commentary on country reports completed by COVINFORM partners and commentary on the governance framework (Ostrom’s SES framework) that was adopted to accompany the country reports. Chapter 3 will present the country reports per country, whilst chapter 4 will provide an analysis of the country reports’ key findings. The analysis will specifically focus on commonalities identified across all the COVINFORM countries. As a key factor of analysis to the COVINFORM project, we also explored vulnerabilities acknowledged by governments and how they changed over time, the emergence of new vulnerabilities, responses in relation to vulnerable groups and how they were supported, and any new vulnerabilities that were created because of response measures. Details are provided in relation to crisis management, barriers of implementation, changes in crisis response, and economic and social welfare responses. Finally, all findings from Chapter 4 will be explored in further detail in the D4.8 deliverable. D4.8 will specifically answer the overarching research questions in a cross-country analysis and synthesis. Finally, Chapter 5, will include an overview of key findings across all the COVINFORM countries. The key findings will be complimented by how the public reacted in terms of crisis management and its changes. The lessons learnt will then be followed by a brief summary.

In D4.3, five dimensions were explored to understand governmental responses and impacts in the COVINFORM target countries, as follows:

- 1) Pandemic planning and preparedness;
- 2) Economic and social welfare responses to COVID-19;
- 3) COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance;
- 4) Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and responses;
- 5) Governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability

As reported in D4.3, the following lessons emerged:

- Each target country followed its own response path, based on both pre-existing and newly developed strategies;
- Governments in target countries identified vulnerabilities based on different variables related to health, cultural, economic, and social factors;
- Governmental structures and European communities strived to tailor their responses based on unique or shared characteristics among the European countries;
- Target countries established economic instruments to support and protect businesses, including funds for businesses and vulnerable groups as well as funds for the pandemic recovery. In addition, target countries also developed and implemented social welfare

measures for vulnerable groups, including support for families, benefits for unemployed people, and support to ensure labour market continuity.

- Ethical and legal challenges existed with the implementation of restrictive measures, the surveillance and contact tracing responses, as well as the COVID-19 alert and warning systems.

The following knowledge gaps were identified:

- Examining how the concept of vulnerability was addressed by governments and what changes there were to addressing vulnerability across different pandemic timelines (and their agendas), particularly between pre and post vaccination rollout, and in younger populations, or those who were deemed clinically vulnerable.
- Exploring the pandemic measures and the repercussions and unintended consequences that the implemented restrictive measures, contact tracing technologies, and alert and warning systems created in terms of surveillance and legal functioning of the target countries' governments and public health systems.
- Identifying the range of economic and social measures each country has implemented.
- Examining on a deeper level the intragovernmental relationships on a horizontal level such as the cooperation between ministries and other agencies, organisations, and companies to identify whether and to what degree the common phenomenon of overlapping responsibilities can be beneficial or hinder stakeholders from an operational perspective, communication and the vaccination campaign.
- Understanding the adaptation of strategies and modification to pandemic management and response in relation to the emergence of COVID-19 variants such as Omicron.

The structure of this deliverable is twofold: it consists of 10 country reports (Section 3) and of the analysis of the data according to the pre-defined dimensions (Section 4).

2 Methodology

The COVINFORM overarching research questions are:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response of certain vulnerable groups?
- RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

This report addresses the overarching research questions RQ1, RQ2, RQ4 & RQ5 in relation to WP4 government responses and impact assessment. The COVINFORM team is doing this by providing an update of the initial findings that were presented in the D4.3 report. Besides using data from the

baseline COVINFORM report D4.1, *“Baseline report: Governmental responses,”* this report also utilises data from the updated baseline COVINFORM report D4.5, *“Baseline report: Governmental responses update,”* and WP4 expert interviews conducted with Government Experts and Stakeholders. In D4.3, it was reported that further interviews would be conducted prior to the current analysis (D4.7), if COVINFORM partners could not secure the required sample (n, 5) by February 2022. Most countries finalised their interviews by May 2023. Partners SYNNO (Austria) and TRI (England), conducted (n, 4) and (n, 3), respectively. During TRI’s second recruitment phase, it was not possible to secure any outstanding interviews because Government Officials were and continue to be during responding to the public enquiry on COVID-19. All additional interview findings have been integrated into this report. SYNNO initially troubles to find a fifth interview partner as government officials were directly involved in the crisis management and thus very time poor. However, SYNNO managed to conduct a 5th interview in the beginning of 2023.

As such, the empirical material presented in this report contains information from the previous deliverables, as well as updated information and to some extent new data. The data has been organized in country reports and so-called country frames for all the 10 countries, completed by COVINFORM partners.

The country reports, presented in Chapter 3, follow standardised questions, which take into account the aforementioned five dimensions from D4.3 (see Introduction) as well as RQ1, RQ2, RQ4 & RQ5. The questions mainly concern the government structure and changes, if any, of COVINFORM target countries, pandemic plans in place prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, changes to governmental responses over the life course of the pandemic, and reflections on pandemic management (see Annex 1). As a key factor of analysis to the COVINFORM project we also explored vulnerabilities acknowledged by governments and how they changed over time, the emergence of new vulnerabilities, responses in relation to vulnerable groups and how they were supported, and any new vulnerabilities that were created because of response measures. Details are provided in relation to crisis management, barriers of implementation, changes in crisis response, and economic and social welfare responses.

The relevant findings are presented in Chapter 4 of this report. Each country is accompanied with a governance framework (known as Ostrom’s SES framework) also referred to as country frame in this deliverable. The country frames can be found in Annex 2. Known for being an empirically applied conceptual framework, the purpose of the framework is to analyse complex social systems. The analysis approach does not have a methodological guide, which means this enables flexibility in how it may be adapted to diverse contexts. The frameworks consist of nested systems (Resource Systems and Units, Governance Systems, Actor Systems/Users; a description of the Interaction Area and Outcomes). This is connected to social, economic, and political settings and related eco-systems. An explanation of the SES framework methodology can be found in D3.2: *“Multi-site research design and methodological framework,”*.

In this deliverable, as well as in all of COVINFORMS Dx.7 deliverables, we used the SES framework to organise the data that we have collected over the course of the project in a systematic manner. We chose three different points in time (see below) to illustrate what has been done in terms of governmental crisis response and how this has changed over time. As such, the country frames are a visualisation of the corner stones of governmental pandemic response and its changes over time, following the logic of the Ostrom model. Finally, the SES approach and the country frames will allow

to contextualise the COVINFORM case studies (WP3) in a national setting as the same methodology is used.

The Ostrom model consists of five sub-systems below which we have operationalised as follows:

Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to in a country and to manage a (health) crisis

Governance Systems (GS) – describes the basic structure of how a country is governed in relation to a (health) crisis

Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis management in a country

Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the governmental crisis response

Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. In this concrete case it mostly describes measures taken to manage the health crisis (e.g., lockdowns, etc.)³.

The D4.3 deliverable had considered the period from October 2020 to January 2021, and this update, as already mentioned, has taken into consideration three different phases of the pandemic:

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic up until January 2020

T1: COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures

T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022

The COVINFORM project did this as this update of D4.3 focuses on temporality and change during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our aim is to understand how government responses reacted to the pandemic and its outcomes over time. This will help us to understand the impact of the pandemic and its measures, key findings and best practices.

Prior to the analysis of the country reports, the questions of the standardised questionnaire were assigned to the most appropriate dimension of all five WP4 dimensions. Then, upon receipt of all the country reports, the approach to analysis was identifying commonalities across all the COVINFORM countries and grouping the commonalities together. When writing up the deliverable, the grouped commonalities were addressed for each question that fell under the dimensions under study for this WP.

The next chapter present the full country report of the ten COVINFORM countries.

³ In the country frames T0 the Interaction area is empty as T0 indicates the time prior to COVID-19. Hence, no interaction was taking place yet.

3 Country Reports

3.1 Austria

3.1.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

The territory of the Federal Republic of Austria consists of nine federal states or provinces which have great autonomy. Austria's federal government normally only has a regulatory role in state affairs. Vienna is the federal capital and the seat of the supreme federal authorities. Since 1995, Austria has been a member of the European Union. Five political parties are currently represented in the Austrian Parliament: The Austrian People's Party (ÖVP), the Social Democratic Party of Austria (SPÖ), the Austrian Freedom Party (FPÖ), the Green Party and the NEOS. All political institutions established by the Constitution derive their powers either directly or indirectly from elections by secret, personal and equal ballot.

The Austrian Parliament consists of two chambers: the National Assembly (Nationalrat) and the Federal Council (Bundesrat). The National Assembly is the main legislative body. The preparation and implementation of legislation takes place in the Federal Government or in the Provincial Governments. Legislative tasks are carried out at federal level by the National Assembly in conjunction with the Federal Council. The Federal Council represents the interests of the provinces in Parliament. Provincial Assemblies (Landtage) represent the interests of citizens in the individual provinces. Each federal province is administered by a Provincial Government, which is headed by a Provincial Governor (Landeshauptmann) elected by the respective Provincial Assembly.

Austrian welfare system

Austria has a well-established welfare system. It supports Austrians as well as other residents with benefits across their life course: from youth, to work life to retirement. Main pillars are free childcare and schooling, unemployment benefits, free healthcare, and pension payments. The social welfare system functions as a social security net. Some of these payments also depend on the citizen's income such as unemployment benefits. However, the welfare state is based on the principle of social redistribution⁴.

Principles of Pandemic Management

Health crisis management including pandemics fall under the responsibility of the Health Ministry and the health minister. They oversee steering and coordinating the health authorities in all of Austria, in the case of pandemic. Strategic decisions such as testing and vaccination strategies, provision of protective equipment and medical goods as well as the development of public health measures for the handling of the pandemic including movement restrictions would also fall under their responsibility.

⁴ <https://www.sozialleistungen.at/c/SL8096520/Aufgaben-und-Ziele>

These instructions must be implemented and followed by the respective governors of Austria's nine states.

Austria also has a designated Crisis and Catastrophe Emergency Task Force (Staatliche Krisen- und Katastrophenschutzmanagement, SKKM) which comes into action in emergency situations. The SKKM is located within the Ministry of Interior. It is an event-driven task force which only becomes active in times of crisis. The SKKM is an institution that supports the federal states who are mainly in charge of reacting to situations of crisis and catastrophe. It is the central institution that coordinates the actions of the states (which oversee crisis and catastrophe management due to the federalism in Austria) on a federal level. It consists of representatives of each of the ministries as well as states, operational organisations (such as police, etc.) and media outlets.

The Epidemiegesetz (Epidemic Law), last updated in 1950, was the base for the pandemic management in early 2020. This is also the document which outlined that the Health Ministry oversees the pandemic response.

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic Austria had an Influenza Pandemic Plan (Influenza Pandemieplan – Strategie für Österreich), which includes a strategy for the country to cope with the Influenza virus. The document was published in 2006 by the former Federal Ministry for Women and Health and is still in use today.

3.1.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

COVID-19 management in Austria (Beginning until vaccination influenced measures – Nov 2021)

The Ministry of Health, under the leadership of the Austrian Health minister, oversaw the pandemic management. Austria does not have an independent public health authority that had decision making power during the COVID-19 pandemic. The SKKM played an important role in the COVID-19 management. Additionally, it was a place where the various COVID-19 advisory boards, set up in different ministries and institutions, could exchange and work together.

This means that the task of the Interior Ministry (where the SKKM is located) is to ensure this coordination, to bring everyone around the table and see that we are all pulling on the same string in the same direction. In the past we very often did that in the background, in secret. This means that all ministries, all federal states and the large emergency organizations and the leading media ORF and APA are sitting at one table to deal with the content, to see how we can create a common thread [Government_Int.4].

Nonetheless, other federal government actors as well as the state governments were also strongly involved in the pandemic management. Key actors within the federal government were the Federal Chancellery of the Republic of Austria, Ministry of Finance, and the Ministry of Interior. Decisions that were under the responsibility of other ministries (other than the health ministry) were often coordinated amongst members of the federal government. The Bundeskanzleramt (Federal Chancellery of the Republic of Austria) led by the Chancellor of Austria was strongly involved in the pandemic management as otherwise it would have been difficult to execute some decisions. One of the reasons why close cooperation was so important is the fact that the Chancellor was and still is from the People's Party and the Health Ministry is still led by the coalition partner, The Green Party. There

was a need for consent between the Chancellor and the health minister as the following quote illustrate:

You can't suddenly rule the whole country, from the government as Minister of Health. That does not work. You have Realpolitik and of course you have a government, and you are also the small mini-partner [in the government]. And vice versa, I understood Kurz [Chancellor Sebastian Kurz] at that point, that wouldn't have been great for him either, that Anschober [Health Minister Rudolf Anschober] is now more or less responsible. (Communication_3 Austria).

While in the beginning of the pandemic Austria's COVID-19 response was mainly regulated by the Epidemic law established in 1950, several COVID-19 laws were passed as the pandemic progressed, the first and most extensive passed on the 15th of March 2020. More precisely, the COVID-19 laws changed and amended the Epidemic law. The first COVID-19 law, amongst other things, enacted a federal law on the establishment of the COVID-19 crisis management fund (COVID-19-FondsG) and a federal law on interim measures to prevent the spread of COVID-19 (COVID-19 Measures Act) as well as the statutory provisional budget for 2020, the Federal Financial Framework Act 2019 to 2022, the Federal Act on the Establishment of a Federal Reduction Participation Joint Stock Company, the Labour Market Policy Financing Act, the Labour Market Service Act and the Employment Contract Law Adaptation Act. These laws and their amendments give the Minister of Health additional power to manage this health crisis via ordinances. In March 2020 to March 2021 several ordinances, based on the above-mentioned laws, were published by the various Austrian departments (for more information see D4.1 and frames D4.7).

The first lockdown started on the 16th of March 2020. This decision was taken based on the newly passed COVID-19 law as it also regulates the measure to contain the spread of COVID-19. The restrictions in public space were controlled by the police, administrative penalties of up to 3,600 euros were threatened under the COVID-19 law, and in certain cases administrative penalties of up to 30,000 euros. Other measures to contain the spread of the virus were social distancing rules and public health advice to keep 1,5-2m distance to others. People were only allowed to be outside with other members of their household. In April wearing a mouth-nose protection became mandatory in shops. At the end of April 2020, the lockdown ended but rules around wearing a mouth-nose protection got extended and then again relaxed in mid-June. Testing, which was initially only available when already sick, was made available for free for people returning home from holidays in August. In September 2020 the *Corona Ampel* was introduced, a tool that should visualise the epidemiological situation on a regional level.

The government temporarily increased the social support for people out of work who are no longer eligible for unemployment money due to the ongoing COVID-19 crisis. Already in March 2020, the Austrian government provided a first aid package (€38 Billion) to battle the negative economic outcome of the Corona virus and related lockdown as well as other measures. This included the short work scheme where employers remove employees from their payroll and have their wages subsidised by the government, financial hardship fund (Härtefallfond) for

small enterprises and one person companies, a Corona fund, and a fixed expenses subsidy program.

Due to rising COVID-19 case numbers a lockdown light was active from the 3rd to the 16th of November 2020 which was then followed by a hard lockdown from 17th of November until the 6th of December. This was followed by 'soft lockdown' from the 7th to the 23rd of December which then again was followed by a 'hard lockdown' from the 26th of December until 18th of January 2021. Finally, the lockdown was extended until the 7th of February 2021. These measures were accompanied by free mass testing. Once the lockdown was over the wearing of FFP2 masks in shops, hospitals and public transport was made mandatory. The nightly curfew between 8pm and 6am, put in place on the 3rd of November 2020 was still active but people were again allowed to meet persons from other households during the day. Shortly before Easter the eastern states of Austria declared another lockdown due to high numbers of hospital admissions and fears of overloading the system. From the 19th of May until the 30st of June 2021 Austria started the first 'reopening' of all spheres of life including hospitality until midnight, events (not full capacities) and the reduction of social distancing rules to only 1 meter.

However, on the 15th of November 2021 the government imposed a lockdown for unvaccinated people (people who did not have a positive green pass that Austria used to validate vaccination). It was also the end of November was also the time when Austria recorded it first Omicron case. Only a week later a general lockdown was enacted which would last until the 12th of December. In early February the validity of the green pass expired for over 200.000 Austrian which slowly led to the end of the lockdown for the unvaccinated in February 2022.

Austria only fully opened in June 2022 when the last COVID-19 measures (mandatory mask wearing in supermarkets and public transportation) ended. Only in Vienna mandatory mask wearing was extended until the end of April 2023.

The above only encompasses the most significant measures and regulations on a national level (except the lockdown for the eastern part of Austria) due to the length limitations of this report. The period between November 2020 until June 2022 was influenced by a constant change of rules and regulations, processes of reopening and 'closing downs' depending on COVID-19 indices, vaccination rates, and political decision making. These often quickly changing rules and regulations were also on times only regional as there were variations in the COVID-19 management in the different states and different priorities that state governments followed.

For example, we can compare all of these pandemic measures with the road traffic regulations. That means the federal government will say at some point that this applies and every authority can always be stricter about it. [...] But wherever I work with an order, I can of course sharpen it. And [pause] at the beginning the government thought one should do everything relatively the same way [the COVID-19 measures]. Now one wants to introduce differences, because of a wide variety of other aspects, which of course also have to be taken into account, such as the

economy, but the question is what weight do I give to the economy, tourism, and personal feelings compared to the healthcare system? [...] To what extent do I give them space and then take regional measures. So classically Tyrol and Vorarlberg, although they have high numbers, open while Vienna stays closed, right? [...] The only question is to what extent does it make sense? Because, if I'm driving through Austria today, I can see relatively quickly from the traffic signs: what applies where? It's much more difficult for me in this area [of COVID-19], because I have to have the text of the ordinance with me somewhere, and it may even differ per municipality or per district. That means the announcement and also the transparency, what applies at the place where I am right now is much more difficult. And that's why you can of course also think about it psychologically and say in the sense of societal aspects I try to introduce as little differences as possible so that people don't get confused. Because if you have to think differently about the measures every ten kilometers, you can ask: does that make sense or doesn't it make sense? Especially with something that knows no boundaries. [Government_Int.4].

The above quote reflects on the one hand, on the decision-making process within the federal structure of Austria and on the other hand, it hints on the confusion that such regional measures, that often did not follow a straightforward logics (such as COVID-19 case numbers) which also made it hard for residents to understand and follow the pandemic management.

On the 27th of December 2020 the first person in Austria was vaccinated with the Pfizer vaccine. Vaccination in nursing homes, nursing staff and family members of high-risk patients was prioritized. Austria established a green pass system to check if an individual was 'fully' vaccinated, tested, or recovered. A positive green pass was a condition to enter many places such as bars or restaurants. Overall vaccination efforts progressed and many of those already vaccinated received their second shot before the end of the summer 2021. In June 2022 around 70% of the Austrian population received at least two COVID-19 shots⁵. Initially the green pass was valid for 360 days with two shots. With more and more evidence this period got shorten. Then a third shot was necessary to have a valid green pass. Between the 05.02.2022 and the 31.05.2022 Austria introduced mandatory vaccination. Finally, by June 2022 no vaccination proof was needed anymore.

Since the new Health Minister Johannes Rauch took office in March a strong change in the pandemic management occurred. It shifted from lockdowns towards a strategy of 'living with the viruses. With this shift Rauch followed the example of other European countries. Additionally, there were two other factors responsible for this change in strategy: growing dissatisfaction of citizens with the pandemic management as well as the introduction of the vaccine.

In 2021, another guiding (and evaluating) document was published by the Federal Ministry of Social Services, Health, Care and Consumer Protection: "The COVID-19 Pandemic: Stocktaking and Framework for Action" (Die COVID-19 Pandemie: Bestandsaufnahmen und Handlungsrahmen). The Minister of Health conducted an update of the document which was

<https://orf.at/corona/daten/impfung>

republished in April 2022. This document outlines pandemic planning and management for the COVID-19 pandemic specifically based on the lessons learned in the first year of the pandemic.

According to the Court of Auditors, the Minister of Health did not make sufficient use of legal instruments at their disposal, such as decrees, ordinances, and directives to make some adequate changes and amendments to the existing Epidemic Act. Therefore, there were, for instance, no effective instructions for nationwide contact tracing, which disturbed the monitoring process of the isolation measures within the framework of the Epidemiological Reporting System - EMS). Further, the document outlines that despite the legal basis for measures, questions on surveillance response and its accordance with basic human rights were raised. Issues regarding data protection appear on multiple stages, starting with the registration and data submission of an infected person to the authorities. Moreover, as part of the contact tracing, the infected person must share data on contact persons. A mandatory quarantine for infected persons limits the freedom of movement, which can only be justified as a measure to protect public security. Similarly, travel warning involving health checks and disclosure of previous travel and contacts affects both freedom of movement and data protection. Social distancing measures including closure of schools, public places religious services restrict people in multiple fundamental rights (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2020).

Talking about barriers and issues in the pandemic management with the governmental stakeholder we interviewed two points stuck out: the idleness of decision making in the Austrian democratic system and federalism.

[...] I'm not criticizing the democratic system. As a democratic republic with all the things it takes to get a law going, we are very, very sluggish in managing a crisis that requires immediate action. Because the decision-making process in our state sometimes takes years. If you look at major legislative projects, and I think that's a good thing. It is also good that all stakeholders have the opportunity to get involved in the discourse. It's also good that you take the time to discuss this with people and listen to the needs of groups that may not be present all the time and don't have a super good lobby. But that means that these processes all have and must have a very low stepping speed, yes. Because otherwise I can't (hear) them all. It is of course difficult in such a situation to enact rules very quickly in a very rapid and dynamic situation.... to enact these rules for everyone in such a way that they are always up to date [Government_1 Austria].

The first led to a rather undynamic crisis response while the latter led to confusing multitude of rules and regulations in the various Austrian states. In the beginning of the COVID-19 the crisis was only managed by the national government. Over time, this changed and those political areas, where the state government has power over, were more and more decided on a local state level than on the national one. This was influenced by different political leadership as well as differing epidemiological developments. In the beginning

[...] everyone was very happy, I think, that there were corresponding requirements and corresponding legal measures at national level. And then ultimately the federal states, but also the social partners, the emergency organizations, had a rather positive connotation that there is now strong leadership. That there are clear instructions, and that it was also clear to the residents that... how to behave. In a later episode, however, that's yes, it developed differently, didn't it? On the one hand, this leadership is no longer so clear, there have been many political disputes. Suddenly, very recently, there have been so many developments in the last few months where the federal government, i.e. the national level, has handed over this control sovereignty and, in the spirit of federalism, has transferred it to the federal states, which then acted at their own discretion which meant that it was different between the countries, uh, that there was more debate about it in public and that the systems are no longer completely harmonized (Government_2 Austria).

Further, some of aspects of the government's COVID-19 response come under critique. For example, conducting a review of the government's ordinances in relation to the COVID-19 management the Constitutional Court, it came to the verdict that some of the government's ordinances banning visits to private households during the first lockdown were unconstitutional.

With the pandemic ongoing some segments of society became dissatisfied with the government's pandemic management. Issues were ongoing lockdown as well as vaccination and in particular the mandatory vaccination. The polarisation of the people in Austria (around vaccination) was also fuelled by the FPÖ. From the beginning, the party opposed the government's measures and participated in the demonstrations against the government. Because of the FPÖ leader Herbert Kickl, many half-truths and fake news about Corona have made it into parliament. For example, on May 26, 2021, he caused a stir in Parliament with the following thesis: "Governments and agencies are coercing their healthy citizens to be participants in a huge genetic engineering experiment - outcome uncertain."

3.1.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

The Austrian government, understand vulnerable groups as those who are at higher risk of suffering from severe symptoms and to whom the disease could potentially be life-threatening: these are people aged over 65 years as well as people with (chronic) pre-existing conditions of all ages (ref). The most important document in relation to this is the so called COVID-19 Risikogruppen-Verordnung (COVID-19 risk order). The order itself was updated but never extended beyond health vulnerabilities. As a government representative point out, the focus was on medical indicators:

"We solved this through a legal perspective... that these under quotation marks vulnerable groups who are still active on the labour market... they were defined and they are allowed... more or less... to permanently work in home office. That means that there is a definition. There are medical indicators and there is the right for these people to stay in the labour market, but just from their homes." (Government_1, Austria)

The other important document in relation to defining vulnerability in Austria is the document that outlined the prioritisation for the COVID-19 vaccination, established by the NIG (Nationales Impfgremium/National Vaccination Committee). This was the roadmap to Austria's vaccination program⁶

“Finally, this was done by the “national” definition. More specifically through the NIG through the prioritisation they established in terms of vaccination. We know that vulnerability is the age of a person, particular medical constellations, this means risk factors and exposure. This is not a bad definition. So, if you think about it, you can even observe this.” (Government_2, Austria)

The document outlines, on the one hand, health risks like chronic disease or pre-existing conditions and, on the other hand, exposure to the virus (in a work setting). The focus on exposure adds a different layer to the definition of vulnerability: it moves beyond a focus on health status towards the likelihood of getting infected due to exposure during work. Nonetheless, the focus on health outcomes remained. However, focusing on exposure meant that teachers or health care staff were recommended for early vaccination. In Austria, these are often professions with lower income and a high percentage of women in the workforce. As such, the focus shifted, to some extent, to groups who felt the negative social impact of COVID-19 more strongly.

The protection of high-risk groups was regulated through the social insurance law (Sozialversicherungsgesetz).⁷ The measures taken to protect these groups encompass home office, paid leave, protective gear and so on. However, these measures are not mandatory for employers and there is no right to home office in Austria. Another health-related measure aimed at protecting pregnant women from the risk of infection at their workplace. They had the right to premature maternity leave.⁸ Similarly, employees got granted additional four weeks of paid time off work between the 1st of November 2020 and the 9th of July 2021 if they have caretaking responsibilities towards children under 14 or people living with disability or relatives in need of care. However, once schools reopened for supervision, special care taking allowance was no longer possible. To mitigate economic vulnerabilities the government temporarily increased the social support for people out of work who are no longer eligible for unemployment money due to the ongoing COVID-19 crisis.⁹ Additionally, already in March 2020, the Austrian government provided a first aid package (€38 Billion) to battle the negative economic outcome of the Corona virus and related lockdown as well as other measures. This included the short work scheme where employers remove employees from their payroll and

⁶<https://www.aekktn.at/documents/e031f3c0-4066-11eb-a558-5254009ad2fe/Empfehlung%20des%20Nationalen%20Impfgremiums%20zur%20Priorisierung%20von%20COVID-19-Impfungendocx.pdf>.

⁷ <https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/Bundesnormen/NOR40223704/NOR40223704.html>

⁸ https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2021_I_44/BGBLA_2021_I_44.pdf#sig

⁹ <https://irihs.ihs.ac.at/id/eprint/5388/7/ihs-report-2020-hofer-titelbach-fink-oesterreich-arbeitsmarktpolitik-covid-19.pdf>

have their wages subsidised by the government, financial hardship fund (Härtefallfond) for small enterprises and one person companies, a Corona fund, and a fixed expenses subsidy program (IHS 2020 May, Desson 2020). The Härtefallfond ended in May 2022 and the fixed expenses subsidy program already ran out in August 2021.

We could only identify one analysis of vulnerability conducted by the Ministry of Health¹⁰. The document primarily engages with people at risk of poverty and social exclusion. It also discusses people disabilities, single parents, children, older people, and people in need of care as vulnerable groups. Other dimensions such as race, ethnicity, sexuality, legal status found little attention in government documents. While also other stakeholders involved in the pandemic response acknowledged the negative impact of COVID-19 on socially vulnerable groups, no mitigation strategies were introduced to address these vulnerabilities by the government.

“Social factors are a bit underrepresented in the National Vaccination Committee also because it is harder to measure. But now we know of course: people who live together in overcrowded conditions, with ever-changing actors...this is particularly the case in workers' accommodations, for example, are particularly at risk.” (Government_1, Austria)

Over time, children became part of the public discourse as a vulnerable group due to school closures. The Ministry of Education addressed the extent of school closures, deciding that restrictions would be reduced to an absolute minimum and would be in line with regulations in other areas of life. The goal is to ensure continuous attendance classes and, depending on the risk situation, to implement targeted security and prevention measures at individual school locations. Finally, many stakeholders acknowledged the negative secondary effects such as loneliness that were created through lockdowns and social distancing measures. These effects were considered in the pandemic management, particularly after the second COVID-19 wave by trying to avoid lockdowns as much as possible.

¹⁰https://www.sozialministerium.at/dam/jcr:5f807a53-5dce-4395-8981-682b5f1dc23b/BMSGPK_Analyse-der-sozialen-Lage.pdf

3.2 Belgium

3.2.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population) structure of government, pandemic planning pre-COVID

Belgium is a federal state with a relatively complex three-level structure. At the top level are the federal state, the communities, and the regions. The Prime Minister and the ministers hold executive power at the federal government level. Each of the federated entities has their own parliament or unicameral council (Gerken & Merkur, 2010). The federal state and the federated entities are on equal footing from a legal viewpoint, but they have different powers and responsibilities. Below the top level is the level of the provinces, and at the bottom of the governmental 'pyramid' there are the communes. Depending on the type of power exercised, the provinces and the communes are under the supervision of the Federal State, a community, or a Region (belgium.be, 2021).

Belgium had set up a National Focal Point (NFP) over the course of 2007 and 2008. The NFP is responsible for coordinating the analysis of national public health events, as well as for communication with the WHO IHR contact points. Besides the NFP, the Belgian monitoring and risk management system has two other main actors: the Risk Assessment Group (RAG) and the Risk Management Group (RMG). The RAG analyses the risk to the population based on epidemiological and scientific data and consists of the health authorities of the federal government and the federated entities; epidemiologists from Sciensano, and other experts with specific knowledge about health risks. The RAG provides advice to the RMG, and the RMG then uses this advice to decide on public health measures (FPS Health, 2018). The RMG is chaired by the Belgian NFP and consists of representatives of the health administrations and all ministers of health. In case of a severe crisis, the RMG meets frequently to manage all health-related aspects of decision making (KCE, 2020).

A key actor in pandemic surveillance and monitoring is Sciensano, Belgium's national public health institute. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, Sciensano's epidemiological department met once a week to discuss signal detection of a series of epidemiological indicators, where they could decide whether to not to send an alert in case signals were detected somewhere in Belgium (Desson et al., 2020). In the case of an epidemic, the epidemiological department supports the authorities in decision-making by providing an epidemiological description.

3.2.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

Throughout the COVID-19 crisis, federal decisions were made through various consultation structures. Initially, two medical advisory groups, RAG and RMG, along with the economic authorities, ERMG, and an Expert Strategy Exit Group, GEES, provided information and advice to the National Security Council (NVR). The RAG and RMG already existed prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, while the ERMG and GEES were founded in March and April 2020 in response

to the pandemic (De Standaard, 2020a; NBB, 2020). Sciensano played a key role in data collection and set up an online dashboard reporting case information. Ministerial orders issued by the Minister of Security and Internal Affairs executed federal measures agreed upon within the National Security Council and the Consultative Committee. The National Crisis Centre oversees drawing up guidelines for applying the decrees, while crisis communication strategies are coordinated jointly by the FPS Public Health and the NCCN.

Regional and local governments have the power to enact (stricter) measures at their level. Communities are responsible for health education and preventive health care, and the Flemish Department of Welfare, Public Health and Family is responsible for elderly care, youth welfare, and various other health and welfare services. Education, culture, and care for the elderly are also the responsibilities of federated entities, with communities in charge of developing protocols to regulate access to schools, theatres, and sports activities. The governors of Belgian provinces and the mayors of cities also have the power to enforce local measures and initiatives, such as curfews. Although the federal government designed and issued COVID-19 measures, regional and local governments had the power to enact stricter measures at their level until the end of the federal phase in March 2022.

The COVID-19 pandemic has varying effects on different groups of people, influenced by socio-economic status and ethnicity (Geldof, 2020b). In Belgium, there is a lack of specific data on how COVID-19 burden differs among cultural, religious, or ethnic minority populations, but higher fatality rates have been observed in impoverished neighborhoods, including Brussels (Desson et al., 2020). Pre-existing inequalities exacerbate the impact of preventive measures. Temporary employees and those in undeclared work face financial consequences (Geldof, 2020a), and the lockdown measures can lead to increased poverty and social inequality (ibid.). Lack of access to technology and suitable workspaces hampered education, particularly for children whose parents don't speak fluent French or Dutch (De Standaard, 2020b).

Legal factors have also shaped the government's response. Measures affecting fundamental rights were implemented through a ministerial decree based on the 2007 Civil Security Act, designed for acute emergencies but not long-term health crises (Verbergt, 2020b). The caretaker administration in Belgium was granted special powers to address the pandemic's impact (Rankin, 2020). Economic considerations further complicate decision-making. The Economic Risk Management Group plays a role in monitoring the impact, ensuring business continuity, and coordinating measures to mitigate economic consequences (NBB, 2020).

COVID-19 management in Belgium overtime

Looking chronologically at the main COVID-19 measures implemented in Belgium, the crisis can be divided into some key periods. A full overview of these measures and links to ministerial decisions are provided [here](#) by the National Crisis Centre.

- In March 2020, a lockdown begins in Belgium in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, lasting until May. During this time, the capacity for testing and tracing has been

expanded. Over the summer, measures are relaxed, with mouth masks mandatory in most public spaces.

- In Autumn/Winter 2020 cases rise again and from October, measures are taken to stop the spread of the virus. Restrictions are made tighter during the winter and last until later in the spring of 2021.
- During the Spring/Summer of 2021, the vaccination campaign was at full steam, and measures were relaxed considerably. By August 2021, most adults in Belgium had had an opportunity to get their first COVID-19 vaccine.
- But by Autumn/Winter 2021, starting from October COVID-19 case rates were on the rise again, and far-reaching measures were gradually introduced once more in Belgium. This included the adoption of the ‘corona barometer’, supporting policy preparation and communication. The barometer consisted of three phases: code yellow, orange and red. From March, the booster shot was also required for the Covid Safe ticket.
- In Spring 2022, following improving COVID-19 case rates, COVID-19 measures were gradually relaxed and lifted. A second booster was available.

The WG SIC was established in Spring 2020 to monitor and evaluate the socio-economic impact of the pandemic, while the Taskforce for Vulnerable Groups focuses on the impact of the pandemic on different vulnerable groups (FPS Social Security, 2020). The GEES was replaced by Celeval, an evaluation unit based at the Crisis Centre of the Federal Public Service (FPS) Internal Affairs in August 2020, and the Consultation Committee took over federal responsibility for the COVID-19 response in October 2020 (HLN, 2020). Celeval became paralyzed due to disagreements between its members, and the RAG was tasked with submitting recommendations in November 2020 (Lefevere, 2020). In mid-December 2020, GEMS, an advisory group consisting of 24 medical experts, was established to coordinate the different groups and committees involved in the COVID-19 government responses. The Corona Commissariat, led by "Corona Commissioner" Pedro Facon, was established in September 2020 to coordinate these efforts, and was formally rescinded in April 2022.

Two years into the pandemic, the so-called ‘federal phase’ of governance of the COVID-19 pandemic in Belgium finished in March 2022. This means that regional authorities, governors, and local administrations are now legally in charge again of managing the pandemic (Nationaal Crisiscentrum, 2022). As in many other countries, the Belgian government had to perform a balancing act between protecting public health and protecting economic interests. The Belgian economy experienced significant decreases in turnover across various sectors, but signs of recovery have emerged (FOD Economie, 2022). Job losses were relatively low, and positive trends were observed in the employment situation (*Ibid*).

In summary, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated existing inequalities and presented challenges in health, education, religion, and the economy in Belgium. Efforts to address these disparities and mitigate their impact remain crucial. Experts commonly discuss the complexity of the Belgian governance system and crisis structure was a common topic, which hindered

the COVID-19 response due to confusion and inefficiency resulting from the division of responsibilities and tensions among different levels of government. For instance, contact tracing was the responsibility of communities, leading to complications when individuals had contacts in different communities. A major lesson learned is that these tensions between federal and local levels of government need to continue to be addressed. One respondent acknowledges that this is a big, structural issue:

“The ‘big guys’ must learn to work together, because they have a common goal. But that’s a problem in the structure of this country.” (Government_7, Belgium)

One expert also lamented the complexity of the Belgian COVID-19 governance system. She indicated that the collaboration went well in situations where the responsibilities were clear, and different actors/representatives had similar responsibilities and interests. However, when different people sitting around the same table had very different responsibilities, this complicated decision-making. She also pointed out the tensions in the coordination between federal and regional levels of decision-making, which she thought was often related to financial considerations.

“There is also definitely a tension between federal and regional. And that is mostly to do with money, I feel. Who takes care of what funding? And then, of course, there is also a little bit of power involved, so then you notice that politics also uses that, like – ‘I’m going to grant you this, but then I want that in return’. And then you see that those political agendas no longer match the scientific agendas. And then there is both a tension federal-regional, but also between the administrations and the cabinets. Where normally the Agency for Care and Health [at the Flemish level] should have the same voice as the Beke cabinet, you notice that a political and a scientific agenda are opposing each other there. And that also makes it kind of difficult. There were many different layers in the policy, and many different players, with many different agendas, where health was not the only one.” (Government_3, Belgium)

Belgian's COVID-19 policy was criticized by some of the experts for being reactive and short-term, lacking transparency and long-term planning. Organizations set up to deal with the pandemic were closed and plans for a Belgium Emergency Management Agency are uncertain. Local actors and organizations were also challenged due to the fragmentation of social welfare, necessitating increased contact with grassroots-level organizations. The crisis highlighted the importance of addressing the complexity of governance structures, investing in long-term collaboration, and trust-building with local communities. For example, one expert interviewed stated:

“People should see it as an opportunity, as a wake-up call. We need to ensure that we have ties to the communities. We should not have blind spots about our people, our citizens. We have to go more into the communities through trusted figures, and go through community organizations, and be present. To give information in a good and appropriate way, through people who have street credibility and who are trustworthy to the people involved.” (Government_2, Belgium)

Many local organizations or initiatives were given by interviewees as examples of good practices. Apparently in some regions this worked well, for example the neighborhood-oriented approach in Antwerpen and Gent worked well. However, this was not the case in all of Belgium, with some local governments failing to pick up on this and instead copying the central story. The expert quoted below highlighted the Brussels-based organisation Foyer as a good example. Foyer works with local community organisations to communicate with and provide support for their members by creating COVID information videos in many different languages.

“[Foyer] has a lot of feeling with the area. They know the communities inside out, and they are based in those neighborhoods. I don’t think the Agency [Flemish public health government agency] always had that same level of contact.” (Government_1, Belgium)

As the COVID-19 pandemic progressed, it became increasingly evident that different groups of people were affected differently by the virus. Experts interviewed expressed their concern that there is still much unknown about how to reach specific groups in society, and this dilemma is related to the collection of disaggregated data. Disaggregated data, such as data by migration background, would provide much more insight into how some groups are disproportionately affected, yet there are fears that such data collection may lead to further stigmatization and discrimination. This was mentioned by multiple experts:

“The data story is also a very important one. [...] You give a mandate to the field where they have to start designing actions and interventions for sensitization to specific groups, almost on an individual level, but there wasn’t the data infrastructure to supply those teams with enough data.” (Government_6, Belgium)

It was however also discussed by one interviewee how in emergency situations, there are limited resources and capacity to carry out tailored approaches for the population.

“At a certain point you obviously get saturated and you’re left with numbers of people where that [personalised approach] hardly works. At the peak of this fourth wave, some people simply cannot be called anymore [in contact tracing] and they are sent text messages instead. You can easily understand that this is of far lesser quality than a careful conversation over the phone, or seeing people in person. Quantity takes priority over quality at a certain point otherwise you miss 95% of people.” (Government_5, Belgium)

Nonetheless, the experts also noted that there has been an improvement in the response over time. The government started to focus more on the broader and indirect impacts of the COVID-19 crisis, including contact tracing efforts, focus on vulnerable groups, and collaboration between different actors. Certain groups became more considered in governmental communication strategies through efforts to develop targeted communication practices for specific groups of people.

Public react to the crisis management in Belgium

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on people's behaviour and well-being. According to the expert interviews, trust, and willingness to cooperate were high in the early stages of the pandemic, but over time, people became impatient with personal measures, and government measures lacked transparency and consistency with a “yo-yo effect of loosening and tightening restrictions” (*Government_5, Belgium*). This led to a decline in trust and cooperation where winning back trust became challenging, with conspiracy theories posing a threat, as the expert interviewed below discusses.

“I would say that trust did diminish, and as a government we were also somewhat responsible for that. I think we could have done a lot better on the communications platform, done a lot more connecting. I also think that the fact that the policy has been changed so many times - yes, then you do undermine your own credibility a bit. [...] So I would say that trust in government has gone down.” (*Government_3, Belgium*)

Another interviewee claimed that this trust was already a problem before the crisis:

“If I'm honest, I don't think you solve during a corona crisis what has become skewed over the course of decades. If you fail to really engage people in society, ensure that there are contacts between groups, that people have a sense of 'we belong,' then you can't just fix that during such a crisis. Because it's deep-seated.” (*Government_2, Belgium*)

However, experts in the interviews noted that Belgium appears to have experienced fewer conspiracy theories than other parts of the world.

A team of researchers from various Belgian universities conducted the "Motivation Barometer" survey between July 2020 and May 2022, monitoring the motivation, connectedness, and psychological health of the Belgian population (Motivation Barometer, 2023). The survey found that strict measures did not necessarily lead to decreased or increased motivation and people were more likely to follow strict measures if they saw them as meaningful and consistent. Empathetic messages that fostered motivation were also crucial. Furthermore, as COVID-19 case rates increased, risk awareness also increased, leading to a greater motivation to comply with restrictive measures. According to the Barometer (2023), if a variant with serious health consequences arose, 80% of people would accept vaccination. Further findings from the barometer were that vaccination hesitancy was not fixed, and rewarding or sanctioning individuals did not necessarily lead to increased vaccination intentions. Instead, building trust and understanding is crucial, particularly among healthcare workers, to increase vaccination rates and compliance with restrictive measures. This corresponds with what one of the experts said:

“The fact that we have had a reactive policy, and have not communicated sufficiently, has also reduced support. We have presented vaccines as the panacea, when it has quickly become apparent that they are not... And I still maintain that vaccines work very well, but for serious illness and hospitalization, not on a transmission basis. We have promised the

realm of freedom, and it hasn't arrived. First, one needs to communicate more clearly, and second, you also must acknowledge your mistakes.” (Government_7, Belgium):

Figure 1. Motivation and adherence during the COVID-19 pandemic in Belgium

3.2.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

In Belgium, efforts to identify socially vulnerable groups in the COVID-19 are linked to attempts to design and implement specific measures and interventions to address the difficulties these groups face. This happened primarily through the creation of several working groups and task forces at the different governmental levels, the most important ones being the Working Group Social Impact COVID-19 crisis and the Vulnerable Group Task Force at the federal level, and the Task Force on Vulnerable Families and Social Emergency Task Force at the Flemish and Walloon level respectively. These working groups and task forces did not exist prior to the pandemic but were installed in the course of the first corona wave (i.e., spring 2020). The working groups and task forces focused primarily on those groups that were at risk of falling through the safety net of socio-economic measures. For example, the Working Group Social Impact COVID-19 crisis documented the impact on groups such as sex workers, disabled people, job students, those with precarious employment, artists, families with children etc. Examples of vulnerable groups identified by the Vulnerable Group Taskforce include homeless people, people with precarious jobs, prisoners, single-parent families, children from vulnerable families, sex workers, people with no or limited access to the internet, undocumented migrants, and persons with disabilities.

At the beginning of the pandemic there was a very strong focus on trying to contain the virus and little attention was paid to how the pandemic and the measures to control it could impact different groups of people differently. As pointed out by one of the experts “...*the sole focus was on the health aspect. ‘This has to be closed and this has to be closed because of the infections.’*” (Government_4, Belgium). While this lack of attention for vulnerable groups of people is acknowledged, the government representative also pointed out that in the early stages of the pandemic a full national lockdown was considered the only feasible option:

“The situation at the time was that a lockdown was the only thing that could be done. And no, I don’t think they thought about ‘what could be the impact on vulnerable people?’. No, I don’t think so. But even if they would have thought about that, could they have decided something else? Probably not. And we also have to be honest about that” (Government_4, Belgium)

At the same time, it quickly became clear that the COVID-19 crisis affected specific groups of people more heavily than others and as the pandemic progressed, attempts for more targeted support measures were made. For instance, the Vulnerable Groups Task Force encouraged leniency for migrants who could not return to their country of origin and had difficulties in proving their legal residence status. Furthermore, the Taskforce also introduced various measures to protect the health and wellbeing of those without secure housing (e.g. an extension of facilities to offer shelter and psycho-medical-social support for homeless people and offering food aid to anyone living below the poverty threshold regardless of their legal status). Another important sector in which some groups of people were more heavily affected than others, was education. For instance, during times of school closures, not all families could provide their children with access to a computer, internet, and a quiet space to work. As a response to this, investments into ICT material and support to try to ‘seal the digital gap’ were made. Also in governmental communication strategies, attempts to develop targeted communication strategies for specific groups of people were made, for instance by translating COVID-19 messages into a range of other languages besides the country’s official languages.

While an initial focus on containing infection rates was relatively quickly broadened by trying to take into consideration the pandemic’s diverging impact on different groups of people, the reality that vulnerable groups were not considered proactively remains a criticism. Indeed, the fact that government responses failed to clearly describe vulnerable groups and proactively include them in their strategy to combat the COVID-19 pandemic is described as a ‘*missed opportunity*’ by a governance actor from the Federal Ministry of Public Health, who underlined the need for a more multidisciplinary perspective in crisis management:

“... there are a lot of vulnerable families with five children living in a small studio. I think it was a missed opportunity, when we determined the rules for the lockdown, that we didn’t include someone with a more multidisciplinary perspective in the conversation. Because, sure, the lockdown was necessary, but perhaps we could have done a few small things differently to make it easier for those families.” (Government_3, Belgium)

It has become widely known that pre-existing inequalities in Belgium have had an impact on how people experienced the measures taken to prevent the spread of COVID-19, and that existing structural inequalities have become even more severe in various sectors (e.g. education). The emotional impact of the COVID-19 measures has also become a point of attention as the pandemic progressed. For instance, a study shows that for a lot of children and young people the loss of the social aspect of education due to school closures had a big impact on their mental wellbeing (Gambi & De Witte, 2021). One of the experts also addressed the emotional impact of lockdown measures on singles who lived alone and experienced increased feelings of loneliness:

“... especially during lockdown periods, [living alone] was not easy. Because as a couple or when you live together as a family, you still have those contacts. But when you live by yourself you have nothing or no one, no shoulder to cry on or someone you can share something nice with or arms to comfort you if something happens, or whatever.”
(Government_4, Belgium)

On the other hand, for family’s lockdowns did not always mean they could find comfort and companionship with each other. Especially for large families living in small apartments, stay-at-home measures could “drive people crazy” (Government_1, Belgium). In this context, experts also highlighted a drastic rise in domestic violence:

“We also saw more violence in general, a tremendous rise in domestic violence due to COVID. When you are 7 people living in a small apartment, try keeping people inside.”
(Government_1, Belgium)

On a more general level, the COVID-19 pandemic also lay bare underlying issues of trust in the government and feelings of belonging in society. In that sense, vulnerability was also put into a wider perspective requiring a broader answer that was considered beyond the scope of crisis-management.

3.3 England

3.3.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

The United Kingdom (UK) consists of Wales, England, Scotland, and Northern Ireland.¹¹ The UK is a constitutional monarchy and parliamentary democracy (ibid). A parliamentary democracy means that UK nationals have the power to elect their legislative representatives, whose work is to present the citizen's interests to the government (ibid). The UK is also a welfare state. Welfare benefits in the UK include five separate groups of services, which are cash benefits, health care, education, housing, and the personal social services.¹²

The UK government and devolved administrations, along with the emergency services and other local responders, have clear responsibilities for identifying, assessing, preparing for and responding to emergencies, as well as supporting affected communities to recover.¹³ Government has risk management processes in place that aim to identify risks (including risks to individual government organisations and short-term risks to the UK as a whole), to ensure that plans are drawn up to mitigate risks and prepare for shocks, and to prevent risks from being overlooked despite short-term pressures (ibid). With a focus on documents relating to risk, the UK has a national risk register that provides an overview of the risks of huge emergencies that could potentially affect the UK, looking ahead two years at a time.¹⁴ Updated every two years, the last register was updated in 2020. Pandemics were rated as the highest likelihood and impact (ibid).

The Cabinet Office, through its Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS), is responsible for coordinating the government's planning for, and response to, major emergencies.¹⁵ Individual departments and other public sector organisations are responsible for identifying and managing risks (ibid). The Department of Health and Social Care, for example, is responsible for planning for the health and social care impacts of health-related risks (ibid).

As mentioned in the D4.1 report, the Civil Contingencies Act and accompanying measures provide the framework for civil protection in the UK, including the activities that relative entities (Category 1) such as the Police, National Health System (NHS) and Fire Department must implement in an emergency. At a local level in England and Wales, the afore-mentioned responders are prepared for emergencies through Local Resilience Forums (LRFs). Note that

¹¹ United Kingdom Government: Type & Structure. (n.d.). Retrieved April 24, 2023, from

<https://study.com/learn/lesson/united-kingdom-government-type-structure-system-britain.html>

¹² Faher, N. (n.d.). *Country case studies and links*. European Welfare States - Information and Resources. Retrieved April 14, 2023, from https://sites.pitt.edu/~heinisch/ca_brit.html

¹³ Comptroller, & Auditor General. (n.d.). (rep.). *The government's preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons for government on risk management*.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-risk-register-2020>

¹⁵ Comptroller, & Auditor General. (n.d.). (rep.). *The government's preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons for government on risk management*.

LRFs have an important role for their communities in the response and recovery from emergencies.¹⁶ Strategic Coordinating Groups (SCGs) also operate at a local level, with documents outlining how it would be likely for the SCGs to be convened in the event of a pandemic to take overall responsibility for the multi-agency management at a local level.¹⁷ Note that SCGs are essentially groups which are responsible for the multi-agency administration of the emergency and to establish the policy and strategic framework within which tactical and operational command and coordinating groups will operate.¹⁸

Before the COVID-19 pandemic broke out, the UK possessed a 2011 UK Influenza Preparedness Strategy.¹⁹ The afore-mentioned plans are frequently reviewed to reflect the most up-to-date expert advice.²⁰ One way of making sure the plans are fit for purpose is via exercises, which are performed both locally and nationally across various parts of the health system to stress-test policies (ibid). One such cross-government exercise to test the UK's response to a serious influenza pandemic was Exercise Cygnus.²¹ However, Exercise Cygnus did feed into pandemic preparedness plans that informed the UK COVID-19 response (ibid).

After Exercise Cygnus, the CCS and DHSC, collaborating across government and with stakeholders including the Devolved Administrations, formed a draft Pandemic Influenza Bill.¹³ This draft legislation, to be utilised in the event of a future influenza pandemic, laid out the legislative easements required to support local and national response activities, as recommended in one of the four key learnings from Exercise Cygnus (ibid).

3.3.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

As already mentioned in the D4.1 deliverable, when the COVID-19 virus first reached the UK, the four nations of the UK collaborated their efforts to respond to the pandemic. Around mid-March 2020, Boris Johnson, the former UK Prime Minister, released new ministerial structures to respond to the pandemic.²² As mentioned in the D4.1 Baseline Report, the structures

¹⁶<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-role-of-local-resilience-forums-a-reference-document>

¹⁷ Comptroller, & Auditor General. (n.d.). (rep.). *The government's preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons for government on risk management*.

¹⁸ Command, control and coordination. (2013, October 23). Retrieved April 24, 2023, from [https://www.college.police.uk/app/civil-emergencies/civil-contingencies/command-control-and-coordination#:~:text=development%20\(CPD\),Strategic%20coordinating%20group,levels%20of%20command%20will%20operate](https://www.college.police.uk/app/civil-emergencies/civil-contingencies/command-control-and-coordination#:~:text=development%20(CPD),Strategic%20coordinating%20group,levels%20of%20command%20will%20operate).

¹⁹ Department of Health and Social Care. (2014). UK influenza pandemic preparedness strategy. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/review-of-the-evidence-base-underpinning-the-uk-influenza-pandemic-preparedness-strategy>

²⁰ (N.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-pandemic-preparedness/uk-pandemic-preparedness>

²¹ Department of Health and Social Care. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-pandemic-preparedness/annex-a-about-exercise-cygnus>

²² Prime Minister's Office, 10 Downing Street, Cabinet Office, Department of Health and Social Care, Foreign & Commonwealth Office, HM Treasury, Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, and The Rt Hon

included four new implementation committees focusing predominantly on health, public sector preparedness, economy, and international response. All structures directly fed into the daily COVID-19 briefings led by Boris Johnson. In June 2020, the committees were replaced by the ‘COVID-19 Strategy’ and the ‘COVID-19 Operations’ cabinet.

With a particular focus on the governmental reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic, the initial reaction was one of optimism. During an opening statement from a press conference (19 March 2020) on Coronavirus, former Prime Minister Boris Johnson said:

“I do think, looking at it all, that we can turn the tide within the next 12 weeks And I am absolutely confident that we can send coronavirus packing in this country but only if we take the steps, we all take the steps we have outlined ...”²³

In terms of what documents were followed when the COVID-19 pandemic first broke out in the UK, the UK government mainly used the Coronavirus Act 2020,²⁴ an emergency legislation approved by Parliament on 25 March 2020.²⁵ The act provided the government with the powers it wanted to combat the COVID-19 pandemic in the UK (ibid).

The pandemic influenza draft legislation was important in producing the basis of the Coronavirus Act 2020.²⁶ What this meant is that departments had already taken into consideration many of the implications a pandemic would have on their department and the legal powers they would require (ibid). A few examples of legislative easements extracted from the draft pandemic influenza bill that were then used for the Coronavirus Act included:

1. Emergency registration of healthcare professionals – in March 2020, barriers were removed to bring back thousands of suitably experienced people to the health and social care workforce, such as formerly retired NHS staff (ibid);
2. Indemnity for healthcare workers – this allowed ministers to offer indemnity for clinical negligence liabilities emerging from health service activities (ibid).

Boris Johnson MP. (2020). New government structures to coordinate response to coronavirus. Retrieved May 26, 2021, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/new-government-structures-to-coordinate-response-to%20%20coronavirus>

²³ Walker, P. (2020, March 19). Boris Johnson: UK can turn tide of Coronavirus in 12 weeks. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/19/boris-johnson-uk-can-turn-tide-of-coronavirus-in-12-weeks>

²⁴ Coronavirus act 2020. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2020/7/contents/enacted>

²⁵ Responding to covid-19 and the Coronavirus Act 2020. (n.d.). Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://committees.parliament.uk/work/310/responding-to-covid-19-and-the-coronavirus-act-2020/>

²⁶(2020). Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-pandemic-preparedness/uk-pandemic-preparedness>

In March 2020, the government published the coronavirus action plan.²⁷ Pandemic influenza plans, strengthened following recommendations from Exercise Cygnus, and prior outbreaks, were able to be adjusted rapidly to form the coronavirus action plan, taking into consideration the differences between the virus that causes influenza and the virus that causes COVID-19 (ibid). To view the specifics of the phases, read more about the coronavirus action plan [here](#).

With regard to whether there were any barriers to implementation of what was planned, an example includes difficulties sustaining social distancing in public (due to the actions of other people or environmental constraints), the need to provide or receive support from family and friends, social isolation, missing loved ones, and mental health impacts, viewing the risks as low, social pressure to not comply, and difficulties understanding and keeping abreast of changing rules.²⁸

In terms of changes to the response, the UK government, during the T1 phase, adopted the concept of “herd immunity” when responding to the COVID-19 pandemic.²⁹ Herd immunity translates to indirect protection from an infectious disease that happens when a population is immune either through vaccination or immunity developed through previous infection.³⁰ Following simulations carried out by the Imperial College COVID-19 response team, however, it was revealed that hospitals would be severely overwhelmed.³¹ It was at this point of time when the UK eventually introduced social distancing measures (ibid).

Changes in crisis response in England

With regard to changes in crisis response, the UK government, in September 2021, published its ‘COVID-19 Response: Autumn and Winter Plan,’ to control the COVID-19 virus during the

²⁷ Department of Health and Social Care. (2020, March 03). Coronavirus (COVID-19) action plan. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/coronavirus-action-plan>

²⁸ Wright, L., Paul, E., Steptoe, A., & Fancourt, D. (2022, March 24). Facilitators and barriers to compliance with covid-19 guidelines: A structural topic modelling analysis of free-text data from 17,500 UK adults - BMC public health. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889021-12372-6#:~:text=Identified%20barriers%20were%20difficulties%20maintaining,risks%20as%20low%2C%20social%20pressure.>

²⁹Neuman, S. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.npr.org/sections/coronavirus-live/updates/2021/10/12/1045219737/the-u-k-s-early-approach-to-pandemic-cost-thousands-of-lives-a-new-report-says>

³⁰ (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/herd-immunity-lockdowns-and-covid-19#:~:text=What%20is%20%27herd%20immunity%27%3F,immunity%20developed%20through%20previous%20infection.>

³¹ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/medicine/sph/ide/gida-fellowships/Imperial-College-COVID19-NPI-modelling-16-03-2020.pdf>

colder months.³² Then, in February 2022, the UK government revealed the ‘Living with COVID-19’ plan.³³ According to an Institute for Government press release, the government “has clearly decided to try to move quickly to an approach in which COVID is treated similarly to other infectious diseases, emphasising personal responsibility and reducing the amount the state spends on COVID mitigations.”³⁴

Examples of barriers and problems faced during this timeframe include:

1. The revelation of government scandals regarding COVID-19 contracts. At the time of reporting, it was noted that former Cabinet Office Minister Steve Barclay refused to reveal meeting minutes and correspondence referring to £3.5 billion of COVID contracts that were awarded without tender to companies with associations to the conservative party.³⁵
2. The spread of misinformation. As of January 11, 2023, the Conservative Party suspended a lawmaker for the spread of misinformation regarding COVID-19 vaccines.³⁶
3. Ongoing COVID-19 protests, such as anti-vaccination protests.³⁷

Regarding occurrences of multiple crises, Brexit, the war in Ukraine, and the outbreak of COVID-19 variants can be taken into consideration.

Positive developments that can be considered is the COVID-19 vaccine rollout which was considered to be a success in the UK.³⁸ As mentioned in the D4.5 report, former Prime Minister Boris Johnson’s 2022 New Year message revealed that the UK had met its target, and that the UK “doubled the speed of the booster roll out” (ibid).

About changes in responsibilities, the following information is relevant. During the T1 phase, Former Health Secretary Matt Hancock stepped down, due to breaching social distancing

³² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/covid-19-response-autumn-and-winter-plan-2021>

³³ Office, C. (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/covid-19-response-living-with-covid-19>

³⁴ Hodgkin, R. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.instituteforgovernment.org.uk/article/comment/governments-living-covid-19-plan-high-optimism-low-detail>

³⁵ (2021). Retrieved from <https://labour.org.uk/press/labour-accuses-government-of-a-corruption-cover-up-over-3-5-billion-of-tory-linked-covid-contracts/>

³⁶ (2023). Retrieved from <https://www.usnews.com/news/health-news/articles/2023-01-11/uk-conservatives-suspend-lawmaker-for-vaccine-misinformation>

³⁷ Stubbley, P. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/home-news/lockdown-protests-london-covid-vaccine-b1889966.html>

³⁸ Prime Minister celebrates success of vaccine programme in New Year's message. (2021). Retrieved 24 June 2022, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/prime-minister-celebrates-success-of-vaccine-programme-in-new-years-message>

guidance.³⁹ Taking his place, Sajid David became the new Health Secretary from June 2021 to July 2022.⁴⁰ During this time (November 2020 to be precise), the UK created a new appointment of UK Vaccines Minister, who was appointed to Nadhim Zahawi.⁴¹ Then, during the T2 phase, current Prime Minister Rishi Sunak but former Chancellor of Exchequer was replaced by Nadhim Zahawi.⁴²

Reflections on pandemic management in England

According to one of the governmental officials, the government did a lot in terms of ensuring the continuation of public administration mechanisms and the provision of important services. That said, the government gave numerous options for all institutions to continue their work normally. These options include working from home, self-isolation, sick pay, testing infrastructure, protective behaviours, procedures to ensure the safety of people, and effective communication in various forms and languages.

Successes highlighted by the interviewee include implementing the required COVID-19 responses/policies. This includes laptops and desks and elements of virtual technology. With a focus on issues highlighted by the interviewee, it was mentioned that there were difficulties during the beginning of the pandemic in terms of shifting from face-to-face interactions to virtual interactions. The interviewee said that they needed 4-6 weeks to comprehend what worked and what did not with new technology.

Another interviewee highlighted successes in terms of addressing and identifying needs.

“I think what we did was successful. We identified some of the needs that were out there. We were able to implement a plan of action and care, but overall it shows the increases in deprivation.”

At the same time, issues were reflected upon. One interviewee explained that at a governmental level, it was difficult to aid vulnerable groups. At the time, the government felt it was better to manage issues centrally. As time passed, however, there was a realisation that it was better to provide money at a local governmental level.

³⁹ Helm, T., Savage, M., & Walker, P. (2021, June 26). Matt Hancock resigns as health secretary after day of humiliation. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://www.theguardian.com/politics/2021/jun/26/matt-hancock-resigns-after-questions-over-relationship-with-aide>

⁴⁰ (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-politics-43947008>

⁴¹ Busby, M. (2020, November 28). Nadhim Zahawi appointed minister in charge of covid-19 vaccine rollout. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://www.theguardian.com/politics/2020/nov/28/nadhim-zahawi-appointed-minister-in-charge-of-covid-19-vaccine-rollout>

⁴² (N.d). Retrieved from https://www.altfi.com/article/9506_nadhim-zahawi-becomes-chancellor-of-the-exchequer-amid-minister-resignations

The interviewee explained:

“This has been a lesson learnt from the UK government, certainly for England where there is too much population to be managed centrally. So objectives are now central but they are managed at the local government level.”

Public react to the crisis management and its changes in England

With a focus on public reaction to COVID-19 measures put in place to manage the COVID-19 crisis, compliance to social distancing measures is worth mentioning. As of 23 March 2020, it was announced that the UK police could issue ‘unlimited fines’ to those avoiding social distancing measures.⁴³ In response to these measures, people did break the rules, and as of 11 June 2020, statistics found that 15,715 Fixed Penalty Notices (FPNs) were recorded by forces in England up to 8 June 2020 for breaches of government public health regulations.⁴⁴

Referring to the interviews conducted with Government Officials, a number of reactions are worth noting in terms of public reaction to crisis management and its changes.

The first reaction concerns distrust among ethnic minorities. In one of the interviews, it was noted that in Birmingham, for example, there was a big issue with people refusing to go to hospital because of the belief that they would not come out alive. Unfortunately, a lot of people passed away at home because they would not call the ambulance. Due to the fear that minorities and low-income individuals felt, this eventually led to distrust.

“The most vulnerable people in particular those from the ethnic minorities had a level of distrust. It started with fear because they didn’t know what was going on so they were frightened. They did not get our messages out quick enough.”

Other reactions to bear in mind are disapproval with lockdowns and vaccines. Like most countries in the world, the UK did see the emergence of anti-lockdown and anti-vaccine protests.

3.3.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

In the UK, and according to the Health Protection (Coronavirus, Restrictions) (England) Regulations 2020, the vulnerable groups recognised were those over the age of 70, people below the age of 70 with an underlying health condition and pregnant women.⁴⁵ As already

⁴³ ITV News. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.itv.com/news/2020-03-23/boris-johnson-downing-street-coronavirus-update>

⁴⁴ (N.d.). Retrieved from <https://news.npcc.police.uk/releases/statistical-update-on-lockdown-fines-given-by-police-in-england-and-wales>

⁴⁵ The Health Protection (Coronavirus, Restrictions) (England) Regulations 2020. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2020/350/2020-06-13?view=plain>

discussed in the D4.1 deliverable, however, research on COVID-19 and vulnerable groups on the UK parliament website provided additional results regarding vulnerability. Below are some of the findings also mentioned in the D4.1 deliverable.

When the COVID-19 pandemic first emerged, vulnerabilities were acknowledged and addressed by the UK Government. As stated in the D4.1 Baseline Report, it was understood that not all people are familiar with digital services and do not possess the required equipment or monetary funds to own digital equipment. Accordingly, the UK government began providing laptops to disadvantaged school children as well as training courses to strengthen workplace skills and agreed measures with leading telecom companies to assist vulnerable customers to pay bills and remove caps on data allowances.

Also mentioned in the D4.1 report is mental health amongst the youth being acknowledged and addressed by the UK government. The UK government began funding specific charities to psychologically assist children and adolescents in need. In addition, the UK government also recognised that children were impacted by the school closures. Specifically, the UK government recognised the impact closures were having on children originating from disadvantaged families who have limited access to technological means and inadequate assistance from their parents in contrast to others. To close the “disadvantage gap,” the UK government released benefit measures such as additional funding for 2020-2021, a tutoring programme and strengthened assistance for remote learning.

Furthermore, people originating from ethnic minorities, and the homeless were also recognised as vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic. At the time, Public Health England (PHE) released an evidence report with propositions for the UK government on how to assure COVID-19 recovery strategies minimise existing health inequalities, while the government declared on 19 March 2020 that it would provide £1.6 billion for local authorities to address COVID-19 pressures. This includes services assisting the most vulnerable, e.g., homeless people.

In terms of how vulnerabilities changed over time, the following information is relevant:

Touching on ethnic minority vulnerabilities in further detail, the D4.5 report also states that the second wave of the COVID-19 pandemic (erupting at the beginning of September 2020) saw a higher proportion of people from Bangladeshi and Pakistani communities dying from COVID-19.⁴⁶ The predominant reason for this higher impact included the following factors:

⁴⁶ Minister of State for Inequalities (2022). *Inclusive Britain: government response to the Commission on Race and Ethnic Disparities. Command Paper CP 625*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/inclusive-britain-action-plan-government-response-to-the-commission-on-race-and-ethnic-disparities/inclusive-britain-government-response-to-the-commission-on-race-and-ethnic-disparities>. Retrieved on 23 June 2022.

1. Occupation (ibid);
2. Deprivation (ibid);
3. Household size (ibid);
4. Underlying health conditions being more widespread within certain communities (ibid);

Further into the COVID-19 pandemic timeline, and especially during the year of 2022, the D4.5 report noted vulnerabilities concerning those with access to the COVID-19 booster vaccine. The February 2022 Living with COVID-19 Plan reported UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) data on vaccine booster uptake recording outstanding disparities. At the time of reporting, it was noted that booster uptake was lowest among the Black and Pakistani adult populations (below 35%) with disparities also recorded between the least deprived (84%) and most deprived areas (53%), as well as low uptake among 18–24-year-olds (39%) (HM Cabinet Office, 2021). Regarding those ages 12-15, there were also large disparities noted concerning initial vaccine doses; the lowest numbers in the Gypsy/Roma, Irish Traveller, Black Caribbean, and Black African groups.

Finally, the UKHSA, on 13 May 2022, noted encouraging data on vaccine uptake among pregnant women but reported that inequalities remained within ethnic minorities (31% of black pregnant women had one or more vaccine doses compared to 58% white pregnant women) and with women from lower areas of impoverishment (38.9% of pregnant women in most impoverished areas had one or more doses in contrast to 71.1% in least deprived areas (UK Health Security Agency, 2022).

In one of the interviews conducted with a Government Official, the interviewee noted that one of the biggest issues early in the pandemic was assisting vulnerable people. The interviewee noted that the immediate response was providing food to the most vulnerable. The government response was compiling a set of policies to feed the most vulnerable, and to understand who they were and which groups to target.

“It became difficult because we also had ethnic minorities that do not have English as a first language. We have inequalities in the systems and COVID-19 shed light on these inequalities of the ethnic minorities and white working class”

Another interviewee gave a general overview of vulnerabilities throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. The vulnerabilities noted include:

- 1) Individuals who were vulnerable before the pandemic and received social and healthcare support. In their own words, the interviewee noted: *“The organisation had to think about how to provide them with support (e.g., food and medicines).”*

- 2) Vulnerable groups due to high risk of mortality from covid (obese, ethnic groups, ethnics communities). The interviewee commented: *“This required engagement with communities, also to avoid stigmatization and stereotypes.”*
- 3) People that are vulnerable due to limitations in everyday life because of isolation and social networks collapse. The interviewee added: *“This includes people with mental health and the so-called “just-about-coping people”, so people who are just able to pay their bills and that lost their job or went on furlough during the pandemic.”*

A few examples of how measures affected vulnerable groups or created new vulnerabilities are presented below.

Victims of Domestic Abuse

In the UK, and in most other countries across the globe, occurrences of violence at home rose drastically during COVID-19 lockdowns.⁴⁷ As stated in the D4.1 Baseline Report, it was this realisation that led the UK government to safeguard victims of domestic violence. New legislation, the formation of a Domestic Abuse Commissioner, monetary funds, availability of safe spaces, accommodation, and admittance to support services are just a few of the measures the UK government took into consideration. To strengthen the UK’s political response on this issue, the House of Commons Women and Equalities Committee performed an inquiry into the effect that COVID-19 and the measures to combat the virus were having on people with protected characteristics under the 2010 Equality Act.

Homeless people

In the UK, the government teamed up with charity organisations to provide people who were sleeping on the streets with accommodation during lockdown.⁴⁸ A scheme called ‘Everyone In’ was created, and this involved the government writing to all local authorities in England asking them to provide shelter to people sleeping rough, including those staying in hostels and night shelters (ibid).

Children

There were a few concerns brought up about the possible impact of coronavirus mitigation measures, such as school closures and social contact rules, on young people’s lives.⁴⁹ This included potential negative effects on educational attainment, mental health, and on children from disadvantaged backgrounds. Disruptions for children have concerned:

⁴⁷ Harrison, E. G., Giuffrida, A., Smith, H., & Liz Ford. (2020). Retrieved from

<https://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/mar/28/lockdowns-world-rise-domestic-violence>

⁴⁸ https://www.feantsa.org/public/user/Resources/magazine/2020/Full_Magazine_Autumn_2020.pdf

⁴⁹ Covid-19: Impact on child poverty and on Young People’s education ... (n.d.). Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/covid-19-impact-on-child-poverty-and-on-young-peoples-education-health-and-wellbeing/>

1. Education and skills (ibid);
2. Health and wellbeing (ibid);
3. Poverty and inequality (ibid);

Disabled people

In a 21 February 2021 the Health Foundation article titled ‘The Forgotten Crisis: Exploring the disproportionate impact of the pandemic on disabled people,’ it was reported that UK COVID-19 restrictions have had a disproportionate effect on aspects of disabled people’s lives.⁵⁰

In one interview conducted with a Government Official, it was disclosed that measures were put in place to help disabled communities. One example is that of the City Deaf Institute whereby universal messages were given and translated into sign languages in several languages. Q&A sessions were also established in different languages (e.g., Somali, Romani, Mandarin). Furthermore, there were targeted sessions for children and young people by using a different language than adults. In this way, tailored messages were delivered. The interviewee also released live on Instagram, while the organization commissioned partners to run Tik Tok campaigns.

⁵⁰ Sayce, L. (2021, February 21). The forgotten crisis: Exploring the disproportionate impact of the pandemic on disabled people. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://www.health.org.uk/news-and-comment/blogs/the-forgotten-crisis-exploring-the-disproportionate-impact-of-the-pandemic>

3.4 Germany

3.4.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

Governmental structure in Germany

Germany is a federal parliamentary democracy, with distinct legislative, executive, and judicial branches. The national parliament, or Bundestag, is currently comprised of 709 directly elected members. It is responsible for electing the Federal Chancellor, who proposes a cabinet comprising the federal executive branch or “government.” On a federal level, the Chancellor sets the top-level policy agenda, while cabinet ministers set policy agendas for their respective ministries. Most national-level legislation is proposed by the Federal Government and must be passed by the Bundestag with a simple majority of votes cast; some legislation also must be passed by the Bundesrat or federal council, which is composed of delegates from the state governments. This system of checks and balances ensures relative continuity in policy under normal circumstances.

Germany is comprised of 16 states, which enjoy significant administrative autonomy. Generally, the states are responsible for internal security, education policy, and cultural policy, as well as infrastructure and day-to-day administration. State parliaments or Landtag (the Berlin parliament is called the House of Representatives, while the Bremen and Hamburg parliaments are called the Citizenry) largely mirror the federal parliament in function, while state Ministers Presidents (in Berlin, Bremen, and Hamburg, Mayors) largely mirror the federal executive branch. The Minister President generally has the responsibility of setting an overall policy agenda and appointing cabinet ministers, who set the policy agendas for their respective state ministries (terminology can differ in Berlin, for instance, the mayor appoints a Senate rather than a cabinet, with Senate departments serving the function of ministries [e.g. the Senate Department for Health, Care and Equality]).

Coordination between the federal and state governments proved a contentious issue in the German COVID-19 response – particularly regarding risk communication, as indicated by interviewees in the target sub-national research site of Mannheim:

“I think it would also be helpful to have a discussion, for example, about the federal approach, which can be... we have a federal system, each state does it the way they o, but perhaps it would simply be helpful to agree on certain basic lines, at least, and then also adhere to them on the ground. I found it really helpful on site to quickly have clarity in communication structures, for example, in inpatient areas” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

Governmental structures vary slightly on the municipal level as well, but general adhere to certain patterns. A typical municipal governmental structure consists of a municipal council elected by citizens and a mayor elected either directly by citizens or by a municipal council;

within the council, committees general review and develop policies in specific areas such as health, finance, education, social services, and transportation. The actual administration of services is general conducted by non-political bureaucrats, sometimes overseen by the mayor as executive and sometimes by a separate city manager. In the selected German sub-national research site of Mannheim, interviewees indicated that municipal responses benefited from a high degree of cooperation between different administrative departments, as well as close contact with health departments in neighbouring municipalities and the Rhein-Neckar region:

“We in the health offices, there is a very close exchange with the Association of Cities – in this case only Stuttgart, Mannheim, Heilbronn – the municipal health offices. And there is a very close exchange. Perhaps a general remark at this point, I have always been happy to be a municipal health officer, and this has been considerably strengthened by the pandemic, because we have all the relevant contacts on site in a direct way, a clear structure – with administrative staff, management, OB – and there were all the relevant office management at the table basically, or also virtually” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

During the time periods T1-T2, the governmental structure in Germany did not change. However, a federal parliamentary election was held on 26 September 2021, which led to a change in government. After two months of talks, the SPD, Greens, and FDP formed a novel coalition government on 23 November 2021. Olaf Scholz of the SPD was selected as Chancellor on 8 December 2021. On 11 February 2022, Chancellor Scholz gave his inaugural address to the Bundesrat, which emphasized the governments and the public’s ongoing responsibility to protect individuals and groups particularly vulnerable to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Epidemic/pandemic planning in Germany

The key legal instruments in epidemic/pandemic planning in Germany prior to COVID-19 were the 2001 Protection against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG); the 2015 crisis management strategy; and the 2017 National Pandemic Plan. The 2017 National Pandemic Plan is itself a successor to an earlier pandemic plan launched in 2005, which was modified in part to integrate lessons learned during the 2009 influenza (H1N1) pandemic (RKI, 2017, pp. 5–6). The National Pandemic Plan covers pandemic governance, medical responses, and non-pharmaceutical interventions such as reporting, diagnosis, hygiene, social distancing and other behaviour modification measures, protective clothing, disinfection measures, and information and risk communication (RKI, 2017, p. 26).

The 2015 crisis management strategy establishes that in the event of a crisis, the relevant ministries have the responsibility of forming a crisis task force that coordinates action on a federal level, whereas the National Pandemic Plan specifies that in the event of health emergencies, protocol is to call up a joint Federal Ministry of Health (BMG) and Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) task force (Krisenstab BMI/BMG). This task force is responsible for advising the Federal Government and implementing policy decisions made by the Federal Government. Every ministry is represented by liaison officers to the task force and has been responsible for implementing measures within its mandate.

The joint task force also coordinates with the Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Response (BBK), which issues advice for health care institutions, and the Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW), which manages logistics support for pandemic-related needs (e.g. setting up testing and vaccination centres, assisting with the distribution of protective equipment). The federally funded Robert Koch Institute (RKI) also plays a key medical and bioscientific advisory role. Particularly important is the RKI Standing Committee on Vaccination (STIKO), which issues official recommendations on vaccination schedules, including which vulnerable groups to prioritize.

3.4.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The first case of COVID-19 in Germany was recorded on January 27, 2020. This precipitated the first “wave” of the pandemic, which occurred between early Spring and Autumn, with a rapid increase in cases during March and April, followed by a decrease in cases during May through August. In February 2020, a BMG/BMI joint crisis task force was set up to deal with the pandemic by Federal Minister of the Interior Horst Seehofer and Federal Minister of Health Jens Spahn in accordance with the federal pandemic plan. Initial measures taken were the rollout of hygiene regulations developed by the Robert Koch Institute, such as compulsory mask-wearing in public, as well as the definition of a risk communication strategy based on the slogan “Through the year with AHA” (“Mit AHA durchs Jahr”), which established the so-called AHA-Formula (AHA-Formel) to publicize basic risk mitigation measures and promote their acceptance:

1. „Abstand halten” – “keep a safe distance”
2. „Hygiene-Maßnahmen beachten” – “pay attention to hygiene measures”
3. „Alltagsmaske tragen” – “wear a mask on an everyday basis”

On 4 March, the Robert Koch Institut officially updated the National Pandemic Plan in response to the COVID-19 pandemic (RKI 2020b). The RKI furthermore released numerous subsidiary guidelines and appendices throughout the remainder of the pandemic. On 11 March, the Chancellor called upon the population to voluntarily restrict their public lives to help control the spread of the disease. Over the following days, hospitals were ordered to postpone admissions and procedures that can safely be delayed; an aid package for businesses, including the creative industry, was proposed; non-commercial land border crossings were prohibited; travel warnings were issued; and large public events were cancelled. The first lockdowns in Germany were announced on 16 March, extending until 19 April. During this period, social contact was restricted to individual households and movements were restricted to shopping for essentials, keeping doctors’ appointments, and individual outside exercise. Compared to measures taken in other countries affected with COVID-19, these measures rank as moderate to stringent. On March 25, the Bundestag declared the COVID-19 pandemic to be of national significance. Shortly after, on 28 March, the Federal Government passes the first Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance (Gesetz zum Schutz der Bevölkerung bei einer

epidemischen Lage von nationaler Tragweite), which gave the BMG extraordinary powers to control the epidemic.

Interviewees in the sub-national research site of Mannheim indicated that during the initial weeks of the pandemic, local officials met intensively under heavy psychological and emotional pressure, with resolve to find solutions but a dominant mood of confusion and fear:

“We knew nothing. Of course, we were already talking among ourselves about how this was getting bigger and bigger. We had crisis meetings every day at some points, whenever there was new information. We assumed a pandemic situation in the... in a modern medical sense. We then also researched the fact that the last real pandemic, where Germany was also affected, was in 1969. That was an outbreak that ravaged Hamburg, with the cargo ships. There were also school closures, but that mainly affected Hamburg at the time. And now we were confronted with a situation that was not yet known to modern medicine. There were already words like ‘the end of the world’, and... Well, we really expected everything, I must say. There were colleagues who, for example, also witnessed the beginnings of HIV. At that time, it took an insanely long time to find out what it actually was. It took much, much longer than with Corona. And I remembered that one of my lecturers once told me that he had worked in an infectious disease ward when HIV was still unknown. And there also, young men died. They were his age, and he didn't know what it was. And if he had told his future parents-in-law, they would never have let him marry their daughter. That's what this made me think of. So those were the images that you actually had in your head” (senior COVID-19 response administrator, State of Baden-Württemberg).

On the economic front, during the week of 23 March, the federal government adopted several economic measures: aid was extended to self-employed workers, MSMEs, and farmers; stabilisation funds were directed toward industry; and access to “reduced-hours work” (Kurzarbeit) was simplified (a program in which employers can reduce their employees' working hours, with social security funds reimbursing employees a percentage of their lost wages). The number of businesses taking advantage of the program rose sharply. During the remainder of 2020, the federal government continued to adopt proactive economic support measures, with particular attention to vulnerable sectors (such as the creative and cultural sectors and industries) and actors (such as MSMEs and freelancers). For example, in April 2020, an expedited credit program was created for MSMEs, employers were allowed to provide employees with tax-free bonuses, application procedures for unemployment insurance were streamlined and moved online, and minimum wages are raised for nursing practitioners. On the social front, numerous services were expanded or newly established in Spring 2020 to ease the indirect consequences of the disease. These included helplines for women threatened with domestic violence and people suffering from depression. On the communications front, the March 2020 communique *How We Will Bring COVID-19 Under Control* (Bundesministerium des Innen 2020) conveyed a strategy of shifting the pandemic narrative from a tone of shock and fear towards a tone of seriousness and resilience, to sharpen awareness of the risks facing the population (and vulnerable groups in particular).

By April 2020, case rates had begun to decrease. On a federal level, the first hard lockdown was phased out on 19 April; however, social distancing measures remained part of the German policy toolkit. During Summer 2020, restrictive measures were adopted flexibly on a state-by-state level in response to local infection rates. On 14 May, the Federal Government adopted the Second Act for the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance, which focused on increasing access to tests, providing better support to workers in the health and care sectors, protecting care home residents and other people at particular risk from infection, and gaining better insight into the course of the epidemic, especially in partnership with other EU member states. Throughout late Spring and Summer of 2020, a focus was placed on increasing test-and-trace capacities nationwide, as well as enhancing the capacity of the healthcare system. In June, the Corona-Warn-App and its accompanying Data Protection Impact Assessment were released. The app was well-received, with over 14 million downloads by the beginning of July.

In October 2020, a second “wave” of COVID-19 hit Germany: both case rates and deaths began to increase precipitously. In response, the federal government implemented a second hard lockdown on 2 November, which extended until 19 December. Like the first hard lockdown, this entailed the closure of most (non-essential) businesses and tight restrictions on movement and social gatherings; schools and childcare centres, however, remained open. On 18 November 2020, the government adopted the third Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance. This iteration introduced the possibility of introducing restrictive anti-COVID-19 measures in response to raising incidence rates into the Infection Protection Act (§28a Para. 1 IfSG). On the economic and social fronts, Winter 2020 saw an extension of key stimulus and support measures, including “bridging aid” for MSMEs and the “Neustart Kultur” programme for cultural and creative sectors and industries. As the Christmas and New Year holiday season drew closer, the federal and state governments debated whether to maintain, roll back, or expand restrictions. While the different states took somewhat different pathways, for the most part, the decision was made to maintain limitations on social gatherings and household visits, limit or close non-essential businesses and traditional Christmas markets and impose travel restrictions.

Throughout the period of T1, the federal and state governments were often criticized for inconsistency in issuing and communicating new restrictions. Interviewees in the sub-national research site of Mannheim sometimes indicated that this could be confusing for not only the public, but also local administrators and front-line workers, and that efforts were made to introduce more clarity by adapting higher-level communications on the local level:

“Federal and state policy again and again also contributed to the fact that the decrees sometimes came at very short notice and that the orders or the communication took place in a language that was not understandable for many. I don't exclude myself at all at certain points [...] We have tried to find ways at the municipal level, but perhaps we'll come to that later” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

As in other developed countries worldwide, perhaps the most consequential development of Winter 2020 was the approval and rollout of vaccinations. On 9 November, the Robert Koch Institute released recommendations for vaccination prioritization. The Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine was given final EMA approval on 21 December, and the Moderna vaccine on 27 December; this marked the beginning of the vaccination campaign in Germany (as in most EU states). By the end of 2020, around 200,000 Germans at risk of a severe progression of the disease had received their first vaccine.

In January 2021, case rates in Germany began to fall even before the widespread introduction of vaccines. Nevertheless, on 19 January, Chancellor Merkel and the heads of the states agreed to extend certain restrictions on social life until mid-February. They furthermore agreed to tighten the obligation to wear FFP2/KN95 masks in public spaces such as public transportation and shops, as well as to continue to recommend social distancing (1.5 meters) and intensive hygiene practices.

In February 2021, after a brief lull, case rates began to increase again due to the spread of variants of the virus. On 1 February, the federal government adopted the Coronavirus Protection Ordinance (Coronavirus-Schutzverordnung – CoronaSchV), which restricted travel from so-called “areas of variants of concern” identified by the Robert Koch Institute. On both a federal and state level, a move from generalised to targeted restrictions can be observed. Targeted general restrictions on social life, extending to lockdowns, were implemented on a rolling basis in response to local infection rates and outbreaks. In the state of Baden-Württemberg, where our sub-national research was conducted, these measures included the periodic closure of non-essential businesses, limitation of public gatherings, imposition of curfews and alcohol bans, encouragement of home office work, and transition to hybrid in-person/distance-learning models in many schools.

Another form of targeting was 30 January 2021 adoption of the Corona Quarantine Ordinance (Corona-Quarantäneverordnung), which provided clear guidelines on quarantine requirements for individuals testing positive for COVID-19. The shift of emphasis from general to targeted restrictions was accompanied by the expansion of test-and-trace infrastructure, including easy access to low-cost or free rapid antigen and PCR tests and the iterative improvement and promotion of the Corona-Warn-App. By mid-June 2021, a year after its introduction, the Corona-Warn-App had been downloaded nearly 30 million times and used to register over 20 million test results. The Federal Ministry of Health evaluated test-and-trace efforts such as the Corona-Warn-App as having had primarily positive effects; however it also notes that the effectiveness of contact tracing can be adversely effected by time delays compounded by short incubation periods; unexpected surges of infections; a high rate of unreported cases; dependence on individual cooperation; and the need to mitigate negative effects such as undue impositions on individual freedoms, mistrust and fear of public health institutions, and the stigmatization of the infected (BMG 2022: 80).

During 2021 and 2022, the most critical element of German COVID-19 response policy was vaccination. Groups at risk of a severe progression of the disease were initially prioritized for

vaccination, alongside healthcare workers. However, during the second quarter of 2021, vaccines became available to anyone living in Germany. From April to June 2021, the vaccination campaign worked at its full capacity as Corona vaccination became available to anyone living in Germany both in dedicated vaccination centers and in medical clinics. During this period, the Standing Committee on Vaccination (STIKO) approved the use of AstraZeneca for people over 60 years of age. From September 2021, booster vaccines were offered to priority groups, and toward the end of the year to all citizens. During the same timeframe, vaccination for children became available. A second booster was offered to priority groups at the beginning of 2022. A crucial factor in achieving a high vaccination rates is vaccination communication. However, decision-makers in Germany at both federal and state levels have been, and continue to be, critiqued for their vaccination communication (BMG 2022: 57).

A controversial measure implemented in Germany during the first and second quarters of 2021 were “2G/2G+/3G” regulations, which meant that only vaccinated, recovered, and/or tested persons could get access to restaurants, events, or other services. These sorts of measures were authorised under the COVID-19 Protective Measures Exemption Ordinance (COVID-19-Schutzmaßnahmen-Ausnahmenverordnung) and implemented mostly on a state-by-state rather than federal level. They aimed at decreasing new infection rates and preventing severe illness courses among unvaccinated people (BMG 2022: 74), as well as at increasing vaccination willingness via passive coercion (BMG 2022: 78). It is difficult to assess the effectiveness of 2G/3G regulations with a high degree of precision, as they were never implemented alone, but solely in combination with hygiene and social distancing rules. In addition, not enough data are available. Nevertheless, the data at hand suggest that 2G/3G regulations are most effective for those who have recently received vaccine boosters or recovered from an infection. Such regulations furthermore appeared to lose effectiveness with the emergence of the Omicron variant. Additionally, contrary to their aim, 3G/2G regulations did not raise vaccination readiness in Germany; rather, the number of newly administered vaccine doses decreased after their introduction (BMG 22: 77). This could indicate a perverse incentive/outcome.

During the third quarter of 2021, the German government did not introduce many policy innovations on COVID-19. However, it concentrated its efforts on consolidating policies that were already in place and addressing responses for societal groups which were not sufficiently included in the response to the pandemic and its consequences so far. Many efforts were directed toward families and education. The Standing Committee on Vaccination (STIKO) released recommendations for vaccination of pregnant and breastfeeding women; the working group of the Federal Ministry of Family Affairs and the Federal Ministry of Health with other experts worked to promote of healthy nutrition and exercise for children and adolescents; and millions of EUR were set aside for the purchase of air purification devices for schools and childcare centres.

During the fourth quarter of 2021, the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) warned of a new rise in rates of infection, hospitalisation, and death. The BMG responded to this fourth wave with a three-

pronged strategy: 1) consistent implementation of 2G rules, hygiene and masking rules, test-and-trace measures, and other existing good practices; 2) compulsory testing in nursing homes; and 3) increasing the pace of booster vaccination. To combat the “infodemic”, the state invoked the Network Enforcement Act (Netzwerkdurchsetzungsgesetz – NetzDG) to order platforms such as Facebook and Twitter to delete malicious misinformation/disinformation about COVID-19 and report it to the authorities. The government furthermore extended economic stimulus and support measures, such as simplified access to “reduced-hours work” (Kurzarbeit). In December 2021, the Federal Government and state governments convened a Coronavirus Expert Council (Corona ExpertInnenrat der Bundesregierung) to assess response measures, as well as to contribute recommendations for measures going forward, from a multidisciplinary rather than a purely epidemiological perspective.

Elevated infection rates – and to a lesser extent, death rates – continued well into 2022. Health minister Lauterbach called for a more aggressive approach to booster vaccination; by the end of January 2022, over 45 million Germans had received a booster. The Standing Committee on Vaccination (STIKO) furthermore recommended a second mRNA booster vaccine for vulnerable groups and medical care workers. By March 2022, case rates and death rates had begun to fall again. In April, many of the remaining restrictive measures in place, such as the requirement to wear masks in shops, were lifted (however, masks remained mandatory in hospitals and on public transportation). In May, remaining 2G rules were lifted. This was justified by the fact that because the dominant Delta and Omicron variants were highly contagious but less severe, there was no immediate danger of a nationwide overburdening of the health care system; state governments maintained the option of implementing restrictions on a local level. A wave of increased infection and death rates in June 2022 did not substantially affect federal policy: while some new rules were implemented on a state-by-state level, most were minor. The Coronavirus Expert Council issued its twelfth, and to date last, communication in August 2022. In October 2022, a further wave of infections and (to a lesser extent) deaths prompted a minor tightening of some restrictions, e.g., the obligation to wear a mask on public transportation. However, the response was generally subdued. By Winter 2022, the consensus among public-facing experts such as virologist Christian Drosten was that COVID-19 had evolved into an endemic (rather than pandemic) disease.

3.4.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

The German federal government’s initial definition (at T1) of “at-risk groups” focused on factors that increased the chance of a severe progression of COVID-19. A 6 March 2020 paper issued by the Robert Koch Institute, for instance, identified the following groups as vulnerable:

- Older persons (risk level rising in correlation with age from the threshold of 50-60 years on)
- Smokers
- Persons with specific pre-existing medical conditions:
 - Heart conditions

- Lung conditions
- Chronic liver disease
- Diabetes
- Cancer
- Weakened immune system

As 2020 passed into 2021 (T2), official definitions of at-risk groups shifted to encompass factors that increased the chance of exposure to the SARS-CoV-2 virus as well. The STIKO's January 2021 "Decision of the STIKO on the 1st update of the COVID-19 vaccination recommendation" defined a stepwise vaccination strategy informed by both health vulnerabilities and social vulnerabilities. Specifically, six priority groups are identified based on several risk clusters:

- Persons at risk for a severe progression of COVID-19 (see above)
- Persons with an elevated risk of infection in front-line occupations:
 - Workers in medical institutions
 - Other health care workers
 - Teachers and early childhood educators
 - Retail workers
 - Workers in critical infrastructure:
 - Public health workers
 - Other infrastructure workers, including first responders and transportation workers
- Persons with an elevated risk of infection due to other conditions:
 - Residents in senior and care facilities
 - Persons with dementia or other cognitive disorders
 - Residents and workers in arrival points and collective accommodations for asylum-seekers
 - Residents and workers in homeless shelters
 - Persons with precarious work and living situations, including:
 - Those who work in spaces where many people work in proximity without adequate ventilation or personal protective equipment
 - Low-wage and short-contract workers who may be less likely to call in sick
 - Itinerant workers who often cross-national borders in crowded vehicles and live in shared accommodations (examples are workers in meat processing plants and distribution centres and seasonal agricultural workers)

The STIKO strategy is guided by "the overarching ethical goal of minimising harms to health and society caused by the COVID-19 pandemic," while taking into account "the principles of self-determination, justice, solidarity and urgency" (RKI 2021 [8 January], Section 11).

While generally regarded as successful from a top-down level, the German approach to prioritising certain groups for vaccination was criticised for being confusing and inconsistent by some local stakeholders, including interviewees in the target sub-municipal research site of Mannheim:

“On the subject of vaccines, I don't know if you remember, but we had new recommendations virtually every two days. Who gets the vaccine? How can we distribute it? What lists do I make? Who gets vaccinated first? Where do we vaccinate? Who gets the super frozen ones? How can this even be distributed? We made new lists every two days: ‘No, you don't get one. Oh, now you do..., you're in. Oh, but we don't get enough. We have 100 people who want to be vaccinated. We only get 50 doses. You're a young woman. You get AstraZeneca.’ Two days later, ‘Oh, my God! Young women are dying from AstraZeneca, you're getting something else.’ From... So the vaccination thing, that was an absolute disaster, even for the doctors” (senior COVID-19 response administrator, State of Baden-Württemberg).

“It was quite clear that access to vaccination in Baden-Württemberg had massively promoted social inequality. It was so difficult that for people with less language skills or less educational background... basically no access to vaccination was possible, and with that, the discussion was also held that the socially weaker do not want to be vaccinated at all” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

Whereas public health measures targeted the general population, with special measures taken to support health vulnerabilities, the broader set of governmental measures explicitly and/or implicitly targeted a wide range of population groups and institutions. These included:

- Population groups
 - Bonus payments and tax relief for **parents**, increased for **single parents**
 - Relief payments for **parents of sick children**
 - Housing and utilities support for **the unemployed**
 - Helplines for **vulnerable women** threatened with domestic violence and **people suffering from depression**
 - Informational campaigns to prevent fraud against **individuals** and **(small) businesses**
 - Raise in minimum wages for **nursing practitioners**
 - Digital learning platforms and mobile devices for **students**
- Institutions/sectors
 - Expanded and simplified access to the short-work (Kurzarbeit) scheme, a program in which **employers** can reduce their **employees'** working hours, with social security funds reimbursing employees a percentage of their lost wages
 - Provisions for tax-free bonuses for **employees**
 - Stabilisation funds directed toward **industry**
 - Up to 750 million euros for vaccine research and development (i.e., **pharmaceutical research institutions and industry**)

- Grants for **(small) businesses** that invest in the production of new, innovative health care products
- Grants and credit programs for **MSMEs** in general
- Targeted financial support for **MSMEs** that participate in vocational training programmes
- Targeted financial support for **art and cultural centres**, especially in rural areas
- Targeted financial support for **live music venues**
- Targeted financial support for **self-employed culture workers**, including visual and performing artists, artisans and craftspeople, authors, translators, organisers of music festivals and live music programmers,
- Targeted financial support for **children’s and youth hospices**
- Targeted support for social organisations such as **homeless shelters, workshops for the disabled, and cultural integration centres**

Later in 2021 and into 2022, the federal government’s (quasi-) official definitions of vulnerability expanded to better align with the wide range of groups targeted by its measures. For example, in July 2021, RKI published a “General guidance for health officials on outreach and collaboration with marginalized populations during the COVID-19 pandemic”, with marginalized populations defined as “people who are pushed to the margins of society by economic, social, geographic, or other societal structures [e.g., through] loss of resources, influence, and status”. It focuses especially on migrant-background and minority ethnic populations (which often see higher rates of poverty, precarity, and discrimination), defining concrete steps to be taken when planning interventions targeted at these groups. On 14 December 2021, the Federal Government and state governments convened a Coronavirus Expert Council (Corona ExpertInnenrat der Bundesregierung). The 11th Statement of the Expert Council, “Pandemic Preparedness for Autumn/Winter 2022/2023”, issued by on 8 June 2022, augments the RKI’s earlier guidelines, including on targeting vulnerable groups. Notably, the Statement concludes with a section on the need to protect vulnerable groups – among which the elderly, those with prior medical conditions, and children and youth are mentioned. The focus on children and youth sets the Statement apart from prior guidelines: specifically, the Statement asserts that “Child welfare must be considered, including access to society, education, and sport, especially for children with prior medical conditions. This will require significant improvements in the effectiveness and efficiency of child health care systems, most critically pediatric stationary care” (Corona ExpertInnenrat 2021, p. 21). Within three scenarios developed by the Expert Council for Autumn/Winter 2022/2023, the risk of overburdening the paediatric care system is emphasised. This focus on children and youth sets the Statement apart from guidelines released in 2020 and Q1-3 2020.

Interviewees in the sub-national research site of Mannheim confirmed that youth were particularly vulnerable, and described attempts by their institutions to mitigate this vulnerability:

“They have online classes, or they are not allowed to see their friends. And these are aspects, I think, where you... quite a lot of things of social interaction were not possible. So we have, for example, in our youth centers already, in the mornings, for example, set up digital access possibilities, for young people who had no possibility from home to attend online lessons at all. And so, I think it's such a mix. At certain points, technical possibilities were helpful, but they can in no way replace personal exchange, personal contact” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

The trend of broadening the range of vulnerabilities recognised in official statements continues in the BMG's 30 June 2022 comprehensive report *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies*. The “Evaluation” asserts that vulnerable groups requiring specific attention include, but are not limited to, those living under the poverty line (less than 60% of median income), those with low socio-economic status, refugees, and other migrants (including labour migrants), and homeless/houseless people. The rationale given for designating these groups are based on both health and socioeconomic considerations: i.e., these groups faced higher risks of infection, more severe courses of illness, more severe mental health issues, and more severe financial burdens. These groups were also harder to test, trace, or vaccinate. The “Evaluation” assesses federal efforts to meet these groups' needs as inadequate and suggests that lessons could be learnt from regional governmental and/or civil society initiatives, such as ‘Hotels for the Homeless’ in Hamburg or ‘Housing First Berlin’ (BMG 2022: 97).

On the municipal level, interviewees in the German sub-national research site of Mannheim identified the pandemic as an opportunity to discuss more intersectional definitions of health and wellbeing as “cross-cutting” issues, and to assign them a higher priority:

“The discussion will have to be held – I can't even say yet what our path should be [...] what I think I also still see is that we have noticed that the topic of health is a cross-cutting issue that will get a much higher priority, basically, in the near future, socially and politically [...] I actually believe that there are or should be extra structures for this” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

Due to a lack of sufficient support for the most vulnerable in most domains and on most levels of governance, the BMG determined the following as important learnings from the COVID-19 health crisis. Firstly, social inequality should be seen as an independent topic within the politics of a pandemic. Secondly, prevention should be target-group-oriented. Thirdly, alternatives for those who are not sufficiently protected in their own homes need to be established. Additionally, there is a need for stricter oversight of hygienically precarious work environments. Furthermore, affordable access to personal protective equipment, like masks and testing, should be ensured. Compensation for financial disadvantages is important. Finally, vulnerable groups need to be specifically targeted when it comes to vaccinations and prioritized in the vaccine rollout (BMG 2022: 98-99).

Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors in Germany that influenced preparedness and response

The German government has not publicly identified the factors or indicators on which specific decisions were based, aside from 7-day COVID-19 incidence rate. However, official evaluations and studies offer insight. Some factors that likely influenced and/or constrained government preparedness and response included:

- Socio-political: the University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring study indicates that during the initial phase of the pandemic, the public expressed relatively high initial trust in public health institutions and government among, along with relatively high acceptance of the measures adopted (Universität Erfurt et al., 2022).
- Legal: the BMG assesses the 2001 Protection against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG) as “designed entirely for outbreaks of a rather local nature and of quite limited duration. It was therefore a formidable challenge to base virtually all (area-wide and covering the entire population) measures to combat the long-lasting Corona pandemic on this law. Policymakers have attempted to accomplish this task primarily through numerous, not always fortunate, amendments and additions to the IfSG, with little evidence of a consistent overall approach. Rather, the IfSG has meanwhile developed into a rather confusing and unsystematic web of regulations” (BMG 2022, pg. 103). This constraint led to significant confusion when it came to communication of changing measures and the rationale behind them, which eventually fed back in the form of decreasing public acceptance.
- Ethical: the 2017 National Pandemic Plan assumes an ethical obligation to protect medically vulnerable population groups as a core element in pandemic management; the general population were accordingly expected to sacrifice certain rights and freedoms in order to enable authorities to fulfil this obligation.

The German government has not publicly identified the socio-political factors or indicators which drove changes in policy. However, records and evaluations indicate that during the course of 2021 and 2022, increasing political pressure was placed on the government to transparently assess the efficacy of its measures, and reconsider its approach when warranted. Factors that may have driven change include:

- Socio-political: the COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring study shows that agreement with the statement “I find the COVID-19 measures excessive” did tend to rise gradually over the course of the lockdown periods (March to late April 2020; late 2020 to early 2021) and during the period of 2G/2G+/3G regulations, indicating that patience wore thin during these periods (Universität Erfurt et al., 2022). Furthermore, the parliamentary records “Statement on an inquiry: Health communication of the Federal Government and the Federal Centre for Health Education in the Corona pandemic (04.05.2021)” and “Statement on an inquiry: Further development of the Federal Government's information and education campaign on COVID-19 vaccination (23.09.2021)”, both of which cite confusion among the general public and specific vulnerable groups (e.g., migration-background residents) regarding the unclear and

sometimes contradictory communication of health-protective regulations and recommendations.

- Legal: in tune with souring public opinions, lawmakers in government and opposition introduced several draft laws revising or challenging the initial policy approach; in combination with the inquiries cited above, this evinces steadily increasing political pressure on authorities. Examples include:
 - Introduced by the governing coalition parties SPD, Greens, and FDP: “To strengthen the protection of the population and especially vulnerable groups against COVID-19 (zur Stärkung des Schutzes der Bevölkerung und insbesondere vulnerabler Personengruppen gegen COVID-19”:
<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/025/2002573.pdf>)
 - Introduced by the CDU/CSU: “Well prepared for the autumn - to improve pandemic management” (Gut vorbereitet für den Herbst – Pandemiemanagement verbessern:
<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/025/2002564.pdf>)
 - Introduced by the Left: “Prepare for changing pandemic - a present action plan” (Auf sich verändernden Pandemieverlauf vorbereiten – Maßnahmenplan vorlegen: <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/025/2002581.pdf>)
 - Introduced by the AfD: “Against COVID-19 vaccination requirements for soldiers” (COVID-19-Impfpflicht für Soldaten: <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/026/2002600.pdf>)
- Ethical: the BMG identifies (justifiably) restrictive data protection regulations and divergent state-level interpretations and technical implementations as barriers to the systematic collection of microdata required for effective pandemic surveillance; however, it holds out optimism that “the creation of a European Health Data Space, which the European Commission is aiming for by 2025, is intended to enable efficient exchange of and direct access to different health data in the areas of care and research” and may set a precedent for overcoming these barriers (BMG 2022, pg. 44).

3.5 Greece

3.5.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

According to data that stem mainly from D4.1 and D4.5, Greece is a presidential parliamentary republic, with central points of authority, particularly in healthcare crises the Greek parliament, the Ministry of Health, and the National Crisis Management Mechanism of the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSPP).

Greece had a central top-down approach as a response to the pandemic with key figures the Prime Minister, the Minister of Health, and healthcare experts such as epidemiologist Dr. Sotiris Tsiodras. As mentioned in D4.1, D4.3, and D4.5, the Greek responses were led by the main governmental actor system which includes the Prime Minister, relevant Ministers with the Minister of Health in a central role, the General Secretariat of Civil Protection, and the scientific community, of which several healthcare experts formed an advisory team.

3.5.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

As a presidential-parliamentary republic (Hellenic Parliament, n.d.)⁵¹, Greece did not establish new Ministries as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic, however as observed in D4.1, D4.3, and D4.5, a crisis management governmental-led mechanism was established to coordinate tailored responses and activities. Crisis management was led by political and healthcare experts who conducted regular press conferences to inform the public about the latest developments for COVID-19. Greece implemented a state of emergency enforcing above 800 legislative acts, that regulated and implemented tailored measures to combat COVID-19 (International Monetary Fund, n.d)⁵². Moreover, the Minister of Health issued presidential decrees and continued to be one of the core figures in the crisis communication, governmental, and public healthcare response.

The governmental response during the lockdowns was tailored and immediate and included measures that especially targeted vulnerable populations. As stated in D4.1 and our expert interviews, measures, such as mobile healthcare units that accommodated the needs of the public that could not easily have immediate access to the healthcare system, were introduced in the early stages of the pandemic. There was an effort to create more ICUs to satisfy the need for hospitalization. At the beginning of the vaccination, it was observed that the healthcare system reoriented towards the campaign to get the population vaccinated and the need to provide such services. Additional tailored responses and measure adjustments were

⁵¹ Hellenic Parliament. (n.d.). *The Constitution*. Available at <https://www.hellenicparliament.gr/en/Vouli-ton-Ellinon/To-Politevma/Syntagma/>.

⁵² International Monetary Fund. (n.d.). *Policy Responses to Covid-19. Country: Greece*. Available at <https://www.imf.org/en/Topics/imf-and-covid19/Policy-Responses-to-COVID-19#G>.

also made to address the Omicron variant of COVID-19, although because most of the population had already gone through the necessary doses of the vaccine, the relevant campaign was not projecting a strict message as the previous ones. It can be said that a constant in the different stages of the pandemic, was the special care towards vulnerable groups.

The COVID-19 response was a joint effort between political figures and healthcare experts who had an advisory role, based on data that stem from D4.1, D4.4, and our expert interviews. The responsibilities of each representative did not change throughout the duration of the pandemic. In contrast, no solution, or alternative to the implemented measures was presented until the gradual decrease of the infection rates which made the restrictive policies less strict and changed the mandatory nature of the measures to optional or they were completely abolished. Similarly, to other European countries, residents in Greece are observed reserved during the first pandemic phase while acts such as a decrease in compliance rates in relation to measures were observed during the latest phases which included demonstrations against the pandemic measures and government, COVID-19 large-scale public and private gatherings as well as cases of public expressions of discontent towards the governmental officials and healthcare experts.

3.5.3 Reflections on pandemic management taking changes into consideration

As stated in our expert interviews, healthcare professionals experienced an overload of responsibilities and work hours which was psychically and mentally exhausting. Healthcare experts experienced fatigue due to long working hours. A success of the Greek governmental response was the swift introduction of legislative acts that allowed a better management of the pandemic, while experts agreed that a similar *modus operandi* was adopted by several European states, adhering to international standards. These acts introduced a series of measures that emphasized in the management of the pandemic and containment of infection rates. Another success according to our expert interviews is the distribution of the relevant responsibilities by the governmental mechanism to agencies and institutions which increased the effectiveness of measures due to enhanced interagency communication and coordination, despite some challenges in communication. A lesson that can be drawn from the COVID-19 pandemic response, is the mandatory involvement of experts, depending on the nature of the crisis. As COVID-19 is predominantly a health-related crisis, healthcare experts and the scientific community had an immensely important role. Moreover, another lesson learned is that society and the governance system can comprehend new dimensions of vulnerability, which will allow a more encompassing and effective response to a potential future crisis. In addition, a lesson that can be taught from COVID-19 is that as the first line of defense, healthcare professionals have increased exposure to healthcare crises, which makes them more vulnerable. In relation to the Greek response, according to our expert interviews, the mobile healthcare units were crucial in engaging with the needs of vulnerable populations who did not have immediate access to the Hellenic healthcare system, thus, accommodating the needs of citizens in need such as refugees, immigrants, Roma community and inmates

among other isolated social groups. According to our expert interviews, it is important that Decision Makers consider equity and equality while drafting and implementing policies while also taking into consideration socio-economic, cultural, health and legal factors, which may include the inability to acquire employment, procurement availability, and cost of healthcare equipment, thus, resulting into realistic and feasible measures, responses and policies.

Further, a success of the Greek response according to our expert interviews was the swift actions that were adopted in order to contain the pandemic and protect residents in elderly healthcare facilities, general healthcare institutions, refugee and migrant facilities by prioritization in relation to vaccinations. In addition, the Greek response, taking into account financial capabilities and capacity, had also successfully, to a certain point, mitigated the impact of COVID-19 by supporting business owners and employees with a variety of benefits and economic support packages.

A measure that was at the centre of criticism is the non-pharmaceutical interventions such as social isolation (lockdowns) while albeit assisted in containing the spread of the virus and potentially saving the lives of many citizens, social isolation introduced several negative impacts on society, national economy and the mental health of citizens. This measure can be effective when implemented for short and targeted periods of time instead of a prolonged phase.

According to experts, the adoption of a multi-level epidemiological map with distinct classification in relation to infection rates allowed a successful management of the pandemic at both national, regional, and local levels while allowing the allocation of resources and assets more evenly. Interagency cooperation, digitization of services, additional hiring of healthcare employees, and distribution of free-of-charge COVID-19 tests as well as the targeted information campaign and rollout of a testing database by implementing exhaustive tracking in combination with the use of the algorithm Empathic Visualisation Algorithm (EVA)⁷² and Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) had a crucial role and can be considered successful practices.

3.5.4 How did the public react to the crisis management and its changes?

During the first phases, as stated in D4.1, the public was predominantly frightened and did not display discontent towards the crisis management or governmental mechanism, mainly due to the lack of knowledge about COVID-19 and the healthcare impact that the virus had. On the contrary, the general public demonstrated a high level of trust in the government and the scientific community as presented in D4.1, D4.3, D4.4, D4.5 as well as based on research conducted by relevant academic institutions such as the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (Fakalis, 2020). During the latter phases and particularly during the vaccine rollout, similarly to other European countries, public discontent was also observed in Greece (Avgi, 2021). Due to the fact that the governmental response mechanism did not rapidly change, no significant fluctuations were observed in public opinion during the first phases.

3.5.5 What are the main milestones of the governmental responses adopted in each country during the different pandemic phases?

From the beginning of the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Greek peninsula, specific restrictive measures have been implemented. Some of the main milestones of these governmental responses were curfew limitations, lockdowns (local and/or national), restrictions to movement and traveling, quarantines, limitation of public or private social gatherings, and mandatory use of face masks both indoors and outdoors (A3M, n.d.)⁵³. As indicated in D4.4 and D4.5, measures such as social distancing, movement restrictions, and lockdowns, have nevertheless also affected specific social groups, such as citizens with health and socioeconomic vulnerabilities, the elderly as well as students among other individuals. Nonetheless, during the time of suspension, distance-learning educational activities, along with financial aid to vulnerable citizens have been provisioned. Such restrictions have also been imposed on a nationwide scope, and even for the facilities of Temporary Reception of irregular immigrants.

All these measures had an impact on many businesses, as stated in D4.4, which could not function only through online applications. For that reason, the government announced certain financial benefits and tax and VAT releases, primarily for small and medium-sized businesses, especially for the most impacted sectors. Regarding the suspension of business and workplaces, the Greek government advised: their operation with the necessary personnel both for the public and the private sector, for provisions with mandatory protection of employees belonging to high-risk groups by granting them special leave of absence and providing teleworking.

Furthermore, the public healthcare system was boosted, in terms of funding and in terms of human resources (European Commission - Directorate General, Economic and Finance Affairs, 2020)⁵⁴. Also regarding the main governmental responses all the official governmental announcements were translated into English, while in relation to religions, ceremonies, rituals, and gatherings, those were allowed if specific requirements were met. Finally, among the measures applied, were the financial support for unemployed citizens or Special Plans for specific categories of Freelancers and Self Employed, as well as additional financial support for absentees to work due to health reasons or childcare.

⁵³ A3M. (n.d.). *COVID-19 pandemic - Greece*. Retrieved May 27, 2021, from <https://global-monitoring.com/gm/page/events/epidemic-0001942.ugWbZWZftslc.html?lang=en>.

⁵⁴ European Commission - Directorate General, Economic and Finance Affairs. (2020, November 16). *Policy measures taken against the spread and impact of the coronavirus – 16 November 2020*. Retrieved May 27, 2021, from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/coronavirus_policy_measures_16_november.pdf.

From the beginning of the vaccination campaign, many of the measures already implemented, continued on, while new ones have been introduced, as observed in D4.4 and D4.5. One of the most important measure to be introduced was the compulsory wearing of face masks indoors such as in workplaces and in public means of transportation. Furthermore, citizens were required to carry a QR code in various formats, justifying why they were exiting their homes, however, there was a gradual disengagement from the mandatory nature of these measures, since wearing a mask became optional whilst restrictions on movement were completely abolished. From May 11th, 2021, upper secondary school students, were able to return to classes, while students in lower grades returned to classes from May 18th, 2021. Moreover, during the pandemic not only the local, regional, and national lockdowns but also social distancing was important whereas contrary to the former, social distancing was introduced as a guideline that was adopted at will by citizens even after the complete abolishment of lockdowns. Curfews were implemented in this phase particularly in the most affected areas, from 11 p.m. to 5 a.m. Finally, at this phase of the pandemic, the priority of the government was to protect the elderly citizens, through prioritizing vaccination and tailoring communication campaigns, along with high-risk individuals mainly associated with healthcare-related vulnerabilities.

3.5.6 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

Vulnerability in Greece was mostly associated with healthcare-related vulnerabilities such as heart diseases and respiratory conditions, nevertheless, based on the negative socioeconomic impact that COVID-19 had, socio-economic vulnerabilities were also recognized and taken into consideration by the Greece response mechanism throughout the COVID-19 pandemic phases, as stated in D4.1, expert interviews, D4.4 and D4.5.

The main focus of the Greek response mechanism was mainly orientated towards healthcare-related vulnerabilities as has already been mentioned above, whilst socio-economic measures were also implemented to address the impact that COVID-19 had on citizens and businesses impacted by the pandemic and relevant measures, as stated in D4.1, expert interviews, D4.4 and D4.5.

The priority of the Greek governmental responses was to protect vulnerable groups, such as persons with disabilities, single-parent families, families with four or more children, immigrants, asylum seekers, unaccompanied minors, and the elderly among citizens characterized by socioeconomic and health-related vulnerabilities, as observed in D4.1, expert interviews, D4.4 and D4.5. To that end, the government issued specific financial support measures during the pandemic waves, to assist these groups. A special telephone landline (10306) had been established to provide 24-hour psychological support and care to all people in need, such as people with mental illnesses, children and families, the elder population,

isolated individuals, as well as for those who had contracted COVID-19 and their families (EODY, n.d.)⁵⁵.

To protect vulnerable groups in care units, centres for the chronically ill, temporary housing facilities such as hostels for the homeless, and social facilities for the immediate treatment of below-the-poverty-line citizens, restrictive measures were implemented, such as suspension of visitation according to the general lockdown measures, as observed in D4.3 and D4.4. As COVID-19-related measures became less strict due to the gradual decrease in infections, the rate and degree of adherence to these measures are decided by the administration of each of the facilities, nevertheless, most if not all healthcare facilities have continued to implement protective measures such as social distancing and wearing a mask in their premises while visitations to hospital patients are now plausible (Hygeia Hospital, n.d.)⁵⁶. Services such as Asylum applications, registrations, etc. were provided upon scheduled appointments, and electronic means of communication were also adopted, capitalizing on the digitization of such services (Ministry of Migration and Asylum, 2020).⁵⁷ In addition to that, an extension of the application period for International Protection was also provided (Ministry of Migration and Asylum, 2021)⁵⁸. Finally, hospitality and tourist accommodation facilities were utilized for the temporary residence of the homeless and other socioeconomic and health-related vulnerable groups as well as individuals that travelled toward Greece and were placed in quarantine. In conclusion, tailored policies and measures were approved to guarantee acceptable living conditions for people that were experiencing the worst consequences of the crisis caused by COVID-19, offering them access to housing, education, necessities provision (such as food, etc), as well as employment activity protection.

The term vulnerability refers to groups such as the elderly and citizens with health conditions, inmates in penitentiary institutions, refugees and migrants, homeless citizens, Roma communities, and “isolated” groups that might not have immediate access to healthcare. However, with the pandemic, society realized the new dimensions of vulnerability, and the need to include societal and economically vulnerable groups, that otherwise would not be considered as such. Under the new interpretation of vulnerability, single-parent families, young citizens, employers, and employees who were negatively impacted by COVID-19 were considered vulnerable, as stated in D4.3, D4.4, and D4.5. Healthcare professionals are also

⁵⁵ Hellenic National Public Health Organization (EODY). (n.d.). *Psychosocial Support Hotline 10306 for the coronavirus*. Retrieved May 28, 2021, from <https://eody.gov.gr/tilefoniki-grammi-psychokoinonikis-ypostirixis-10306-gia-ton-koronoio/?print=print>.

⁵⁶ Hygeia Hospital. (n.d.). *Protective Measures COVID-19*. Available at <https://www.hygeia.gr/en/covid-19-protection-measures/>.

⁵⁷ Ministry of Migration and Asylum. (2020, October 19). *The electronic platform of the Asylum Service is strengthened - The service of the public exclusively by electronic appointment*. Retrieved May 28, 2021, from <https://migration.gov.gr/apokleistika-me-ilektroniko-rantevoy-i-exypiretisi-toy-koinoy/>.

⁵⁸ Ministry of Migration and Asylum. (2021, January 8). *Extension of applications for international protection*. Retrieved May 28, 2021, from <https://migration.gov.gr/paratasi-deltion-aitoynton-diethni-prostasia/>.

considered vulnerable, due to the constant exposure to COVID-19, along with employees in the tourist and hospitality sector. According to government regulations, these professionals should be placed in quarantine, when necessary, as they are faced with an enhanced risk of exposure to COVID-19. Furthermore, a variety of initiatives took place to avoid stigmatization, targeting, and further isolation of the aforementioned vulnerable groups. A notable example is the continued participation of representatives of the Ministry of Public Health, who made frequent references to vulnerable populations.

Through the implementation of 64 mobile healthcare units by the National Public Health Organization (EODY), the governmental response was immediate to increase the effectiveness of preventive responses and address the needs of vulnerable groups. Tailored responses and measure adjustments were made to address the financial needs of business owners, as well as employees with various benefits, due to the disruption of their professional activities.

3.6 Italy

3.6.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population) structure of government, pandemic planning pre-COVID

As mentioned in D4.1, Italy is a democratic parliamentary Republic with a three-way division of power. Executive power is exercised by the Council of Ministers, legislative power is vested primarily by the Parliament, and the judiciary power is independent of the executive and legislative branches. The State has powers of control - subjected to constitutional limitations - over 15 ordinary regions and 4 regions and 2 provinces with special autonomy. The regional government is composed by the regional council that has the power to pass laws and issue administrative regulations, the regional committee with executive power and the president of the regional committee. The legislative powers of regions are limited by the Constitution; in particular, they cannot conflict with national interests. The regions can also enact legislation necessary in order to enforce state laws when the latter contain the necessary provisions. The state has powers of control over the regions. The smallest local government unit is the municipality: they are governed by popularly elected municipal council, the municipal committee, or executive body, and the mayor. Regions have some control over the activity of the municipalities. Between the regions and the municipalities there are the provinces that are organized similarly to the municipalities; they each have councils, committees, and presidents. The president of the regional committee and the mayor of a municipality also have central government duties: they can, in cases of emergency, issue ordinances concerning public health, town planning, and the local police.

As mentioned in D4.5, since the end of 2003, when the outbreaks of avian influenza by virus has become endemic in birds and the virus has caused infections in humans as well, the risk of an influenza pandemic has been more concrete and persistent. For this reason, the WHO recommended all countries to develop a Pandemic Plan and to constantly update it following agreed lines. The *“Piano nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale”* [National influenza pandemic preparedness and response plan] was drawn up according to the 2005 WHO guidelines, updated and it replaced the previous Italian Multiphase Plan for and Influenza Pandemic, published in 2002.

With the Ministerial Circular “New Coronavirus Pneumonia (2019-nCov) China” of 22 January 2020 were officially declared the first cases COVID-19 in Italy. The “Piano Nazionale in risposta a un’eventuale emergenza pandemica da COVID-19” [National Health Plan in response to a possible COVID-19 pandemic emergency] established epidemiological surveillance of COVID-19 cases in Italy, on the basis of the case definitions prepared by the WHO and the technical specifications provided by the ECDC from UE/EEA countries and the UK.

Other two documents have been upset and have replaced the previous influenza pandemic plans: “Prevenzione e risposta a COVID-19: evoluzione della strategia e pianificazione nella fase di transizione per il periodo autunno-invernale” [Prevention and response to COVID-19: evolving strategy and planning in the transition phase for the autumn-winter period] and

“Piano strategico-operativo nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale (PanFlu) 2021-2023” [National Strategic-Operational Plan for Pandemic Influenza Preparedness and Response (PanFlu) 2021-2023]. The first one refers to the second pandemic phase, while the last is valid from the end of the state of emergency.

On the 31st of January 2020, Italy declared the State of Emergency for six months (later prolonged with decree-law 7 October 2020 n°125 and decree-law 14 January 2021 n°2). From January 2020 on a total of 1034 acts (the complete list is available here: <https://www.openpolis.it/coronavirus-lelenco-completo-degli-atti/>) have been issued to counter the spread of coronavirus in Italy, for an average of more than 27 per month. The first months of 2020 were the most intense from the point of view of regulatory production: in February 67 Covid acts were published, in March 103, in April 65. In 2022, the total number of published acts was 176. In 2023, 12 acts have been issued (Openpolis, 2021).

3.6.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

As mentioned in D4.1, on the 5th February 2020, a Scientific Technical Committee (CTS) was established by decree n ° 371 of the head of the Civil Protection Department to consult, support and coordinate the activities for overcoming the epidemiological emergency due to the spread of Coronavirus. The CTS members were all experts and qualified representatives of the public administration and relative entities (decree 18 April 2020 n°663; decree 15 May 2020 n°673; decree 25 November n° 715; decree 29 January 2021 n° 735). The Government appointed a regional coordinator in each of the 20 Italian regions to implement the decisions and the decree of both the Civil Protection Department and the Ministry of Health. The Head of the Civil Protection Department, in agreement with the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, modified the structure of the CTS with the Ordinance of the 17st March 2021.

On the 25th February 2020, following the outbreaks registered in Lombardy and Veneto, the first "red zone" was established. Some municipalities were isolated and were suspended all educational, cultural, economic, commercial and recreational activities. On the 4th March, educational activities in schools and universities, congress activities, cultural events and sporting events were suspended throughout the country, recommending the use of smart working from home. In Italy, the law and Constitution defined that Parliament had to approve the Government's measures with a long and complex legislative process. To deal with the epidemic, the Government chaired by Giuseppe Conte adopted a shorter administrative, not legislative, procedure: the issuance of Decrees of the President of the Council of Ministers (D.P.C.M.). With the D.P.C.M. of the 8th March 2020, the interpersonal safety distance of at least one meter was introduced as a containment measure. To avoid gatherings became mandatory and the use of the mask was recommended.

The D.P.C.M. of 9th of March 2020 was issued to block traffic and transit (lockdown), except for health needs, and to stop essential and non-essential activities, including schools, commercial and recreational business. The lockdowns were reinforced by the imposition of

obligations such as the use of surgical mask outside; the spacing of two meters between people wherever they passed or stopped; limited clusters according to the space capacity. At the end of the first phase of the emergency was issued the D.P.C.M. of 25th April 2020 that focused on the strategy to adopt from the 4th of May the gradual reopening of the economic activities. Several D.P.C.M. were issued during the following months. However, the restrictive measures (e.g. lockdown, border controls...) adopted to face the pandemic in February and March 2020 were resumed only in Autumn 2020 at the beginning of the second wave of it.

The following months, a series of decrees were issued and approved to implement an urgent measure which provided a substantial increase in the level of financing of the standard national health needs, committing the regions to draw up operational programs to use and administer these incremental resources, with joint monitoring by the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Economy and Finance. Furthermore, through the National Emergency Fund, the law-decree 17 March 2020 n° 18, so called "*Cura Italia*" [Cure Italy], and the law-decree 8 April 2020 n°23, so called "*Liquidità*" [Liquidity], promoted the purchase of devices and equipment specifically aimed at treating Covid-19 patients, such as assisted ventilation system in intensive care units, and ordered the requisition of health facilities and movable and immovable property, including hotels. In particular, the National Emergency Fund's resources were used by the Civil Protection Department for the purchase of medical devices and personal protective equipment. During the second wave (Fall 2020) a new way to deal with the restrictive measures was adopted, more specifically, the articles 1-quinquies and 19-bis of decree 28 October 2020 n° 137 defined a procedure to identify the regions receiving restrictive measures. More precisely, the Ministry of Health was committed to publish, on its institutional website, on a weekly basis, the results of the monitoring of the health risk connected to the evolution of the epidemiological situation relating to the spread of the Covid-19 virus. On the basis of the data acquired and the related processing carried out by the direction cabin for the classification of the risk, the Minister of Health could identify the regions at higher epidemiological risk. These regions were the recipients of more restrictive measures - compared to those applicable throughout the national territory. In any case, parts of the regional territory could be identified in which the same measures were not applied. Subsequently, the D.P.C.M. of the 14th January 2021 partially modified the classification criteria of the risk areas, establishing specific measures according to the weekly incidence of contagion cases per 100,000 inhabitants. These criteria were definitively regulated by art. 1 of the decree 23 February 2021 n°15, which supplemented the legislative discipline of the region's classification criteria in relation to the types of scenarios and the levels of epidemiological risk. This regulation was extended to block interregional mobility until the 25th February 2021. Thus, four types of territorial areas were identified, which replaced the previous classification referring to four different restriction scenarios: white, yellow, orange and red zone. On the 13th March 2021, a new decree was issued imposing a strict lockdown for 10 out the 20 Italian regions from the 15th of March to the 6th of April.

As mentioned in D4.5, the month of April opened with the approval of the Decree Law No.44 of the 1st April 2021, known as April Decree, on further “Urgent measures for the containment of the COVID-19 epidemic, SARS-CoV-2 vaccinations, justice and public competitions”. In addition, the State of Emergency and the division of Italian regions by four different colours continued until the 30th April 2021 (Decree Law No.2 of the 14th January 2021). In particular, the extension concerned: the suspension of the yellow zone (low-risk), except in the case of low prevalence of COVID-19 infections and particularly significant data in relation to the corresponding vaccination campaign, and with the possibility for the regions to apply the measures provided for the red or orange zones only. Visits by friends and families were also restricted, except during Easter holidays, when “red zone” measures (the most restrictive ones) were in force for the entire national territory. Visits, once a day and with no more than two people, were instead permitted in the orange zone, within the municipality of residence.

The measure also provided that from the 7th to the 30th April 2021, the presence of educational services for infants and kindergartens, as well as the teaching activities of the first cycle of education and the first year of secondary school would be ensured throughout the country. For the subsequent levels of education, the carrying out of activities in presence was confirmed from 50% to 75% of the student population in the orange zone, while in the red zone the relative activities were carried out remotely, guaranteeing in any case the possibility of carrying out activities in presence for people with disabilities and special educational needs.

On 21st April 2021 the Council of Ministers approved the so-called “Decreto Riapertura” [Reopening Decree] which set out the framework of measures to be applied from 1st May to 31st July 2021 for the gradual resumption of economic and social activities, in the context of a positively evolving health situation following the slowdown of the infection curve and the acceleration of the vaccination campaign.

Subsequently, the Decree Law of 17th June 2021 approved the free circulation in national and European territories for all people with COVID-19 green certification.

With the Decree Law No. 105 of 22nd July 2021, the state of emergency was extended until 31st December and the emergency measures defined on the specific national areas changed in relation to different assessment of infection parameters and the occupancy rate of beds in the medical area and intensive care unit. The Decree also established the possibility of carrying out several activities only in possession of COVID-19 vaccination certificate.

From this point onwards, the Italian government focused on various measures relating to the extension of the vaccination obligation and the restriction of access to areas of recreational, entertainment and catering activities for those who refused the vaccination.

On December 2022 (Decree Law No.221 and No.229) the state of emergency was extended until the 31st March 2022, when it ceased, and new arrangements were made for the management of positive cases of infection. The Green pass was expected to be phased out; the vaccination obligation was maintained until 31st December 2022 for health care

professionals and workers, also for people working in residential, social care and social-health facilities; for over 50 people the obligation remained until 15th June 2022.

In summary, the factors that influenced the policy choices stemmed from the need to contain the spread of the virus and reduce hospitalizations. Initially, in fact, the delayed response to the pandemic brought the entire health care system to a standstill: doctors and health care personnel were untrained and lacked protective devices; civil society was afraid of being infected moreover, it was frightened because basic health care treatments were not guaranteed. Subsequently, when the situation came back under control, the government began working toward a reopening, both because civil society was showing weariness with the lockdowns and to boost the country's economy. Despite scepticism, the desire to resume normal life and some restrictions imposed by government prompted many people to vaccinate. The number of hospitalizations rather than the number of people infected guided the government's choices about the reopenings.

As mentioned in D4.5, in early stages, the Covid-19 crisis in Italy looked nothing like a crisis. The initial state-of-emergency declarations were met by scepticism by both the public and mainly in policy circles.

The lack of protocols for managing the emergency was also felt in the response of the territorial health systems: sometimes ending up leaving people with obvious symptoms and their families undiagnosed; general practitioners were not prepared and did not receive adequate protection; for many days, no separate hospital pathways were set up for Covid-19 patients, so that the hospitals themselves became a hotbed of contagion.

Only with the Ministerial Circular “New Coronavirus Pneumonia (2019-nCov) China” of 22 January 2020 were officially declared the first cases COVID-19 in Italy.

Conte's government posed all attentions to contain the spread of contagious and manage the overcrowded hospitalization. The restrictive measures aimed to decrease the number of contagious, especially to relieve hospitals and ensure a resumption of their functions.

In December 2021, when the vaccination campaign began, the Government was already working towards opening up of activities that until then were severely restricted.

The end of the first phase of the pandemic coincided with the formation of a new government headed by Mario Draghi, on the 13th February 2021.

In April 2021, the Prime Minister Mario Draghi and the Health Minister Roberto Speranza announced the country's new recovery strategy based on three pillars (“Sintesi della conferenza stampa del Presidente Draghi | www.governo.it”): a clear road map of reopenings, measures to support the economy and businesses, and the revival of growth through investment. This strategy was based on an improved health situation, with the slowdown of the infection curve and the acceleration of the vaccination campaign.

In March 2022, the Council of Ministers met to dictate new measures to overcome the emergency phase (“Comunicato stampa del Consiglio dei Ministri n. 67 | www.governo.it”).

The path for the gradual return to the ordinary included a phasing out of the Green Pass (vaccination certificate or COVID-19 negativity certificate valid 24 hours after the result of a swab) and elimination of precautionary quarantines.

The restrictive measures adopted by the Italian Government and in particular the lockdown of March-May 2020 and the following in December 2020 and in March 2021 had a huge impact on Italy's economic and social structure. Italy, which in Europe is among the most affected countries in terms of infections and human lives lost, has seen a loss of 8.8% of GDP in 2020 (Berardi et al, 2020). The main causes are the halting of social and productive activities, such as tourism, which is one of the most impacted by containment measures. During 2020, through the Cure Italy, Liquidity, Relaunch and August decrees, the Italian Government implemented a series of fiscal measures aimed at supporting Italy's economy. The most significant measures were suspensions, extensions and postponements of payments for companies and professionals; cancellation and reduction of taxes; incentives and grants; support for capitalization. Indeed, one of the stakeholders highlighted that “the lockdown has improved public health but killed the public economy” (*Government_3, Italy*).

Other important measures released by the Government concerned the empowerment of digitization. In Italy, the epidemic brought out the problems related to unequal technological development (Berardi et al., 2020). The Government promoted measures to facilitate smart-working and teleworking in all those sectors in which there was no urgent need for physical presence and/or manual work and to facilitate distance learning. The Government provided an economic bonus to incentivize the purchase of computers in low-income families. However, the digital divide still manifested in access to adequate internet coverage and in the use of information technology. Because of the suspension of the educational activities in presence from the 9th March 2020, the Government made mandatory the implementation of distance learning. As highlighted by the DESI 2019 report, in Italy, only 20% of teachers have attended digital literacy courses (DESI, The Digital Economy Society Index, 2019). Based on the Istat report, 33.8% of families do not own a computer or tablet at home, a percentage that drops to 14.3% among families with at least one minor and still decreases, reaching 7.7% in families where at least one component has a degree, highlighting how the level of education has an impact on the digital cultural divide (Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, 2020). Fifty-seven percent of young people aged between 6 and 17 must share a computer or tablet with other members of their family. This situation led to a widening of social inequalities and an increase in the school dropout rate.

The measures to combat the health emergency from COVID-19, including the complete interruption of production activities, immediately produced a strong demand for social protection (Sanfelici, 2020). As a response to the rising social instability, the “*Rilancio*” [Relaunch] decree of 19 May 2020 established the Emergency Income - Rem, extraordinary support aimed at families in conditions of economic need due to the emergency. Other measures taken by the Government included an increase of 150 million euros for 2020 of the Fund for families Policies; a specific parental leave for a continuous or split period, in any case,

not exceeding a total of 15 days, for parents with children under the age of 12, or alternatively a bonus payments for the purchase of baby-sitting service; additional funds for a total of 400 million euros to municipalities, which could be used with simplified procedures for urgent food solidarity measures.

The Italian government renewed the policy that had already been partially started by the Decree “Sostegni” [Support Decree] (“LEGGI ED ALTRI ATTI NORMATIVI”), when, in March 2021, anti-poverty funds were allocated to support families and workers.

As mentioned in D4.5, on 21 January 2022, the Council of Ministers approved a series of new measures to support enterprises and economic operators, labour, health and territorial services, related to the COVID-19 emergency, as well as for the containment of the increases in the electricity sector. The Decree intervened to support sectors that had been closed as a result of the pandemic.

Similarly to what happened for the years 2020 and 2021, with regard to social policies, some measures directed State funding of 58 million euros to initiatives in favour of municipalities to promote and strengthen activities aiming at countering and promoting recovery from the critical issues that had emerged as a result of the impact of pandemic stress on the psycho-physical wellbeing and development and growth paths of minors; and activities able to promote the study of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering & Mathematics).

Ultimately, the fiscal measures and economic bonuses enacted by the government sought to address the needs of some labour groups most affected by the pandemic and to help emerging vulnerable groups.

3.6.3 Reflections on pandemic management taking changes into consideration

Successes in pandemic management as described by interviewee:

“although the decision for a national lockdown was the most difficult and painful, because of its economic and social consequences as well as the consequences on individual lives, it proved to be the most effective in limiting the spread of the virus. The vaccination campaign has also proved to be an effective solution, as shown by data on admissions to intensive care of covid patients, currently divided into two distinct groups: those who are not vaccinated and those who are vaccinated but have by pre-existing vulnerable health conditions.” (Government_2, Italy). Another stakeholder reported about the vaccination campaign as a success story “the vaccination campaign was a good example of institutional response toward vulnerable population. Identifying the elderly and the HCWs as vulnerable population to whom the vaccine should be given preferentially has allowed for very high vaccination rates in these populations. Lately, the vaccine in Italy was also made available free of charge to undocumented migrants.” (Government_1, Italy).

One of the main issues mentioned by all the stakeholders is related to communication:

“both for the (often confusing) information given by governments to citizens, and for the increasing scandalous tone of several newspapers, as well as the overexposure in the media of some virologists and other health professionals who have not provided

constructive contributions. In particular, it should be the responsibility of the government to provide clear information, even in cases where this information is not reassuring. It is therefore necessary to avoid giving partial or incomplete information, which has often proved contradictory (as in the case of the Astra Zeneca vaccines) and weakens public confidence.” (Government_2, Italy).

Another critical point underlined by three different stakeholders was the management of RSA (residential care facilities) during the Covid-19 outbreaks.

According to one of the stakeholders:

“in Italy there is no socio-health integration, and we do not have “a culture of integrated provision of primary care”;

however, some good examples exist in the Italian regions. The Italian Recovery Plan is planning to use the European funds to re-design the primary care following the example set by two regions (Emilia Romagna and Toscana). These regions created into their health districts some structures they called “health houses”. The health houses have the task of providing services for elderly and vulnerable people, strengthening the role of the GP and reducing the care burden of hospitals; however, the Stakeholder was critical of this model of care. He said that no evidence on the cost-effectiveness of this model of care exists in literature, and it does not provide a viable solution. We should learn from the covid-19 pandemic and re-establish the Italian primary care system. (Government_3, Italy).

Other success stories mentioned by the stakeholders:

“the hospitals showed impressive organizational management and preparedness. The hospitals quickly created new wards, care pathways, procedures, and guidelines. Many doctors quickly became Covid-19 specialist.” (Government_3, Italy).

On the same line of reasoning, another stakeholder said that:

“Functional cooperation between different hospital facilities is a fundamental aspect to be promoted and fostered in the future. If the NETWORK had not been created it (i.e., the management of the pandemic) would have been a disaster.” (Government_4, Italy).

In the Autumn 2020, although the restrictive measures were active, a series of mobilizations by civil society took place.

First, students and teachers expressed their disapproval of distance education. After brief opening for summer vacation, the restrictive measures were renewed in response to the increasing of contagious. Citizens, perhaps exasperated by the pandemic, demanded more safeguards to ensure in-person teaching; more teachers by hiring of precarious and temporary workers; more space by making habitable the existed buildings or build new, temporary, sustainable ones, and using the disused spaces; more outdoor activities; and more resources for public schools. They asked the Government for investments to reduce the number of students for classrooms and to prevent the crowding in public transport (Rai News, 2020).

In addition, the categories economically mostly affected by the mandatory closure, such as restaurants and bars asked for help to survive to the restrictions. They used the slogan “If you close us, you pay us” in front of government buildings in big cities (Fanpage.it, 2020).

In the second phase of the pandemic, when the government enacted measures regarding mandatory vaccination and restricting access to entertainment and dining areas for those who refused vaccination, Italian cities were hit by new waves of strikes. Several political parties from both right and left sides participated in the demonstrations (Corriere della Sera, 2021). Not only citizens who were deniers, sceptics and/or afraid of the efficacy of vaccines attended the protests, but also those who opposed to mandatory vaccination in the workplace. The labour unions felt that the implementation of the Green Pass denied the right to work to people refusing vaccine. Similarly, the alternative requirement for workers to take a swab every 48 hours was not accepted, because at the worker’s expense (Unione Sindacale di Base, 2021).

3.6.4 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

In phase 1, when the pandemic became more severe and selective, vulnerable categories were immediately addressed with specific policy measures and communication models were dedicated to them.

However, as highlighted by one of the stakeholders:

“on a national level, the government and the Scientific Technical Committee have not identified any specific vulnerable population, they just did “a general reference to fragility” in their papers. This was a major problem for the Stakeholder as data showed that covid-19 has killed mostly elderly people with an average of three comorbidities, however, no specific measures have been implemented to protect this target”. (Government_3, Italy).

Indeed, as mentioned in D4.1, other fragilities emerged during and after the lockdown phase: women had more disadvantages than men for the sharp decline in work activities; women were confined in their houses and suffered violence and harassment by their partners; children and adolescents forced into distance learning and social isolation; people with physical and mental disabilities deprived of support from institutions other than the family; migrants, especially those in irregular status; and people closed residential communities, such as prisons.

In this regard, one of the stakeholders mentioned the

“activities carried out by the Group [of Experts appointed by the Department for Family Policy of the Presidency of the Italian Government to assess the impact of the pandemic and restrictions due to the health emergency on demographic dynamics] aimed at the triple objective of: allowing the public debate to have solid and updated empirical references on demographic and social impact of the pandemic; offer the scientific community an overview of ongoing research activities; provide useful information on the

policy side. The picture that is returned here highlights a strong dynamism in terms of research and analysis (both in Italy and abroad) relating to the impact of the pandemic on families, on the new generations, on the reconciliation of work and life times, on the material and psychological. The studies revealed, in particular, the types and characteristics of the most vulnerable population groups. These include women victims of violence and ill-treatment, children especially in single-parent families and the elderly, removed from the family network if in an institution or otherwise isolated from children and grandchildren during the lockdown.” (Government_5, Italy).

As mentioned in D4.5, to deal with the Covid-19 emergency, the Government introduced, starting with the decree “*Cura Italia*” [*Cure Italy*], a series of measures in favour of Italian families, subsequently strengthened and extended with the decree “*Rilancio*” [Relaunch] and the decree “*Agosto*” [August]: interventions in support of working parents, measures to ensure the necessary liquidity and the suspension of tax and contribution payments, the introduction of allowances and new tools such as the Emergency Income for families in difficulty, important allocations to expand social protection. The decree Relaunch also definitively canceled the safeguard clauses, eliminating the increases in VAT and excise duties planned for 2021 to benefit the companies and families. For the vulnerable groups, specific actions were necessary, implemented in the course of the pandemic. The Ministry of Health's webpage dedicated to Covid-19 specific sections to three population groups: the elderly and frail, women, and children.

- *Elderly and their caregivers.* The ISS in collaboration with the National Institute for Insurance against Accidents at Work (INAIL) and the Center for Promotion and Development of Geriatric Care (Cepsag) published the booklet "Practical Guide for Caregivers of the Elderly" with a number of instructions to be followed at home and outside to protect their own health and that of the person assisted. It was possible to ask for home delivery of groceries and medicines by calling the toll-free number 800 06 55 10 (active 24 hours a day, every day), which in turn contacts the Red Cross committee closest to the territory. The service was free and available in all languages.

- *Workers, families, low-income citizens.* In 2020, the Government and Parliament deployed a high amount of resources to address the Covid-19 emergency. (<https://www.mef.gov.it/en/covid-19/misure-coronavirus.html>). With the new lockdown situation (phase 3), the important measure for working parents (Art. 5 of the decree-law of 8 September 2020, no. 111) in favour of dependent working parents was extended to cope with the newly decided closure of the schools. Among the measures in support of working parents, a bonus for purchasing baby-sitting services, extraordinary days of parental leave and smart working for parents with at least one child under the age of 14 years were instituted. In addition, the Government promoted welfare policies for people with disabilities (law 5 February 1992 n°104).
- *Migrant population.* Migrants and minorities noted issues regarding access to knowledge and information about COVID-19 and some lacked the socio-economic or technical means (such as internet access) to care for them and their families during lockdown. A particular concern was for all those who lived in crowded conditions, with difficulties in self-isolating and maintaining social distances (e.g., in reception centers), or in conditions of poor hygiene and reduced

access to clean water (e.g., in informal settlements). The decree “*Cura Italia*” included some provisions relating to the reception and protection of immigrants' health in consideration of the needs related to the state of emergency. In general, migrants, both legal and temporarily undocumented, are eligible to receive the same public healthcare services available to Italian citizens.

Some political forces to face labour shortages, especially in agricultural and domestic sectors went through with the closure of borders and the consequent blockade of foreign workers envisaged the regulation of migrant labour. The Italian government introduced measures of regularization of irregular workers with a “*Doppia Sanatoria*” [Double Amnesty] contained in the “*Rilancio*” decree⁵⁹ Unfortunately, however, several studies point to serious delays, by the administrative bodies, in the processing of submitted applications and, above all, very low rates of issuance of resident permits⁶⁰; “*Ero Straniero*” campaign (Gonnelli Elisa, 2021). These reasons prompted migrants and civil society to demand an amnesty for all and immediate implementation.

- *Women victims of domestic violence*. The Department for Families and Equal Opportunities launched the #LiberaPuoi [Free you can] campaign to promote a toll-free number for reporting domestic violence: 1522, active 24 hours a day. The Minister of the Interior, to face the closure of many reception centers for women victims of violence for health security reasons, instructed the prefects and mayors to work to find alternative solutions, given the dramatic situation experienced by many women.

- *Children and Teenagers*. The Agency for Childhood and Adolescence (AGIA) tailored the decalogue of rules to be followed by the general population to avoid the spread of the contagion with a language suitable for children, both in Italian and in English. In the portal of the Ministry of Education was available a page dedicated to the pandemic with references and useful tools for students and teachers for teaching, correct information, useful links.

- *People with disabilities*. These fragile citizens and their caregivers were granted with increased funding for disability assistance and services, an emergency income for families with disabled members, and dedicated resources for teaching students with disabilities and those with specific learning disorders and other special educational needs (<https://www.mef.gov.it/en/covid-19/misure-coronavirus.html>).

The Crisis Unit Covid-19 of the National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities (ANFFAS Nazionale) produced a document entitled "Epidemic emergencies in residential facilities for people with disabilities" with the primary objective to provide the appropriate knowledge and health regulations issued by national, regional, and local authorities.

⁵⁹ https://www.camera.it/temiap/documentazione/temi/pdf/1215466.pdf?_1588825553154

⁶⁰ <https://www.interno.gov.it/it/notizie/emersione-dei-rapporti-lavoro-presentate-piu-207mila-domande>

- *People in prisons.* The situation of prisons in Italy is rather complex, characterized by chronic overcrowding and inadequate structures. During the first pandemic phase, in more than twenty Italian prisons there were riots triggered by inmates. In a few days, several prisoners died and numerous were injured, including members of prison police. The reasons behind these episodes were linked with the new and the festering emergencies that prison has been experiencing for decades. The fear of contagion and the new restrictive measures fueled the anger of those who thought that was an additional restriction of their right. The movement of people, the possibilities of socialization, work, education for prisoners were further reduced (Internazionale, 2020).

Subsequently, the “Cure Italy” decree provided for some measures to make less crowded structures, such as the possibility, for those who had a sentence of no more than 18 months, to carry out at home the residual part and the temporal extension of the “Extraordinary award licenses for prisoners in a semi-liberty regime”. The “Ristori Decree” also extended these benefits by another month.

- *Health-care providers.* In addition to the psychological effects of the national state of emergency, the health and social-health care providers experienced specific problems and were exposed to situations of hardship with limited possibilities for resolution (Chirico, Nucera & Magnavita, 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Kursumovic, Lennane & Cook, 2020). The rapid evolution of the pandemic and the consequent progressive updating of national and local operational indications made it necessary to continuously modify the strategies implemented, particularly in areas with a high COVID prevalence, committing operators to equally continuous organizational adaptations. In some cases, within a few days, entire health facilities, or parts of them, were reorganized and completely dedicated to the COVID-19 emergency (der Filippis, Cavazzana, Gimigliano, Piacenza & Vimercati, 2020). The operators found themselves exposed to risk factors for their safety and were required to immediately and repeatedly modify activities and procedures, teams and spaces/workplaces.

To help operators manage this situation, the ISS made available a platform for distance learning in public health. In addition, both the ISS and the Ministry of Health prepared the publication of a series of technical reports and guidelines aimed at providing information on health and social health professionals. These were interim reports, which were constantly updated in the light of the evolution of the pandemic and emerging scientific evidence. The support interventions included the provision of adequate availability of PPE; the organization of places for recovery and rest in the workplace; the provision of accommodations to avoid returning home or for the management of isolation; support in the management of children; financial rewards.

3.7 Portugal

3.7.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

Portugal is a parliamentary democracy with a representative democratic republican structure for its administration with two autonomies (Madeira and Azores). The Prime Minister is the head of government, whereas the President of the Republic is the head of state. The direction and execution of the nation's overall policy, including public health policy, is the responsibility of the government. Setting policies and rules for crisis response, distributing resources, and coordinating with other sectors are all responsibilities of the government. The DGS (Direção Geral da Saúde; Directorate-General of Health), Portugal's national public health agency, oversees the promotion and safeguarding of public health, as well as disease prevention and management. It is an independent agency that is described as the *National Health Authority*. This agency is the one that has autonomy to declare a pandemic state. The connection with the Ministry of Health is complex, since it offers technical assistance and guidance to the government, healthcare providers, and the public on matters pertaining to health, but the final form of measures implementation should be sustained by the government. DGS has played a significant role in the control of the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal by offering direction and suggestions on precautions, testing, treatment, and vaccination. The DGS supported decision-making and public health initiatives and also oversaw the monitoring and surveillance of the epidemic. The two autonomous regions above mentioned have regional health authorities and autonomy. The National Health Service (SNS), which offers free and open access to healthcare services, is the main provider of health care in Portugal public health system. The SNS manages the delivery of medical services, disease surveillance, and public health promotion. It is divided into primary care facilities, hospitals, and specialty clinics. Also, there are very dynamic private health providers particularly in high density areas that have a connection with the public system either by being contracted to provide diagnostic services or directly deal with private health insurance systems.

The Portuguese government has a crisis communication framework in place, which comprises a national emergency plan and a communication strategy. While the Directorate-General for Health (DGS) supervises the communication of health-related information to the public and healthcare rules, the National Civil Protection Authority (ANPC) is in charge of coordinating and communicating emergency responses. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the DGS worked closely with other government departments, particularly the Ministry of Health, to organize the national response to the pandemic.

We were unable to uncover any earlier COVID-19 crisis-related government communication plans or initiatives. Usually there is an *Ad-hoc system* where when a crisis is recognized as such, the above entities and others that are considered relevant, are invoked to respond. But if it is health related the DGS always take the lead. Due to the central role of the DGS, the

communication strategy should implicitly be of this agency responsibility. It also created a small advisory group of risk communication that was unable to implement any ideas (one of the experts interviewed).

The Portuguese government had several preparations and documentation in place before and during the COVID-19 pandemic to cope with pandemics and other crisis circumstances, like the National Plan for Pandemic Influenza (that the Directorate-General of Health (DGS) released in 2007 and revised in 2014) and the National Emergency Plan (released in 2009, updated in 2015 by the Portuguese Civil Protection Authority). However, as noted by (Borges et al., 2021), the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted several gaps and challenges in these plans, including the need for more resources, coordination among different sectors, and flexibility in adapting to new situations.

3.7.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The government and pertinent agencies adopted several steps to control the problem when the COVID-19 pandemic first appeared in Portugal in March 2020 (Directorate-General for Health [DGS], 2020). On March 18, the government proclaimed a state of emergency, giving them exclusive authority to enforce curfews, prohibit travel, and shut down non-essential companies (Governo de Portugal, 2020). The National Contingency Plan for SARS-CoV-2 Infection served as the primary document that guided the DGS and the Ministry of Health's reaction to the pandemic in terms of crisis management (DGS, 2020). Measures including illness surveillance, testing and tracking, healthcare response, and communication initiatives, travel restrictions, curfews, and the shutdown of non-essential companies were all part of the National Contingency Plan (DGS, 2020; Governo de Portugal, 2020). To coordinate the country's reaction to the pandemic, the government has formed a task force known as the Operational Task Force for COVID-19. Representatives from several governmental organizations, including the Ministry of Health, the National Civil Protection Authority, and the Armed Forces, among others, made up the task force. A Risk Communication Plan for Public Health Emergencies was launched in March 2020 (DGS) but it was never really pursued. In that plan, dealing with uncertainties is one of the most relevant points. However, uncertainty was dealt poorly since the inception of the pandemic news. It is important to underline that, like other countries, since the beginning, the Government and the DGS held public and daily press conferences, always with the presence of DGS head and either the prime or the health minister. The lack of personal protective equipment, testing supplies, and medical personnel were only a few of the difficulties the crisis management had to deal with (DGS, 2020). There were also concerns about the capacity of the healthcare system to handle a surge in cases, especially in the intensive care units.

The socio-political, legal, and ethical factors that influenced the government's preparedness and response to the pandemic in Portugal include the country's decentralized healthcare system, which allowed for greater flexibility in decision-making at the local level. The strong sense of community and solidarity among the Portuguese people also contributed to

compliance with the restrictions and measures implemented by the government (DGS, 2020). Additionally, the government had to balance the need to protect public health with the need to maintain the tourism industry's viability, which was a delicate and difficult balance to achieve (Governo de Portugal, 2020). The legal framework in Portugal, which includes a constitution that guarantees citizens' rights and freedoms, also played a role in the government's response (Governo de Portugal, 2020) since it had to balance the need to protect public health with the need to respect citizens' rights, such as the freedom of movement and the right to work (Governo de Portugal, 2020). In sum, Portuguese government's response to the COVID-19 pandemic was a complex and multifaceted effort, influenced by various socio-political, legal, and ethical factors (DGS, 2020).

Barriers to implementation of what was planned

Portugal's aging population presented problems in terms of increasing viral susceptibility and healthcare demands (Nordic Welfare Centre, 2020) putting the healthcare system under additional strain to safeguard this vulnerable population. There was also limited capacity for testing and contact tracing, what made it challenging to properly detect and control the transmission of the virus (Público, 2020). In terms of public behaviour, it was difficult to get people to comply with some of the preventative measures at certain points in time (Público, 2020).

COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown:

In March 2020, a state of emergency was proclaimed that put Portugal on lockdown. Starting from May and over the summer, Portugal is no longer under a state of emergency and measures are relaxed. In Autumn 2020 cases rise again to a new maximum and from October, tighter measures are taken to stop the spread. In November, a new state of emergency is proclaimed, and the government makes restrictions tighter during the winter. To be more efficient in vaccination procedures, the government nominates a task force. The task force for the elaboration of the "Vaccination Plan against COVID-19 in Portugal", initially managed by Francisco Ramos, aims to ensure the coherence and execution of the plan and coordinate the work already done, among all the entities involved in the success of this operation (SNS, 2021a). In December 2020, the vaccination plan is presented, and the priority groups are people over 50 years old with associated pathologies, residents and workers in nursing homes, and health and essential services professionals. By the end of December, vaccines start being administrated. By January 2021, Portugal becomes the country in the world with the highest number of new cases per million inhabitants and big central hospitals announce they are overstrained, working beyond their capacity. In February 2021, the numbers of new deaths and infections are starting to drop. The pressure on hospitals is also beginning to decrease, with fewer hospital admissions and fewer people in intensive care. Francisco Ramos – the initial manager of the task force – is substituted by Vice Admiral Henrique Gouveia e Melo. This task force ended up being very successful and gained a lot of popular support.

“It was important to have a spokesperson, a public figure who is not the minister, who is not the general director of health, not the prime minister, it was important to have someone who communicated about the process.” (Portugal Expert 4)

As vaccination became more widely available, Portugal gradually lifted restrictions, removing the state of emergency in May 2021. In June 2021, Gouveia e Melo announces the creation of an "open house" so that people over 70 (and after that, gradually, younger people) who have been left out of the process can be vaccinated without an appointment. By July, more than half of the population is fully vaccinated. As of September 2021, Portugal had administered over 12 million vaccine doses and fully vaccinated over 6 million people (Our World in Data, 2021).

Omicron up until September 2022

The emergence of the Omicron variant in November 2021 led to a resurgence of COVID-19 cases. The government and health authorities responded by reintroducing some measures, such as mask mandates and capacity restrictions. By the end of December 2021 Portugal registers the highest number of new infections, but this is not reflected on the number of hospitalizations and deaths. In February 2022, DGS announces that the biggest surge in cases has passed, and measures are once again relaxed. Portugal's vaccination campaign and experience with the pandemic allowed for a more targeted response to the Omicron variant. As of September 2022, Portugal had fully vaccinated over 85% of its population, and the country had a relatively low number of daily cases (DN, 2021). One of the reasons, commonly used to explain this high adherence to the vaccination scheme was the fact that the national system of vaccination is relatively new and people have an acute perception of their positive effects with a other ailments as measles.

Changes in crisis response occurred in Portugal

During the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal, crisis response evolved to adapt to changing circumstances and challenges. The response initially focused on controlling the spread of the virus through measures such as lockdowns and business closures, but as vaccination became more available, the focus shifted to managing the impact of the virus on healthcare and the economy. One significant change was the introduction of the digital COVID-19 certificate, which allowed individuals to prove their vaccination status, negative test results, or recovery from COVID-19, facilitating travel within the EU and reopening sectors such as tourism and hospitality (European Commission, 2021). The integration of the National Civil Protection Authority within the Ministry of Internal Administration in September 2021 was a change in the allocation of responsibilities for crisis management, seen as a move to strengthen the government's response to crises (Government of Portugal, 2021). However, challenges in securing personal protective equipment and testing kits, as well as concerns about the capacity of the healthcare system to handle a surge in cases, remained (Our World in Data, 2022). Throughout the pandemic, the country had Marta Temido as Minister of Health, and Graça Freitas as director of the DGS. In August 2022, Marta Temido left their position and was

replaced by Manuel Pizarro (DN, 2022). Also, Graça Freitas left their position for normal retirement.

Communication and coordination were identified as key factors in effective crisis response (Santos et al., 2021). This coordination did not always happen as efficiently as necessary in terms of communicating with the population. It was mentioned that certain media groups still give voice to opinions less grounded in science, and that sometimes there was a lack of planning and unification in terms of information, creating inconsistencies. However, experts consider that there was a slight improvement over time, as the pandemic progressed.

“Overall, in 2020 it wasn’t that great. It was not always clear. Some measures were not properly explained. In a civilized Europe, people tend to obey according to their perception of rationality of what is happening and that requires someone with didactic qualities to explain why it is a certain way and not another.” (Expert 1)

“(…) This is what the plans must do, anticipate what will happen. Last year’s communication plan was not that, it was a global plan, not adapted, not customized and therefore it will never be as effective because it does not respond to real needs, it is a general plan and not specific.” (Expert 4)

Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors

The country’s decentralized healthcare system allowed for greater flexibility in decision-making at the local level, as mentioned before, allowing for a shift towards a more localized approach to crisis management. Measures to apply at the local level were established, considering the incidence, and it is determined that in the case of low-density territories, twice the values applied for the rest of the country are considered as reference values for the incidence. This way, having restrictions targeted to areas with higher incidence rates rather than nationwide measures (Observador, 2022) was one of the main changes in crisis response. Additionally, the fact that the two autonomous regions have regional health authorities and autonomy lead to different evolutions and responses to the pandemic. For example, even though both regions follow the states of emergency proclaimed at the national level, while Azores has 5 degrees of risk and different measures for each of them, Madeira does not distinguish between municipalities (even when it had one of the municipalities with higher accumulated incidence in the country) (Observador, 2021). Both Azores and Madeira registered a very low number of cases in the first months of the pandemic, an increase in incidence only around October/November 2020 and then again around January 2021. However, while in Madeira the decrease happened around March, in Azores, there was a decrease earlier, in February, but then a new increase in April 2021 (CNS, 2022). In terms of ethical factors, there was some public debate regarding COVID-19 vaccination (e.g., should vaccines be mandatory or not; should children be vaccinated or not, etc.) associated with the fears felt by the population. However, given the high adherence to COVID-19 vaccination by the Portuguese population, the question of making the vaccines mandatory did not arise and there was no need to discuss it by the government (so it did not influence crisis response) (RTP, 2021).

Reflections on pandemic management in Portugal

Several issues and successes were highlighted by the experts regarding pandemic management.

“The government decided to temporarily regularize all immigrants’ granting full access to public services, namely public health services (free medical care upon covid-symptomatic suspicion, vaccination and testing). This helped to cease discrimination against immigrants who do not have their situation regularized in Portugal and hence do not have financial means to receive the appropriate assistance” (expert 2).

This was an important measure particularly because it was implemented at a very early stage.

“Absence of interruption of water and sanitation services, in situations of non-compliance with the associated payments during the pandemic period. Regarding the levels of trust of these populations in government entities the perception is that in some cases it may have even increased the confidence” (expert 5).

The fast swift to other forms of working and education was stressed as a very positive consequence of the response:

“The reinforcement of the already existing infrastructure to hold online meetings and classes, both in his organization and in public institutions, was deemed as a success. The adoption of these technologies in the workplace was also seen as a good practice.” (expert 3)

“The transition to telework was successful allowing a team of 12-14 people to switch to working remotely without loss of productivity.” (expert 4)

“The pandemic and all that’s entailed created potential opportunities like teleworking, distant learning, news strategies to deal with vulnerable groups, and major connection between politicians and experts.” (expert 1)

One major issue was the lack of coordination between different levels of government, with some experts noting that local governments were often left out of decision-making processes or asked for involvement very late in the process. However, and despite the fact that articulation with local authorities was sometimes absent, it is important to underline those local authorities rapidly got in action to deal with the more vulnerable people:

“We found young people (...) who did not have regular employment contracts, the day after confinement they ended up on the street, (...) it was necessary to respond very quickly to all these people and all the measures that were built in terms of food, shelter, protection and later also vaccination, we created a program with the general health department and the regional health administration of Lisbon and Vale do Tejo to vaccinate all homeless people.(...) The yearly vaccination against the flu in the homeless population helped decrease the suspicion and resistance to the Covid-19 vaccination.” (expert 5)

Several experts praised Portugal's healthcare system for its response to the pandemic, including the expansion of ICU capacity and the use of telemedicine to support patient care.

Additionally, there was recognition of the importance of clear and consistent communication from the government and health authorities, particularly in the early stages of the pandemic. Although a huge discussion was undergoing in almost all phases that referred an absence of articulation between the public dimension of the NHS and the private providers:

“Portugal failed in not having mobilized efforts for the creation of public-private partnerships (...) Public health centers are units with their vast experience and perhaps were not duly heard by the Ministry of Health or the DGS. It’s also doubtful that within the public health system itself all involved were heard. The less people participating, the safer it would be to follow the line of work the government thought was the right one. The component of private health in Portugal should have been more explored in this collective effort to fight covid.” (expert 1)

One of the more peculiar questions raised in crisis risk communication is the fact that any message is connected with the messenger and the large majority of the receivers can’t help activate the negative or positive attitudes they have about the emitter (Palma-Oliveira, Trump, Wood & Linkov 2018; Palma-Oliveira, Trump & Linkov, 2021). Also, the communication of uncertainties is very important. That’s why even the expert point:

“Government ... were warned that principles such as transparency, not hiding information, communicating what we know and what we don't know and what we are doing to have information about what we don't know, these are all processes that can increase confidence in governmental entities in the management of the pandemic. Due to the new measures, a lot of confusion at the level of isolations, whether it was necessary to be isolated or not, giving as example the parents and schools who don't understand why whole classes have to stay at home when cases appear.” (expert 3)

Key Findings from the pandemic management in Portugal

Effective coordination and communication between different levels of government and stakeholders: During the pandemic, Portugal faced challenges related to the coordination and communication between different levels of government and stakeholders. As a lesson learned, experts have emphasized the importance of effective coordination and communication to improve crisis management in the future. This includes coordination between national and regional authorities, as well as with the private sector and civil society organizations (Palma-Oliveira & Trump, 2021).

Flexibility and adaptability in responding to changing circumstances: The pandemic highlighted the need for flexibility and adaptability in responding to changing circumstances. Portugal has been praised for its response to the Omicron variant, which included adapting measures in real-time to address the evolving situation. Experts stress the importance of maintaining this flexibility and adaptability in future pandemic response efforts.

Investing in healthcare system capacity and preparedness for future pandemics: The pandemic highlighted the need for increased investment in healthcare system capacity and preparedness for future pandemics. This includes investing in healthcare infrastructure,

medical supplies, and personnel training. Experts have called for increased funding to ensure that the healthcare system is better equipped to handle future crises.

Prioritizing equity and accessibility in vaccine distribution: The pandemic highlighted the importance of prioritizing equity and accessibility in vaccine distribution. Portugal has been praised for its vaccine rollout, which prioritized vulnerable populations such as the elderly and healthcare workers. Experts stress the importance of maintaining this focus on equity in future vaccine distribution efforts.

Addressing the social and economic impacts of the pandemic on vulnerable populations: The pandemic had a significant impact on vulnerable populations, including those who were already socially and economically disadvantaged. Experts stress the importance of acknowledging and addressing these impacts, including increased investment in social welfare programs, such as unemployment benefits and housing support. Lessons learned from pandemic management in Portugal include the importance of effective communication and coordination among government agencies and with the public, incorporating the perspectives and needs of marginalized and vulnerable populations in crisis response, a more localized approach to crisis management, and the need for flexibility in decision-making at the local level (Sousa-Pinto et al., 2021; WHO, 2021).

In a nutshell, a basic problem is how to deal with uncertainty. Although the experts seem conscient how to deal with it, it is difficult for the governance bodies to apply it:

“Regarding uncertainty, one needs to keep track of the science, but it is not possible to say that we don’t know. However, since there is never 100% of certainty, we need to be able to say that there are no certainties, but that we are going in a certain direction with a high probability and in another direction with less probability. If we wait for absolute certainty, we will follow the virus and let it get advantage over us.” (expert 3)

Public react to the crisis management

The public's reaction to the crisis management and changes during the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal varied throughout the course of the pandemic, with different social outcomes and impacts on society. During the early stages of the pandemic, the Portuguese government was praised for its swift and effective response to the crisis. In a survey conducted by Eurobarometer in May 2020, 72% of Portuguese respondents expressed satisfaction with the government's response to the pandemic, higher than the EU average of 62% (Eurobarometer, 2020). However, as the pandemic continued and restrictions on daily life persisted, frustration and fatigue among the public grew. In November 2020, a protest the government's COVID-19 measures drew thousands of people to the streets of Lisbon, with some participants expressing their belief that the government was exaggerating the threat of the virus (Reuters, 2020). Additionally, the pandemic has had significant economic impacts in Portugal, particularly in industries such as tourism and hospitality. Unemployment rates increased from 6.5% in Q4 2019 to 7.9% in Q4 2020 (Eurostat, 2021), and there have been reports of businesses struggling to stay afloat due to the pandemic (Portugal Resident, 2021). In terms

of social outcomes, the pandemic has also highlighted inequalities and disparities within Portuguese society. Low-income and marginalized communities have been disproportionately impacted by the pandemic, with higher rates of infection and greater economic insecurity (ECDC, 2020). Overall, the public's reaction to the crisis management and changes during the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal has been mixed.

3.7.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

At the government level, we did not exactly find specific communications for vulnerable populations, perhaps because they may be different from each other and need help at different levels, and perhaps identification and communication is needed at a more local level, such as in parishes or municipalities. Although, the Government frequently communicated (via news on the website) that, in coordination with local authorities, they “will remain attentive to the needs of the most vulnerable populations in the face of the pandemic, among which are some Roma communities, and will provide the necessary measures to help these vulnerable communities” (ARS, 2020). We can also find a statement advertising a youth volunteering initiative to help disadvantaged communities. “In order to support, strengthen and qualify the community support responses carried out by Portuguese parishes during the isolation period, the Portuguese Institute of Sports and Youth (IPDJ), in partnership with the National Association of Parishes (ANAFRE), promotes the volunteering action "Greater Support" (Government of Portugal, 2020).

In the beginning of the pandemic, the Portuguese government, public health system, and civil society organizations acknowledged and addressed several vulnerabilities among different groups, including:

- **Elderly:** As one of the most vulnerable groups to COVID-19, the government implemented measures to protect the elderly, such as setting up specific care homes for COVID-19 positive patients and providing support for home care. (Sources: Reuters, 2020; World Health Organization, 2020).
- **Chronically Ill Patients:** The expansion of telemedicine services for individuals with chronic health conditions was promoted (ECDC, 2020).
- **Healthcare workers:** The government recognized the importance of protecting healthcare workers, providing personal protective equipment (PPE), and offering mental health support to those on the front lines. (Sources: European Commission, 2020; SIC Notícias, 2020)
- **Homeless population:** Civil society organizations, in collaboration with the government, provided temporary accommodation and access to basic needs for the homeless population. (Sources: The Guardian, 2020; Cáritas, 2020)
- **Immigrants and refugees:** The government provided support for immigrants and refugees, including access to healthcare, education, and social welfare benefits. (Sources: Migration Policy Institute, 2020; Expresso, 2021). The Government decided that immigrants and asylum seekers with residence permit requests pending at SEF

were in a regular situation until 30 June 2020 and they would have access to the same rights and support that the Portuguese have.

New vulnerable groups were acknowledged over the course of the pandemic. For example:

- Low-income workers: The pandemic highlighted the vulnerability of low-income workers, who often work in essential jobs and may lack access to adequate PPE or paid sick leave. (Sources: The Guardian, 2020; Público, 2020)
- Children and youth: School closures and social distancing measures affected the education and mental health of children and youth, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. (Sources: UNESCO, 2020; UNICEF, 2020)
- People with disabilities: The pandemic had a disproportionate impact on people with disabilities, who may face challenges accessing healthcare and social support services. (Sources: European Disability Forum, 2020; BBC News, 2020)

In addition, the government launched a campaign to promote awareness of the risks of COVID-19 among vulnerable groups and to encourage adherence to public health guidelines. This campaign included targeted messaging and information dissemination through social media and other communication channels (WHO, 2020).

Overall, the Portuguese government, public health system, and civil society organizations demonstrated a willingness to acknowledge and address vulnerabilities among different groups during the pandemic, although there were still challenges in ensuring that support and resources were provided effectively and equitably. For example, there have been reports of high infection rates and inadequate protective measures in nursing homes (Público, 2021), and some have criticized the government's response to the needs of low-income households and unemployed individuals (Observador, 2021).

The amount of pandemic related fake news online and on media outlets was substantial, including essentially conspiracy theories and information not scientifically based. In 2020, almost 1/3 of the people living in the most economically deprived households reported difficulties in distinguishing between real and fake news and almost 40% felt anxiety while reading the news (CNS, 2022), illustrating, therefore, the way the communication measures exacerbated vulnerabilities. The economic impact of the pandemic has also affected low-income families and people in precarious jobs, leading to food insecurity and difficulties in paying for basic needs such as rent and utilities. Domestic violence was one of the concerns during the pandemic, and civil society organizations launched campaigns to raise awareness and provide support for victims. Domestic violence crimes were less reported and registered in 2020, compared to 2019, but that does not mean that there were less crimes – only that they were less reported. It is important to note that there were still 32 voluntary manslaughter crimes in contexts of domestic violence registered in 2020. The suspension of school activities may also have left children more vulnerable to violence, and excessive exposure to screens may have increased the risk of online exploitation of children and youth (CNS, 2022). The pandemic has also had an educational impact, particularly for children from low-income

families and those with special needs. Host schools were established to receive children and young people unable to take online classes at home and measures were implemented to support remote learning and provide technological equipment. Still, the learning gap created was insufficiently dealt with.

Several surveys revealed increased levels of anxiety and stress at the start of the pandemic, with high percentages of respondents reporting fear, sadness, worry and sleep disturbance. These symptoms occurred more frequently in people who reported difficulty in finding a work-family balance, concerns about maintaining work or income, and worries about the future. There was a reduction in these negative symptoms over the course of the pandemic, but it was less evident in groups like women, unemployed people and chronically ill patients (CNS, 2022).

Additionally, housing politics generated problems for vulnerable groups that were revealed to be difficult to manage. In general, the pandemic exacerbated the housing problems.

“People are continuously arriving on the street. Without a housing policy based on affordability and quality (without the creation of ghettos, urban structures that make it difficult to fight the pandemic) to provide decent housing in large cities. What we observed was many families living in rooms in Lisbon, which puts them at a bigger risk of spreading the virus between them.” (expert 3).

Furthermore, the allocation of resources to the COVID-19 response resulted in the negligence of the non-COVID services. This affected especially groups with other pathologies that need continued consultation and treatment – like chronically ill patients – therefore creating new vulnerabilities (CNS, 2002). The suspension of face-to-face healthcare has led to a very significant drop in the number of first and subsequent consultations and scheduled surgeries. It is estimated that more than half of cancer patients may have had their diagnosis delayed, as well as many cases of diabetes. The delay in rescheduling healthcare and the absence of specific communication directed at people with illness could have a significant impact on health in the short, medium and long term (CNS, 2020).

3.8 Sweden

2.1.1. Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

Sweden is a parliamentary democracy where parties in the national parliament are represented in proportion to their opinion strength for four years periods. The government is appointed by the prime minister who needs to be supported by the parliament. On the national level there are also government agencies with responsibility for different areas. These have a high degree of independence in relation to the government. Sweden is also a highly decentralised governance system, where the regional and local level have certain responsibilities and high levels of independence. Both regional and local level have elected councils and the right to levy income taxes. The regional level (21 regions) administers health care and other areas. National government conducts an oversight of the medical services they deliver but in terms of formal jurisdiction, central government lacks authority in relation to the regions. Consequently, agencies in the healthcare sector have no remit over the regions delivering healthcare. Their only means of guiding the regions is to provide information and through informal networks. Local government is allocated to 290 *kommuner* (municipalities), each with an elected assembly and the right to levy income taxes and to charge fees for various services such as school and elderly care. To sum up, the national government and central government agencies manage and coordinate a highly decentralized system. However, the government system is conducive to allow expertise to influence policy and administrative action. Given that much of the expertise is found in government agencies and to a lesser extent in government ministries, ministries normally invite or consult with experts in the agencies.

All three levels of Swedish government (national, regional, local) are involved in the healthcare system. At the national level, the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs is responsible for overall health and healthcare policy, working closely with national government agencies, especially the National Board for Health and Welfare (NBHW) and the Public Health Agency (PHA). The role of the government on the national level is to establish principles and guidelines and establish the overall political agenda for Swedish health care. This is accomplished through legislation and regulations, or through agreements with the Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions (SALAR), which represents local and regional authorities.

Principles of Pandemic Management

Crisis management in Sweden is based on three fundamental principles: 1) The principle of responsibility - that whoever is responsible for an activity in normal situations also has a corresponding responsibility in the event of disturbances/crisis in society. Responsible actors also have a responsibility to act in uncertain situations. The extended responsibility principle means that the actors must support and collaborate with each other. 2) The principle of

proximity - that societal disturbances must be handled where they occur and by those who are most closely affected and responsible, and 3) The principle of equality - that actors should not make major changes in the organization than the situation requires. Activities during societal disruptions must function as under normal conditions, as far as possible.

In 2005, the National Board of Health and Welfare (NBHW) was commissioned by the Government to produce a national pandemic plan that included plans for national interventions and provided a basis for regional planning⁶¹. It was revised in 2009, and later in 2012 after the swine flu, and again in 2015 after the Ebola outbreak⁶². Since 2015, the Public Health Agency (PHA) coordinates pandemic preparedness at national level in Sweden and provides support for planning at regional and local levels. The pandemic plan was revised again in 2019. The current plan consists of three volumes:

- Folkhälsomyndigheten, *Pandemiberedskap. Hur vi förbereder oss – ett kunskapsunderlag*, 2019. [*Pandemic preparedness. How we prepare – a knowledge-base*]
- Folkhälsomyndigheten, *Pandemiberedskap. Hur vi kommunicerar – ett kunskapsunderlag*, 2019 [*Pandemic preparedness. How we communicate – a knowledge-base*].
- Folkhälsomyndigheten, *Pandemiberedskap. Tillgång till och användning av läkemedel – en vägledning*, 2019. [*Pandemic preparedness. Access to and use of pharmaceuticals – guidelines*].

It should be noted that the Swedish *constitution* does not specifically regulate crises or emergencies in peacetime, only during war or in danger of war. Peacetime crises thus fall under ordinary regulations. Consequently, an emergency permit or curfew cannot be imposed in Sweden during peacetime. As pointed out above, the decentralised system and independent government agencies limited the national government possibilities to enforce strong measures. This said, arguments have questioned this conclusion, arguing the national government does have more executive power in crisis management, but chose to rely on expert government agencies during the pandemic. However, there are clear signs on how the decentralized system made centralized crisis management more difficult. In short, as the regions were responsible for both health care and vaccination, Sweden experienced somewhat different strategies during the pandemic. The decentralized governance system is said to slow down decision making and blur accountability mechanisms. However, in deference to the decentralized system scholars also point out advantages in that local

⁶¹ Socialstyrelsen, *Beredskapsplanering för en pandemisk influensa*, december 2005.

⁶² Socialstyrelsen, *Beredskapsplanering för en pandemisk influensa*, december 2012, (rev. april 2015).

authorities take responsibility and try to solve problems in local settings instead of waiting on national decisions.

3.8.1 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

The measures became more strict as time passed and when the Pandemic Act was introduced stronger measures could be implemented. In general were stronger measures applied during the second wave compared to the first one and there were plans to take even stronger in December 2021. However, these were never introduced as the effects of vaccination led to limited death toll and severe illness among the public. See more details in main text.

The Corona Commission stated that the Swedish response during the first wave was too slow and too limited. This could be interpreted as a consequence of the general Swedish pandemic strategy where politicians rely on expert authorities, but maybe also a “path dependency” where experts relied on previous experiences of influenza treatment and possibly also fear of “doing too much” which led to a backlash after the Swine flu vaccination campaign (350 children and adolescents suffered from narkolepsia after taking the vaccine). See main text for more information.

COVID-19 management in Sweden

When WHO on March 11th declared COVID-19 a pandemic preparation had been made in different governmental bodies and agencies for quite some time. The PHA had for example implemented the crisis organization as they realized COVID-19 would require different needs compared to ordinary daily work. Similar discussions and decisions were made in other national, regional, and local government organizations. Pandemic plans on different levels were activated – which have been developed after the Swine flu influenza in 2011 – however, they were mostly found to be less valuable for decision making during the COVID-19 pandemic. A general communication plan was also available from the PHA.⁶³

The national government took a large amount of decision about crisis management during the pandemic, still it should be stressed that informal dialogue and meetings characterized a large part of the work between the political and agency domain which can be illustrated by how the Director General of the PHA described the daily work:

...the head of the authority has had a very close dialogue, not only with the state secretary at the Ministry of Social Affairs at the political level, but also with the entire government that Johan Carlsson (DG at the time) was invited to several government meetings. Johan and I with several department heads when I had that role have participated in party

63

<https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/contentassets/2f2a536f14e54a83b983594b4b71c3d4/pandemiberedskap-kommunicera.pdf>

leadership meetings at the political level. Been invited to the crisis management council on several occasions and presented shorter status reports, etc.

So even if there was preparation for a health crisis, decisions taken were less strict compared with other countries. The Swedish COVID-19 strategy focused more on “nudges” than strict measures. This was partly due to lack of legislation not making lockdown an option, but the Swedish government and its expert agencies also made somewhat different analyses of the situation compared to other (Nordic) countries. This was a consequence of giving expert agencies like PHA and NBHW the leading role. The decisions to keep society open, with no closed borders and kindergartens and schools open, Sweden stood out internationally. Even if critique against this strategy was found, the public generally approved and the support for both government and government agencies were high, especially during the first wave of the pandemic. The image of the open Swedish society should, however, be nuanced. Public gatherings were limited, first to 500 and later to smaller numbers. Legislation was also used to limit the spread of the virus by introducing restrictions for restaurants and a national ban for visiting care homes was implemented. Remote teaching was introduced in high schools and at universities and public theatres, sport venues and other public events were closed. So even if Sweden did not have a strict lockdown, one could argue it was a “soft” lockdown in practice.

The expert regime of pandemic management followed the same procedures used in earlier pandemics, where the PHA was in charge and expected to issue recommendations for regions, municipalities, and citizens, based on scientific evidence. Dealing with the virus was a question of collecting facts, analysing them in a scientific way and suggesting measures based on the conclusions. This strategy was from the beginning (March and April 2020) widely supported by all political parties, news media and citizens. The chief epidemiologist Anders Tegnell was given a key role as he presented daily analyses and recommendations by the PHA. He also gained the status of a popular icon for his calm communicative style and his steady appeal to react according to ‘what we know in the scientific community.’ No recommendations were presented until there was what the PHA deemed as solid scientific proof to back them up.

This “expert regime” was in line with a general expectation of how pandemics should be managed, where the quite large expert government agencies take the lead and politicians lean on them for guidance, even if they in the end take the final decisions and balance different needs and interests of society. The Nordic countries are similar in many ways, but the pandemic management was to some extent different in Denmark, Finland and Norway where politicians (especially the prime minister) were more visible as communicators-in-chief compared to Sweden, where the chief epidemiologist was the central communicator of how to fight the pandemic. This became apparent on the 2 p.m. daily (weekday) press conferences which were initiated by the government. From March 4th, 2020, until May 2020, the PHA held 198 press conferences.

The focus on the PHA had accountability consequences since critique of how the virus spread was directed toward the agency about issues they were not in charge of. As an example, the General Director of PHA explains how the PHA was blamed for deficits in elderly care which caused a high number of deaths of COVID-19 in care homes.

Exactly what I was getting at, that as far as it is concerned, since the agency then received a government assignment to hold these press conferences, it was understood that we (PHA) were responsible for everything. It became a narrative, that we had responsibility for elderly care, that we had responsibility for protective equipment in hospitals. Then, issues that do not lie with us, but for which we had to cover shots.

The “expert regime” was also prevalent at other levels of governance. Politicians on the regional and local levels relied on the expertise in the administration to manage the pandemic in an efficient way and viewed their main role as provider of resources to hospitals, and other social services instead of putting themselves in the front seat of crisis management. One regional politician describes this trust in their organization and willingness to solve problems like this:

“Instead, we (the region) quickly prepared study materials in healthcare in nursing homes and special accommodations and such, which we only offered and distributed online, and they could work with the various units and such. So, I think the inventiveness was great and the desire to solve problems was great. What you know about how slow care is, when you must change health care, you were amazed at how much they can do when they want to.”

From the regional and local perspective, the national crisis management was considered ineffective, even if they relied on PHA for advice to limit spread. Especially the information and support from the infection control units and their doctors seen as important. Collaboration between regional and local levels was generally viewed as functional and focused on solving problems. The SALAR was judged as an important player in coordinating crisis management between the national and regional/local level of governance, but the ability for crisis management on the national level was questioned and arguments were raised for centralizing crisis management to the national level. Politicians and government agencies on regional and local levels also addressed criticism against what they saw as inefficient crisis management, where government agencies were given tasks, of which they had no previous experience. Critique was also addressed toward national government agencies for collecting a lot of data without any feedback of how they were used. This is for example addressed by a regional politician interviewed in COVINFORM, but similar opinions have been expressed in other studies.

“They made the mistake of building up organizations not existing before the pandemic. They gave the county administrative board a mission to collect a lot of information. They didn't have an organization for this. It got messy and created some irritation with us and

our employees. The National Board of Health and Welfare, was no particular support ...and the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency were probably mostly invisible. There is probably a need for a crisis management organization in the state that is more well-trained and well-trimmed, that has greater powers, right?"

The use of facemasks was a recurrent issue in the Swedish debate, where the PHA argued there was no scientific proof showing they would limit the spread of COVID-19. Critics of the Swedish strategy pointed out how Sweden in the fall of 2020 was one of the very few countries in the world dismissing a general use of facemasks. During the second wave this also changed as PHA recommended the use of facemask public transportation in the beginning of 2021. This shows the gradual strengthening of the Swedish pandemic restrictions, which became apparent during the second wave of COVID-19.

The second wave hit Sweden late fall 2020, which was a bit unexpected since Sweden had widespread virus dissemination of COVID-19 during the first wave in the Spring of 2020. It was believed Sweden would be less affected by the second wave, but this belief turned out to be wrong. In December and January death tolls were high once again.

One important change of Sweden's crisis management strategy was the adoption of the temporary Act to prevent the spread of COVID-19. The legislation is intended to give the government the authority to adopt more binding communicable disease control measures than was previously possible. The Act entered into force on 10 January 2021 and is in effect until 30 September 2021. The COVID-19 Act is a framework law through which the parliament temporarily gave the government the authority to issue ordinances containing more binding communicable disease control measures. The new Act was intended to allow accurate measures, adapted to the conditions of different activities, and to not unnecessarily hinder activities that can be conducted in an infection-safe manner. If necessary to prevent infection, it will be possible to introduce special limitations regarding public gatherings and events, commercial centres, public transport, domestic flights, and places for private gatherings.

Restrictions for non-European travellers had been in place since 2020, who then needed a negative test to enter the country. In February 2021 a similar request was introduced for EU/EES countries including the Nordic countries.⁶⁴ The PHA also recommended all travellers (even Swedish citizens) without symptoms to take a COVID test and isolate themselves after entering Sweden. These recommendations were removed June 1st and citizens from the Nordic countries did not even need to show a negative test anymore to enter the country. As the EU vaccine certificate was introduced, it replaced the requirement for a negative test result for EU/EES travellers from June 30th of 2021.

⁶⁴ <https://www.regeringen.se/artiklar/2020/04/fragor-och-svar-om-inreseforbud-till-sverige/>

The measures related to public gatherings were lifted in the summer of 2021. Cultural and sports events started to allow audiences from June onwards. First, 500 persons were allowed on outdoor events (50 indoors)⁶⁵, in July 3000 outdoors (300 indoors) and at the same time limitations of opening hours in restaurants were removed. From the end of September all restrictions for sports and cultural events and public gatherings were lifted. No vaccine certificates were mandatory, instead the PHA was given the task to produce recommendations for individuals and non-vaccinated citizens on how to act in crowded areas. At this point the PHA also removed regulations about keeping distance in restaurants and advised people to work from home (if possible). Despite this, the Pandemic Act was prolonged.

The spread of the virus was low during the fall of 2021, few persons were hospitalized, and the number of casualties were limited to a few persons each day. The vaccination program rolled out as planned, and the shortage of vaccine availability and difficulties to book appointments for vaccination, which had been a problem in the summer, were solved. At the end of September, 78 percent of the adult population had received one dose and 69 percent two doses of the COVID-19 vaccine. At this time decisions were already made to also include adolescents between 12 and 15 years in the vaccination program.

There were not at the time any clear signs on rising infection rates, hospitalization or deaths related to COVID-19 in Sweden. However, due to a more alarming development in other parts of Europe the government and the PHA decided to prepare for a more difficult situation. Vaccine certificates were declared as being possible to use for concerts and other public events with more than 100 visitors from December 1st.⁶⁶

On December 8th, the new Prime Minister, Magdalena Andersson⁶⁷ - who was more active in communicating the pandemic compared to her predecessor Stefan Löfven - gave a press conference declaring a plan for how Sweden should meet an increased spread of the virus. The plan had three steps where Step 1 was implemented the same day as the press conference. It contained advice to adult residents to keep social distance in public places. If necessary two more steps could be implemented. Step 2: with significantly higher spread, vaccine certificates would be mandatory for public gatherings and more limited access to these would be imposed. Step 3: with high-level spread and a strained situation for health

⁶⁵ <http://www.svensklive.se/nyheter-2/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2021/11/vaccinationsbevis-kan-kravas-for-tilltrade-till-allmanna-sammankomster-och-offentliga-tillstallningar/>

⁶⁷ Stefan Löfven resigned from office and Magdalena Andersson became the first female Swedish Prime Minister. Both are Social Democratic politicians and the resignation of Stefan Löfven was not related to the pandemic, but to the general election 2022 where he would not candidate for a new term of office.

care, limited opening hours for restaurants and maximum number of visitors in shops and malls would be employed again.

The change of Prime Minister (and government) led to some changes in the management of the pandemic. The Corona Commission⁶⁸ later criticized the government led by Prime Minister Löfven for giving too much power to the PHA, regions and municipalities. Their audit was critical to the strategy of giving PHA the leading role in fighting the pandemic, even if it is the traditional way of crisis management of Swedish public administration. They argued a more visible and distinct leadership could and should have been effectuated. The new Prime Minister Andersson reorganized the government chancellery and moved responsibility for crisis management closer to the Cabinet office (Statsrådsberedningen). Another change of leadership was that the General Director of the PHA, Johan Carlsson, was replaced (retirement), by Karin Tegmark Wisell. Since Tegmark Wisell was co-director to Carlsson, this meant no significant change of strategy or leadership, even if there were signs of the new Director General being more visible compared to her predecessor, who more often let chief epidemiologist Anders Tegnell be the spokesperson for the PHA.

On December 21st Sweden again introduced mandatory vaccine certificates for adult foreign citizens entering Sweden from EU/EES and the Nordic countries. Other certificates showing vaccine status, recovery from COVID-19 the last six months or a recent negative test could also be valid.⁶⁹

On December 23rd the government decided to implement more strict measures including a vaccine certificate, mandatory seating with social distance, limited numbers of attendees etc. to be used for public gatherings and public events. These regulations were strengthened on January 12th, since opening hours for restaurants and pubs were limited (close at 23.00 latest). On January 19th a new limitation of public gatherings and public events were executed and the new maximum for attendees was 500 (seated) persons. The General Director of PHA also declared that these measures were valid for all residents, both vaccinated and non-vaccinated because of uncertainty to what extent the vaccines protected from the Omicron variant of the virus.⁷⁰

The infection rates were rising around Christmas 2021 and in the beginning of 2022, and the levels kept being high as the Omicron variant spread in Sweden during the first months of the

⁶⁸ https://coronakommissionen.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/sverige-under-pandemin-volym-2_webb-slutbetankande.pdf

⁶⁹ <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2021/12/andringar-i-inreseforbuden-till-sverige/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.msn.com/sv-se/nyheter/international/d%3a4rf%3ab6r-g%3a4ller-restriktioner-%3a4ven-vaccinerade-%e2%80%9domikron%e2%80%9d/vi-AAS1Cee>

new year.⁷¹ What was different compared to previous waves, were the significantly higher levels of infection rates, but still less hospitalization of COVID-19 cases and lower death rates compared with earlier waves.

Even if the pandemic was still prevalent in Sweden, the Government decided on February 8th to remove most of the restrictions, such as limitations for public gatherings and events, such as social distance requirements, mandatory seating, and group size in restaurants and pubs (previously 8 persons was the maximum for persons from the same group/family/company). Further, recommendations to use face masks in public transportation were also removed. Advice to avoid attendance to and organizing of sports events or other meetings were also abandoned and companies and universities were advised to start the process of ending distant work and remote teaching. Some recommendations were still in place, such as campaigns for vaccination, and advice for the non-vaccinated to avoid crowded public gatherings. In terms of traveling, EU vaccine certificates were no longer needed for travellers from EU/EES countries when entering Sweden. The PHA General Director explained the decision by first declaring that the COVID-19 pandemic still was a serious problem globally, but also that a new approach was needed, which was to learn how to live with the virus. The argument posed was that immunity in society was high and that continuing with strict measures might cause severe problems in society. Similar judgements and decisions were made at the same time in Denmark and Norway.⁷²

On April 1st COVID-19 no longer was classified as a socially dangerous disease, which means it is no longer subject to the Infection Protection Act, further the Pandemic Act was also removed. The last restrictions were lifted, such as travel restrictions from countries outside EU/EES[14]. Still, the Government decided that a doctor's duty to report COVID-19 should continue to be mandatory to facilitate the tracking of the infection.⁷³

Evaluations of the Government strategy

After the outbreak of the pandemic, on 30 June 2020, the Swedish government, following the request of the Swedish Parliament, appointed the so-called Corona Commission (CC), an independent commission assigned to evaluate the Government's response to the COVID-19 pandemic in Sweden. It was formed of a panel with 8 experts from different sectors.

⁷¹<https://www.msn.com/sv-se/nyheter/international/d%c3%a4rf%c3%b6r-g%c3%a4ller-restriktioner-%c3%a4ven-vaccinerade-%e2%80%9domikron%e2%80%9d/vi-AAS1Cee>

⁷² <https://www.expressen.se/nyheter/coronaviruset/sverige-danmark-norge-darfor-oppnar-vi-upp-igen/>

⁷³ <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2022/03/tillfalliga-smittskyddslagar-sutar-galla-den-31-mars/>

In December 2020, a report by the commission criticized the Government for failing to protect people living in elderly homes or with home care to the high level of community spread.⁷⁴ In October 2021, the commission's second report characterized the Government's response in early 2020 as "insufficient" and "late"⁷⁵. The Commission's final report was presented in February 2022.

In their first report⁷⁶, the CC concluded that "the strategy to protect the elderly has failed" and that "the general spread of infection in society is most likely the single most important factor behind the high spread of infection in Sweden's special care homes." Shortcomings in the organisation and staffing of elderly care were pointed out and it was argued that "elderly care was unprepared and ill-equipped to deal with a pandemic." The CC argued that the shortcomings in elderly care had been known for a long time and that current and previous governments were responsible. The late attention given to the problems in elderly care and the length of time it took to identify the need for protective equipment in elderly care was also criticized.

In its second and final reports⁷⁷, the CC argued that the Government's and the public health authority's choice of advice and recommendations rather than closing schools and pre-schools was the right one. However, the advice should have been formulated as clear rules of conduct and not open to interpretation, such as "avoiding unnecessary travel" and keeping "an appropriate distance". They also noted that unprecise advice and recommendations made even greater demands when it came to communicating with people with a first language other than Swedish, or who for other reasons had difficulty taking in messages.

The CC believed that the PHA and the government took "too few, too late and too weak" measures compared to neighbouring Nordic countries and in relation to the spread of the disease, and that the disease therefore spread unnecessarily in society. Returning winter holiday travellers should have been quarantined, entry bans imposed earlier, and the attendance limit for public gatherings lowered. Legal support would have been needed for early closure of public places, such as shopping centres, swimming pools, restaurants, cultural and sporting events, and hairdressers' salons. The authorities should not have required full evidence to recommend protective measures, instead they should have recommended face masks in public places as soon as they were available.

The Corona Commission also stated that coordination of the responsibilities both within national, regional, and municipal level, as well as between the levels, has been a challenge. It expresses that "The system of preparedness is based on geographical responsibility for specific areas. But this arrangement can become unclear in a crisis centered on health care

⁷⁴ *SOU 2020:8, Delbetänkande 1 – Äldreomsorgen under pandemin, December, 2020.*

⁷⁵ *SOU 2021:89, Delbetänkande 2 _ Sverige under pandemin, February 2021.*

⁷⁶ *SOU 2020:8, Delbetänkande 1 – Äldreomsorgen under pandemin, December, 2020.*

⁷⁷ *SOU 2021:89, Delbetänkande 2 _ Sverige under pandemin, February 2021; SOU 2022:10, Slutbetänkande – Sverige under pandemin, February 2022.*

and disease prevention and control. At a regional level, area responsibility rests on county administrative boards, while health care and disease control are handled by regional councils in the same geographical areas. It is far from evident how this lack of clarity should be reduced. /.../ experience of the pandemic has highlighted the importance of the proposals for regional-level administrative reform and clearer central government control, repeatedly presented by earlier inquiries. The Commission considers that the question of far-reaching administrative reform, advocated by those inquiries, must as soon as possible, and in earnest, be made the subject of new, open-minded deliberations.”⁷⁸

3.8.2 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

The communication efforts by the government and PHA was centred around reaching the general public through mass media, where the press conferences turned out to be more effective than expected. This said, the expert interviews with the Communications Director (CD) at the PHA stressed they already at the beginning of the pandemic had knowledge and preparation for reaching out to vulnerable groups.

“And where we already know before - it's nothing new - there you have to put a lot of gunpowder to reach out, and that's what we've tried to do. Cooperation, I just want to say, is the whole watchword of it. No one does it themselves, but they do it in collaboration with other authorities and regions and so on. It's super important, it's absolutely crucial.”

The PHA talks about “customized communication” which is tailored messages and channels for specific target groups and the PHA early identified groups with low socio-economic status as having need for tailored information, but migrants with low trust and non-Swedish speaking inhabitants were also early on recognized as being more vulnerable. Later, other groups were put on the list for being more vulnerable as for example disabled, chronically ill, obesity and pregnant. For some of these groups were messages tailored, for example were pregnant women addressed with vaccine communication, but obesity was not addressed any particular way and the NBHW kept the level for obesity as a risk group to a BMI +40, even if studies showed the risk was significantly higher even with a BMI +30.⁷⁹ Apart from these were of course also elderly people identified as being more vulnerable from the very beginning and were therefore advised to keep social distance and limit social contacts to a minimum.

To customize the pandemic communication, PHA translated material to different languages, tailored messages to different groups and cooperated with civil society organizations (churches and mosques) to get in contact with migrant dense communities. Government agencies, regions and municipalities have also used health communicators, vaccine communicators to communicate with people living in migrant dense areas. And even if

⁷⁸ *SOU 2022:10, Slutbetänkande – Sverige under pandemin, Summary in English, February 2022, p. 24.*

⁷⁹ <https://www.dagensmedicin.se/specialistomraden/infektion/socialstyrelsen-vanlig-fetma-inte-riskgrupp/>

information is seen as crucial the PHA stresses availability as a key factor, especially for vaccination.

“For those target groups, we have - after all, printed material is definitely successful - so we have had posters in 20-30 different languages with simple messages and to be at hand. But what are A and O - it doesn't matter how much you communicate if there is not at the same time a super high availability.”

In December 2021 the government released a plan for improving communication to the public, especially targeting groups where vaccination rates were lower compared to the average population. This task was given to the PHA, National Board of Health and Welfare, Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency, and Medical Products Agency to make sure vaccination about COVID-19 was gathered, easily accessible and updated. The Government agencies should also acknowledge aspects of dis- and misinformation in relation to vaccination.⁸⁰

As pointed out a demographic problem with vaccination was the reluctance to take the vaccine among citizens with migrant backgrounds, and especially those living in migrant dense suburbs. This skewness in vaccination rates was visible already in the Spring 2021 and the PHA and other agencies tried to understand why this was happening and what to do about it.⁸¹ National vaccination campaigns from the PHA and regions (responsible for vaccination) were launched, also with information in different languages. Decisions were taken during the fall to let local needs guide the campaigns, and examples of local vaccinations/health guides and drop-in vaccination outside mosques, vaccine-buses and other activities were tried out⁸². To further increase vaccination rates, the government allocated 40 million Swedish crowns (app. 4 million Euros) at the end of September to speed up the vaccination program among groups who had not yet been vaccinated.

Even if these attempts are evaluated as quite successful, there are still significant gaps in vaccination against COVID-19 in Sweden depending on where you are born in 2022. In May that year the vaccination rate (two does) among the oldest (+60 years) were above 95 percent, while being approximately ten percent lower among those born outside Sweden. Similar gaps were found in all age cohorts and the largest differences related to where you are born are

⁸⁰ <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2020/12/informationsuppdrag-om-vaccination-mot-covid-19/>

⁸¹ <https://www.svt.se/nyheter/inrikes/folkhalsomyndigheten-kritiserar-nar-utrikesfodda-halkar-efter-i-vaccineringen-detta-har-vi-varnat-om>

⁸² <https://news.cision.com/se/liberalerna-i-stockholmsregionen/r/fyra-provtagningsbussar-mot-covid-startas,c3419047>

found between middle aged residents (app. 35 percent units).⁸³ Further, there are socio-economic factors related to taking the vaccine. Income plays a role, where lower income – independent of where you are born – relates to lower vaccination, especially among those being younger than 60 years. The same tendencies can be found between people with different levels of education.

The Vaccination coordinator in Västra Götaland explains how they use different strategies to reach out to different “hard-to-reach” groups:

Our focus has been on accessibility and presence and a lot of focus on working on what already works: health interpreter, cultural guides, collaboration with the city of Gothenburg, the city of Trollhättan, the city of Borås, where we have the most hard-to-reach people. If you say, vulnerable in other ways, e.g. those who live in prostitution or homeless or addicts, we have also had our own traces, if you say, for them. Sahlgrenska Univeristy hospital has for example has worked in mobile teams as part of our group that has been out to cafes and shelters and various places and vaccinated. So there have been spot efforts and broad efforts parallel to each other.

The Swedish strategy for vaccination campaigns built, as most other measures, on voluntary choice and most of the campaigns focused on spreading information so that citizens could make an informed decision. This was also true for campaigns targeted to those living in immigration dense suburbs with low levels of vaccination.⁸⁴

In general crisis communication was tailored to specific groups, where low socio-economic status was seen as an important target group (in combination with limited Swedish language skills). More medically defined groups were also seen as risk groups, even if less effort were made to reach them using communication campaigns. This can of course be explained by the fact that chronically ill and other risk groups often have regular contact with health care and can be reached through these channels.

⁸³ <https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/folkhalsorapportering-statistik/statistikdatabaser-och-visualisering/vaccinationsstatistik/statistik-for-vaccination-mot-covid-19/uppfoljning-av-vaccination/vaccinationstackning-i-undergrupper/>

⁸⁴ <https://vgrfokus.se/2022/03/guiderna-i-nordost-pratar-vaccin-med-folk-pa-gatan/>

3.9 Spain

3.9.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

Spain is a decentralised country, which implies that different levels of government rule and manage specific areas of public policy and their own administration. The Spanish institutional design determines the relevance of both the national and the regional levels in policymaking, in contrast to the local level that has been poorly developed (Alba and Navarro 2003; Velasco Caballero 2020). At the national level, Spain is a parliamentary system where the role of central government leading the policymaking process is particularly relevant (Heywood 1995, 90). At the subnational level, Spain is organised into 17 Autonomous Communities and two Autonomous Cities (Ceuta and Melilla). The system tends to be symmetric, even if some communities have developed higher levels of decentralisation such as the Basque Country and Navarre (which enjoy a high degree of fiscal autonomy) (Aja and Colino 2014, 444). Following the same pattern of the national level, Spanish regions are parliamentary sub-political systems, whose governments are elected by their own regional parliaments. The relevance of regional governments in policymaking reproduce the pattern observed for the national arena: the governments, and not parliaments, lead the policymaking process (Aja and Colino 2014, 448).

Autonomous Communities are a key piece in the Spanish institutional structure. They manage more than the 33 per cent of the public revenue, and some the most relevant universal services of the Spanish welfare state, such as Health and Education. This exemplifies a complex governmental structure, where different levels of government manage specific competences and others have to be shared by the national and subnational administrations. Spanish regions have exclusive competences in areas as social services, agriculture, industry, tourism, or trading. Some areas, in contrast, are shared by the regions and state. In those competences, the usual consists in the state providing a basic regulation, and regions adapting it to the particularities their territories. This is the case for environment protection, economic policy, education, or health. In fact, the management of education (from compulsory education to university) and health (including both primary attention and hospitals) correspond to the Autonomous Communities, even if basic regulation is provided by the state. Finally, the central government has exclusive competence in some policy areas related to the national interest, which are most of the times a manifestation of statehood: defence, security, international relations... In spite of this distribution of competences, national regulations can mandate some spaces of co-decision, allowing Autonomous Communities to manage or regulate specific parts of national exclusive policy competences (for further information, see Aja and Colino (2014)).

This complex scenario where different governments rule and manage alone specific policy areas, and other policies are shared by the state and regions, needs the cooperation between them through intergovernmental coordination structures (Agranoff and Gallarín 1997). At the

parliamentary level, the Spanish Senate is supposed to be a key institution for this purpose. However, this function is poorly developed and has got many criticisms (Rodríguez López, Harguindéguy, and Sánchez 2019). To compensate the inefficacy of the Senate in coordinating both the national and regional arenas, other institutions have emerged (León and Ferrín Pereira 2011). The first one, mainly to arrange general political agreements, is the (a) Conference of Presidents; the other two address specific policy areas in a more specific perspective: (b) Sectorial Conferences, and (c) Bilateral Cooperation Conferences (see deliverable 4.1). These intergovernmental mechanisms diminish potential conflicts between regions and the state. However, when conflicts emerge, Spanish Constitution confers to the ordinary Courts and the Constitutional Court their resolution (Harguindéguy, Sola Rodríguez, and Cruz Díaz 2020). The Covid-19 has showed, as we will expose later on that improving coordination structures between regional and national arenas is needed to face a quick response to any crisis which requires different political levels. Territorial organisation of Spain has evolved practically, since many circumstances of regional governance were not included in the Constitution. This flexibility should be taken into account to improve the system by analysing what was successful and what was not during the crisis management. As a decision-maker stated:

“I believe that the system of co-governance with the autonomous communities. In a state like Spain, which has such important competences as health, managed by the autonomous communities, if there is a system of co-governance, which will surely have to be perfected and improved, it is undoubtedly a good practice” (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

The instrument to deal with the pandemic: the State of Alarm

The Spanish Constitution oversees the declaration of three kind of emergency regimes to face serious threats for Spanish society: alarm, exception, and war. The one planned for pandemics and health crisis is the State of Alarm, even if the Constitutional Court declared unconstitutional some restrictions of rights because they were found too strict. This regime allows to limit some fundamental rights and permits the creation of new structures of government to unify the coordination of decisions that, in normal circumstances, follow the distribution of competences foreseen by the Spanish Constitution (Gross 2011). The State of Alarm allows the central government to assume the direction of policy areas although regions keep on managing the services, providing new regulations that must be respected and observed by the regions, (Aba Catoira 2011; Vidal Prado and Delgado Ramos 2011). During the pandemic, three Decrees of State of Alarm were approved by the Government and ratified by the Spanish Parliament. Each one foresaw different measures in terms of right restrictions, but also in terms of economic and social responses to face the economic paralysation caused by them. This regulations are available in a public website, published by the Spanish Government, accessible in English: https://administracion.gob.es/pag_Home/en/atencionCiudadana/Crisis-sanitaria-COVID-19.html.

Spanish welfare system and its policies

Spain has a Southern European welfare system, which has a strong basis from the continental or corporative model that can be found in Germany, Austria, Belgium or France. However, regarding the health system, the Spanish one reproduces the National Health System model where the primary attention is the most important piece of the system and hospitals are less relevant. The Health System is managed by the Autonomous Communities. Coherently, mechanisms of wage replacement are linked to workers and companies' contributions to the National Social Security Institute: workers can receive funds in case they have contributed enough, this requirement is established, usually, in terms of years of employment. This had to be reformulated to respond the crisis caused by the spreading of the Covid-19.

3.9.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

As it well-known, the health crisis caused by the Covid-19 started becoming a visible problem in the first weeks of March 2020. During those days, both the hospital and primary care were unable to assist citizens that attended with respiratory problems, fever, and general disease according to normal quality standards. First in the Autonomous Community of Madrid, and then in Catalonia, the health system collapsed, and the Central Government declared the Emergency State.

The State of Alarm⁸⁵ was declared by the Spanish Government on 2020 March 14th, and validated by the Spanish Parliament each 15 days until its end on June 21st as Constitution requires⁸⁶. This emergency regime called for a limitation of constitutional rights, establishing a hard lockdown, suspending the attendance to education centres, and demanding home-office when it was possible, among other measures that will be described in section 3. Besides specific measures to limit mobility, the State of Alarm constituted a new coordination structure, the Single Authority (also labelled as Single Command) to lead and coordinate the responses to the Covid-19, assuming then the responsibility of dealing with the pandemic.

The Single Authority was led by the President of the Spanish Government, Pedro Sánchez. As a Single Authority, the President assumed the direction and coordination of the policies that had to be implemented to control the evolution of the pandemic and mitigate its consequences in different areas, particularly in the economic arena. The President delegated some of those coordination competences to four ministers: Salvador Illa, Minister of Health; Margarita Robles, Minister of Defence; Fernando Grande-Marlaska, Minister of Interior, and

⁸⁵ More information available here: <https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/covid-19/Paginas/estado-de-alarma.aspx#:~:text=El%20primer%20estado%20de%20alarma,provocada%20por%20el%20COVID%2D19.>

⁸⁶ Spanish Constitution states that the Spanish Government is the competent to declare the State of Alarm. However, this regime must be validated by the Spanish Parliament within the first 15 days from its declaration. Once validated, the Parliament can change the terms and conditions of the emergency regime, including its duration. In this occasion, the Parliament demanded the validation of the State of Alarm for several periods of 15 days. The parliament followed a different strategy with the State of Alarm decreed at October 2020 as we will discuss below.

José Luis Ábalos, Minister of Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda. Those ministries were identified as the managers of the most relevant policy areas to control the spreading of the Covid-19. In particular,

- the Ministry of Health supervised the decisions to mobilise resources to fight the coronavirus, both in terms of purchasing materials and following the evolution of infections, hospitalisations, and victims. The Minister of Health coordinated and supervised the regional health systems, even if Autonomous Communities kept on managing them.
- Both the Ministries of Interior and Defence coordinated the observance of the mobility restrictions by citizens. Military also helped to disinfect some critical spaces, such as elderly residences, food markets, train stations, or airports; and contributed to build field hospitals.
- Finally, the Ministry of Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda coordinated the normal functioning of transports, and the respect of the social distance in the interior of trains, planes, and buses⁸⁷.

The leaders of these ministries constituted the Single Authority, which met daily to analyse the evolution of the pandemic. Nonetheless, the Single Authority invited to the Director of the Coordination Centre of Health Emergencies, Fernando Simón, which acted as the spokesman of the government in technical aspects related to the evolution of the pandemic.

The creation of the Single Authority did not imply a change in competences distribution, but the concentration of decisions in a single structure, to coordinate the responses to fight the coronavirus. That is, the Autonomous Communities kept on managing their own policy areas, including the management of their health systems, but following general instructions from the Single Authority. To deal with possible conflicts between regional and national governments, the Single Authority resorted to the intergovernmental structures foreseen in the Spanish institutional design described before. In order to reach agreements between regional and national governments, the Conference of Presidents was called 14 times while the Alarm State was active. This is remarkable, taking into account that these conferences had been convoked six times in a period of almost 15 years.

There were several difficulties for the government to deal with the pandemic: (a) an unfavourable and polarised political environment; (b) a very different health crisis precedents; (c), and c) problems derived from a complex governance system. We will depict briefly those aspects.

⁸⁷ This section has been elaborated from the text of the Decree which declares the State of Alarm, and the information offered by the Spanish Government (see footnote 2).

Polarised and unstable political context

Spain is a polarised country, where the conflict between government and opposition is usually crowd and straightforward. To understand why, we are going to present the key facts of recent Spanish history for a better understanding (for further information, see Simón (2020, 2021)):

In January 2020 the social-democratic Socialist Party and United We Can, a radical left formation, conform a coalition government in minority. It is the first coalition government to be formed in Spain, at the national level, since the beginning of this democratic period. The Socialist Party and *Unidas Podemos* have their own agendas, styles and ideology, which sometimes generates tensions within the government that are shown without dissimulation in the parliament, in front the media and the public opinion. Parliament is very fragmented, we have 16 parties, an effective number of parties (at the parliamentary level) of 4,7. The opposition is made up of the right-wing bloc, which has been divided into three parliamentary groups: one more centrist (Citizens), the conservative PP and a radical right one, VOX; and a group of territorially based, regionalist or nationalist parties. The entry of the far right into Parliament has greatly polarized political life. A few days after the formation of the coalition government, the Covid-19 exploded.

The political landscape is not the most favourable for managing such a dramatic crisis as the one provoked by the Covid-19. The tension between the government and its investiture partners -separatist and regionalist parties- and the opposition is a constant in Spanish Politics. The Popular Party, the main opposition party, is competing with two others to maintain the leadership of the Spanish right wing, using a very tough opposition strategy in parliament against the government, trying to recover part of its space gained by VOX. The Catalan issue has added political tension and rarefied the general political context.

The State of Alarm is a mechanism that requires the approval, the ratification, of Spanish Parliament. Therefore, the Government needed the votes of many political parties to keep the measures against the Covid-19, and also the ones that found to protect vulnerable population economically affected by the pandemic. Government did not obtain the support to extend the first State of Alarm beyond June, as it was the government's intention. Some can be said regarding the National Budget. It had many difficulties to bring forward the 2020 budget, although the government finally succeed. In addition, some Autonomous Communities governed by the PP are using the management of the pandemic to make opposition against the central government, particularly the Autonomous Community of Madrid. The distribution of vaccines among the autonomous communities were the last area in which dissension and political battle between government and opposition have been shown. In this regard, a practitioner commented that:

“Madrid has been a case apart, I think that the autonomous communities have had good coordination and that the inter-territorial council has functioned as it had never functioned at any time since its creation after 2003, which is when it began to work well and at full capacity. It had never functioned in this way before and in fact, the first agreements were reached unanimously by the inter-territorial council, reached during... During this stage,

and this is something to highlight, isn't it? Apart from Madrid, which has been quite reactive, even to the point [that] I've been in meetings, like those of... well, I remembered, didn't I? With the evaluation, where the Madrid representative didn't even go to the meetings" (SPAIN WP4_DM_1).

Therefore, underlining that some political entrepreneurs used the pandemic to fight against the government, which resulted on a context of polarisation and decrease in Government decisions' political support. Other decision-maker related this situation as it can be seen:

"I don't think there was so much difference in the measures proposed by some administrations and others, but rather in this polarised political context there was a kind of search for advantage to try to accuse the other of doing something or to put on your medals for something you did, so I think that above all because of ineffectiveness. In other words, I go back to what I said before, stopping a country and activating it again is very complicated, but for us communication is fundamental, because in the end those who have to stop and activate themselves are 47 million Spaniards" (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

Different health crisis precedents

Precedents, which are usually considered useful in the field of public policy formulation, have been detrimental on this occasion:

- Neither the SARS-COV in 2002, nor the Avian Influenza in 2009, nor the Ebola crisis in 2014, affected the country significantly, abounding in the feeling of invulnerability, that these phenomena were something strange and improbable in our territory. The director of the Centre for Coordination of Alerts and Health Emergencies, said on January 31, 2020 that "... "Spain will not have, at most, more than one diagnosed case.... and it is expected that there will be no local transmission, and in that case, it would be very limited and very controlled". A few weeks later, a state of alarm was decreed.
- The avian flu made clear the risks of "over-preparing" for a health crisis, affecting the credibility of the WHO and calling into question, if not ridiculing, the government's anticipatory strategies and, even worse, casting doubt on its true intentions: to scare the population to justify a massive purchase of vaccines (more than 300 million euros were spent on vaccines). The government's initial hesitations and delays before COVID-19 probably have to do with this, with the need to act "prudently" so as not to make the same mistakes as the government of President Zapatero.
- The avian flu-Ebola crisis binomial added a third negative element, in addition to the feeling of invulnerability and detracting from the value of proactive strategies, these two crises opened the door to the use of health crises as a terrain for political struggle, for partisan confrontation: on both occasions, the opposition did not miss the opportunity to criticize the government in a furious manner, undermining the legitimacy of crisis response policies among citizens and generating a toxic political climate, which has been reproduced in the COVID-19 crisis. In short: invulnerability, politicization and procrastination are the legacy left by precedents.

This has been clearly repeated in the interviews, for instance, regarding the system of vigilance used to analyse the evolution of the data:

“The surveillance systems have improved a lot, but they have improved along the lines of what was planned to be done in the case of design, they have been able to be done in the space of a year, all these things have changed, but the truth is that much of what has been changed has been done to speed up things that were in our heads due to a lack of resources, or because the resources were spread over several years or because the processes required a process of several years with the previous staff, it has been possible to cut some things and make them a faster process, in terms of communication” (Spain_URJC_WP4_2_DM).

Problems derived from a complex system of governance

The National Health System in Spain is highly decentralized, even if it can be grouped within the National Health System kind of health regime. It is strong in primary care, but since primary care becomes a gatekeeper for attending hospitals, hospital care is less developed (Freeman and Rothgang 2010). The role of the state is minor in managing the Spanish Health System, since the system was decentralized since the eighties. The process of transferring healthcare competencies and resources to the Autonomous Communities began in 1981 and culminated in 2001. Since then, all health management has been in the hands of the regional governments, with the central government playing a coordinating and supervisory role in order to safeguard the value of equity in access to health services in the territory (Petmesidou and Guillén 2008).

The fundamental structure for the coordination of the system, as we have seen in the previous point, is the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System, the Sectorial Conference of Health, which was designed as a coordination body and not as an organization to manage health crises. In fact, as we have discussed before, there are conflict about the decision-making process within this Conference and that affect to its capacity to force regions to apply its agreements. This body, designed to meet, in plenary session, four times a year, has only met 82 times in 2020 for the management of the pandemic. There is a clear need for additional coordination structures to relieve the highest body for the governance of the national health system.

The cohesion of the national health system, after twenty years of operation through 17 semi-independent subsystems, is insufficient in several points, such as information exchange between the regional ministries and the Spanish ministry.

- The management of information in the pandemic has been one of the most visible weaknesses, having taken months to have a scorecard on the situation and the real evolution of the pandemic that could be used to make well-informed decisions. This issue has been one of the central points of discussion and political confrontation between the opposition and the government and between the territories and the

ministry. Information and trust are the glue that holds complex systems together and, especially in the first wave, they do not seem to be in abundance.

- The transfer of patients between Autonomous Communities has taken place, but in a testimonial way: in February 2021, the Ministry of Transport enabled several trains to transfer up to 60 patients between regions.

Another aspect to be resolved is the coordination between the public health system and the private health sector. During the first State of Alarm, the ministry regulated a kind of nationalization of the private system. When it changed the strategy of centralized management of the crisis for one of an intergovernmental nature -co-governance, in the language of the central government- it left this matter, also, in the hands of the communities. Some have signed collaboration agreements with the private sector and others have not. In general, a decision-maker describes it as it follows:

“Of course, afterwards we saw the cracks in how other actors understood how governance or co-governance should be in a decentralised State like Spain, and well, we all know how during these months there have been discrepancies between the different administrative levels, not so much in the decisions, but in terms of who had to take the decisions, whether they should be centralised or territorialised in the autonomous communities. I also believe that the evolution of governance was the result of the knowledge of how the virus itself worked, because it is difficult to go back to March 20, but when decisions began to be taken, it was not known how the virus was transmitted, whether it was transmitted through the surface, through the air, through the fluids, etc. In other words, it was not known how the virus was transmitted, In other words, they didn't know what it was like, so I think that this evolution also responds to the knowledge that, hey, decisions don't have to be general for an entire territory, but can be adapted according to the epidemiological situation of each region, and in some places they were even made by region. Difficulties? For example, even in defining the territorial unit in which it should be, the autonomous communities themselves often did not agree on the... I remember that in the de-escalation there were communities that decided to do it at a provincial level and others wanted it to be like Castilla-León, at a county level, often far removed from an overwhelming logic in terms of citizen awareness. For example, in the case of Madrid, the health areas, in other words, I was unable to find out what the health area was; so there is an extremely important point which is, in a crisis communication like this, that the information has to be clear and above all understood by those receiving it, and I believe that in many cases it was not (...). the system of governance was also built on the progressive knowledge and the relationship with the set of institutional actors who were facing the same difficulties as the central level of government when it came to developing their own decisions, because we were all, well, dragged a little by the health consequences, people's lives and in our own lives in the social system” (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

From May to June 2020, the spreading of the Covid-19 decreased, and the State of Alarm started reducing the intensity of some limitations. However, the structure of government went on being the same as declared in March. The Single Authority kept its function of coordination and supervision, being responsible for the decisions to relax restrictions. For the

first time in the health crisis, the restrictions and their flexibilization were applied considering the numbers of each region: levels of contagions and hospitalisations. Spanish government created a scenario of different phases according to which the limitations would decrease. Regional governments asked for the relaxation of restrictions, and the Single Authority (so, the national government) responded approving the proposal or rejecting it according to the available data. The measures went from allowing walks in specific hours, to permit mobility within Spanish provinces. Only when the State of Alarm ended, the main restrictions finished.

Until June 21st 2020, this structure of government characterised by the capacity of the national government to be responsible for the decisions to deal with the Covid-19 did not change. The end of the State of Alarm and the restoring of fundamental rights implied that regions recovered the fully control of their competences. Nonetheless, the Spanish parliament approved a law that fixed some limitations to assure social distance after the State of Alarm, in a period labelled as '*new normality*': reduction of capacity in shops, bars and restaurants, the mandatory use of masks, and some rules about physical distance inside buildings. The mobility between regions was also restored and the Spanish citizens could travel to visit friends and family and enjoy their holidays.

During this period, the spreading of the virus seemed to be under control. When some coronavirus outbreak appeared, the Autonomous Communities were responsible for applying regular legislation to avoid the virus expansion (specifically, the Organic Law 2/1986). When decisions consisted in limiting fundamental rights, the law on public health permits regional governments to restrict fundamental rights. To be effective, those measures must be validated by the courts (as the Law 29/1998 demands)⁸⁸.

In this phase of the pandemic, Spain went back to normal regarding governmental structures. However, the main change had to do with the active role of judges and courts to validate restrictions of rights when a virus outbreak exploded.

From the late August to September, the spreading of the Covid-19 started to increase faster. The decisions made by the Autonomous Communities to hinder the extension of the coronavirus started affecting the fundamental rights of the general population, and not only to specific groups of people or small towns. Therefore, their capacity to limit fundamental rights to general population was discussed and criticised by some judges and experts. Furthermore, some of those limitations needed to be coordinated between different regions and had to be controlled by the police, managed by the Ministry of Interior. In this context, during September and October, the Sectorial Conference of Health gained momentum as the main government structure to coordinate measures among administrations of both the regional and the national levels⁸⁹.

⁸⁸ Further information can be found in Alonso Timón (2021).

⁸⁹ This section has been built on different press documents as well as the two decrees that declared the State of Alarm for Madrid, and for the entire country in October 2020.

From September to October, the Sectorial Conference approved some measures that were considered mandatory for the Autonomous Communities, after agreeing a set of indicators to apply different restrictions. This strategy was not enough to control the pandemic. The regional governments needed to ask for validation to the courts, and sometimes judges declared as illegal some restrictions of rights. To restrict fundamental rights, argued some of them, the Spanish Constitution regulated three emergency regimes, and the State of Alarm should be the appropriate to make decisions to reduce mobility and impose a stricter social distance. Additionally, there were disagreements when interpreting the Sectorial Conference's rules of procedure. For most of the regions, a simple majority of regions could approve responses that had to be respected and observed by all of them. For some, those agreements could be mandatory for all of them, only if it was reached by consensus. The first option prevailed, but the region of Madrid appealed to the courts, which have not revised the matter yet.

In this context, to impose the decisions approved by the Sectorial Conference to the Autonomous Community of Madrid, the Spanish Government approved a new State of Alarm, specifically for this region. The goal was to prevent citizens' mobility from inside to outside and vice versa. This regime of emergency followed, in terms of governmental structure, the same parameters described above for the first State of Alarm declared in March for the entire Spanish territory: the authority designed to coordinate and adopt decisions in Madrid corresponded to the national government, although the region kept on managing its own competences, including the health system.

As the Covid-19 spread across Spanish regions, more voices demanded a new State of Alarm covering the entire Spanish territory. After some formal requirements by regional governments, a new State of Alarm was declared on 2020 October 25th. However, in this occasion, the strategy of the Spanish government to rule the pandemic was quite different. The new State of Alarm delegated the authority to each regional government, restricting their capacity of decision only in some points described in the text of the Decree of the State of Alarm (mainly related to some limits in restricting fundamental rights).

Therefore, in this emergency regime there was no Single Authority but as many Delegated Authorities as regions. The Autonomous Communities' governments assumed the competences of the Single Authority; although as a delegation, the Spanish Government kept the competence to recover the delegated authority if necessary. Therefore, it can be considered a quite open regulation that allowed Autonomous Communities to adopt more or less restrictive measures depending on their own situation. This measure pretended to reduce political conflict, since parties in regional governments that held different political sensibilities from the central government could adopt different measures to fight the pandemic.

The Sectorial Conference of Health became a key institution to coordinate regional policies and follow the evolution of the Covid-19. The own State of Alarm foresaw that this sectorial conference was the organism competent to clarify the interpretation of restrictions, create exceptions or impulse new measures, developing the limitations of this regime of emergency. The sectorial conference meets weekly, and their agreements are mandatory for both the

regions and the central government. First, because the Spanish ordinary law expressed the obligation to accomplish the agreements (even if the Courts must clarify this point); but also because the Decree of the State of Alarm establishes that this conference is competent to force regions to observe decisions when they are developing its content.

Other remarkable difference from the emergency regime declared in March, was the coordination between government and parliament. As we pointed out before, the State of Alarm must be validated by Parliament 15 days after its declaration by government. However, once validated, the Spanish parliament can approve an extension as long as they decide. It supposed a problem for Spanish government in March, since the support went down as they had to get the approval of the parliament. It favoured a context of increasing polarisation between government and opposition, in which criticisms focused on the State of Alarm as instrument and the restriction of freedoms to reduce mobility. In October, the state of alarm was validated once in the parliament, approving a duration of six months (until May 9th).

All along, a structure of government that underlined co-decision and shared responsibilities between the national and the regional governments and the duration of the state of alarm has served to reduce political conflict. Moreover, the Sectorial Conference of Health continued to be a key instrument to reach agreements among administrations, to adopt the relaxation of some measures in special days like Christmas (for instance); but also to plan the vaccination process that started in January 2021. This governmental structure characterised by delegation of the decision-making from the central government to the regional ones is expected to endure until May, when the State of Alarm should finish, unless the Spanish government requests a new prorogation to the parliament.

Regarding now policies related to the economic management of the pandemic, the Spanish government adopted a total of 326 measures to tackle the crisis since its beginning until 8 March 2021. In quantitative terms, the governmental response varies greatly from one area to another:

- The largest number of measures relates to government responses linked to social, economic and health consequences: areas 2 and 6 of the table, totalling 150 measures.
- The second block of responses relates to restrictions on mobility and confinement: areas 1, 3, 4 and 5 of the table, totalling 112 measures.
- There remains the category of "other types", which, as we shall see, are mostly related to adaptations of deadlines and administrative procedures to deal with the impossibility of citizens to meet their obligations to the public administration due to home confinement.
- Temporarily the regulatory effort is decreasing:
 - o The majority of responses (232 out of 325) occur during the first wave of the pandemic which includes three of the identified management periods: awareness of the problem, strict home confinement and planning for de-escalation in the face of a favourable evolution of the disease. The first wave has affected the country most severely.

- This was followed by the government responses (55 measures) included in the government's own so-called "New Normal Life" period, which lasted through the summer and saw the start of the second wave of the pandemic.
- Finally, there are the measures addressed in the current period of pandemic management (48 as of 8 March), that of soft containment, which includes territorial and other mobility restrictions, and which is expected to last until May 2021. The second and third waves of the pandemic have occurred during this period.

Economic measures constitute the most numerous package of governmental responses to the crisis and the one that extends more regularly throughout the different periods identified to describe the governmental policy of intervention on the consequences of the pandemic. Paying attention now not to specific vulnerable population, but the rest of the population, we have generated an overall view about how the Spanish political system answered to the vicissitudes that the disease triggers, gathering all the royal law decrees, orders and resolutions that the different representative institutions passed during the different stages of the crisis. Among all the packages in which we have divided the different measures adopted by the government, the economic block is the widest one due to the impact of COVID-19 in the national economy. All the restrictions adopted to reduce the infection rates among the population have doubtless impact in the general capacities to keep the economy levels even remotely close to what they were before the breakdown. Small business but also big enterprises, in every different non-essential sector, have the responsibility to adapt to the general needs and were bounded, first, to stop their usual economic rhythm; and second, to reduce their operation volume so as it would be compatible with the “new normal life.”

Six economic public policies were passed to adjust labour and working conditions. Three of them were passed during the hard confinement and the other three were adopted since October 2020. These policies were intended to assure that every company or worker who can carry out their activity telematically, following the requirements of the COVID-19 crisis public management. During the lockdown, the priority was to reduce mobility as much as it was possible, but services related to health care were marked as essential.

- Those workers needed mobility permissions and there were rules passed to grant they could carry out their duties in the safest conditions.
- Workers who were in contact with biological agents were provided with special equipment.
- Another important group of policies was the one related to protect those workers whose contracts expired during the period of the lockdown, assuming the continuity of them with public endorsement.
- Recoverable paid leaves were also legislated, giving the chance to workers to recover some loss hours. This package was orientated to shore up internal flexibility.
- The economic diagnosis revealed that it was crucial to extend all the instruments focused on workers to those women who carry out activities less susceptible to be

protected by law. The diagnosis underlined the difficulties that women suffer in order to access to these social benefits linked to salaried work. Minimum vital income was thought as an instrument to reduce the gender gap related to this unequal distribution of the social benefits and to achieve a new reality distinguished by an ideal of effective equality. Two specific gender policies were passed during the pandemic.

Once the economic goals were defined and the strategy was clear don't let fall the economic system -during the total paralysation of the economy- so as when the situation turns a bit more favourable the effort that companies and workers must do would be less intense. There was an urgent need to create instruments capable of generating the potential impact that was intended to ensure liquidity through different kind of credits, to protect employment, to extend debts payment terms and to extend social protection to those workers whose situation is critical. Thirty-seven economic instrument policies were adopted, concentrated mostly during the lockdown and during the preparation for the des escalation.

One of the most popular policies during the pandemic was the law passed by the government which authorized companies to organize and apply temporary regulation files (ERTE). This instrument allows companies to reduce costs while the economic activity was frozen in order to maximize their economic margins. It is a legal tool that suits perfectly with the situation so as the contracts could be modified to reduce the working hours. The reduction range could oscillate between 10% and 70%, and their use is limited to exceptional situations. They do not have any maximum or minimum terms, but the companies are who must manage the extensions. The affected worker by an ERTE is suspended and it has the right to perceive the 70% of his usual wage during the first sixth months, percentage that would reduce to 50% from the seventh month. Social Security institutions oversee managing terms and payments. Companies significantly reduce their labour cost during a lapse so they can continue, after the exceptional situation, with their activity avoiding being economically exhausted. Currently 805.000 workers are under the protection of this instrument. It has been estimated that by May the accumulated cost would be 40.000. € millions. According to our interviews, the ERTE programme has been the most successful instrument to replace wages for people whose labour activity was suspended by the authorities:

“The main one and the one that has occupied us the most, of course, is the framework of the specific ERTes for COVID. Well, it is a development of a regulatory framework that existed in the workers' statute and that had been developed by regulation after the 2012 reform, and what we have tried to do is that with that idea, with that skeleton, to develop it and add measures to it, which are not that they were....They were within our rights, but they were not so consolidated, so ambitious, and above all they had not been used so much, that is to say, they had not been put into practice, nor had they been so effective and to the satisfaction of companies, which has led to many adjustments that have had to be made” (Spain_WP4_4_DM).

Other interviewee, also decision-maker confirms this: “I do believe that the response that was taken, agile, rapid, at the time of decreeing the confinement, was fundamental; for

example, everything that the ERTes entailed, which in the end basically produced two effects, that the workers who could not work had an income and that the companies that could not have activity were kept afloat, and that therefore afterwards they could resume some activity with a certain degree of normality (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

Another popular instrument during the pandemic have been the ICO (Official Credit Institution) credits which are addressed to SMEs and self-employed workers, mostly. Banking sector conceded around 115.000. € millions. Most of these credits were conceded by State endorsements. They were intended to give margin and liquidity to business so as they do not waste all their resources which would lead to a critic situation. There have been passed many term extensions as the official economic previsions were landing. Fourth sections of 20.000 € millions each were approved.

Another kind of instruments were the ones related to postpone debts and social security quotes payments. This kind of tax instruments offer the possibility to fractionate payments. Following this line of policies that ensures the monetary liquidity during the pandemic, all those workers who are unemployed have the chance to request their unemployment benefits in advance.

Because of the barriers and difficulties depicted above, the response to the crisis to the pandemic in Spain folles three different strategies:

- **Single responsibility of the central government.** The first State of Alarm constituted a Single Authority that assumed the main decisions to deal with the Covid-19. Although Autonomous Communities kept on managing their own competences, they had to follow central government's indications. The central government, then, led the responses to the pandemic. The main coordination institution was the Conference of Presidents, which highlights the relevance of personal leaderships in leading the responses against the Covid-19.
- **Back to normal,** with relevance of judges and courts. Between June and October, the Autonomous Communities recovered the complete decision power in policymaking according to the Spanish Constitution's distribution of competences. However, when making restrictions of fundamental rights, regional governments needed the validation of those measures by judges and courts. The central government was clearly less salient during those months. In this structure, the Sectorial Conference of Health, whose agreements must be observed, increased its relevance.
- **Co-responsibility between central government and the regional ones.** The second State of Alarm declared for the entire Spanish territory did not restore the Single Authority. It regulated a new scenario where Autonomous Communities became Delegated Authorities, with fully competences to activate or disable restrictions of rights to reduce people's mobility within the frame approved by the Spanish parliament. The main intergovernmental structure of coordination was the Sectorial Conference of Health.

What about the local governments? They have had during the pandemic a minor role, according to the Spanish institutional design. Nevertheless, they have been important in two areas related to the control of restrictions. Spanish local governments have the competence to control the observance of some laws affected by the responses to the Covid-19. For instance, some have local police that have controlled the observance of the limitations of mobility. As well, they have contributed to control the

closeness of business and the accomplishment of the restrictions in the visitor-capacity of shops, restaurants, and other public spaces. Furthermore, big cities have also adapted their transports to guarantee social distance within trains and buses.

Reflections on pandemic management in Spain

Highlight issues or successes and talk about reflections based on the expert interview.

In general, officials interviewed do a positive trade-off regarding how the pandemic has been faced in Spain. However, it is precise to underline that all decision-makers have participated in the government, so this has to be taken into account. In general, they think that Spain responded quickly to the pandemic in spite of the complex context in which decision had to be made:

“Well, starting with the consequences, we can begin with the economic ones, which are the ones that I say are clearest, and here I do believe that the response that was taken, agile, rapid, at the time of decreeing the confinement, was fundamental (...) Well, I think that a crisis like this one, in which you have to be very agile and quick in your decisions, obviously the system of governance, as it was put in place with the State of Alarm, showed that it could respond as it has been to a crisis situation like this one” (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

3.9.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

The regulations and specific policies for vulnerable population were, in Spain, highly fragmented. Consequently, it is not easy to establish a specific characterisation of what vulnerable people meant for the Spanish authorities. In general, the different Decrees of Alarm identified as a vulnerable, sometimes because measures made to fight covid-19 spreading affected specially to vulnerable population or created other vulnerabilities:

- Minors under 14 years old.
- Elderly people, particularly who lived in residential homes or were disabled.
- People who needed housing assistance.
- People who were labelled as a consumer, since they had no access to food or other basic products or services of the daily life.
- Women that might be suffering gender or domestic violence who lives with the aggressor.

In general, vulnerabilities have not been in the main position of the agenda in Spain, so many of the measures implemented during the crisis of Covid-19 disappeared. One relevant policy that have kept on after the crisis is the minimum income programme. Spain is one of the few European countries (Martínez Torres 2004) that did not have a national income guarantee system that covers the general risk of poverty. However, regional governments did have minimum income guarantee programs in their respective territories (Ayala et al. 2016) with different institutional designs, target populations, degrees of coverage, amount, duration and requirements for access to them. Inequality in Spain is higher than the European average, the previous crisis aggravated the situation and the improvement in the economic situation since 2013 has failed to reduce this inequality substantially. According to the VIII Foessa Report⁹⁰, in 2019, 18.4 percent of the population in Spain is in social exclusion. That is eight and a half million people, one million two hundred thousand more than in 2007. In 2019, the National

⁹⁰ See <https://www.foessa.es/viii-informe/>

Strategy to Prevent and Combat Poverty and Social Exclusion 2019-2023⁹¹ was approved (Ministry of Health, Consumer Affairs and Social Welfare, March 22, 2019), which provides for the implementation of a Minimum Living Income to address poverty and income inequality.

As noted in Royal Decree-Law 20/2020 establishing the Minimum Vital Income, the COVID-19 health crisis and the state of alarm decreed on March 14 have accelerated the need to implement this income guarantee policy. The paralysis of economic activity in many sectors and the decline of economic activity in the economy as a whole has negatively affected household income, especially among the most vulnerable: informal workers, part-time, with temporary contracts, with wages below the minimum wage, often linked to sectors such as construction, hospitality, retail, domestic work, immigrant workers, single-parent households, etc.

To these profiles, the pandemic crisis has added others: households whose main income earner is a self-employed worker, family micro-enterprises (bars, small restaurants, local stores) that maintained a precarious balance between income and expenses, with no savings to face the crisis, who have been forced to ask for social assistance because they are unable to meet the current expenses of housing, maintenance of household members, etc. Attention to these groups has been led by regional and local governments through regional income guarantee programs and municipal social services. For example, the Madrid City Council established in April 2020, a program of economic and emergency aid, aimed at alleviating the liquidity crisis of the most vulnerable households, and also the distribution of a bank card to buy food⁹², which is recharged monthly, to respond to the exponential increase in demand for food in the first months of the pandemic (Spanish Federation of Food Banks).

Design of the Minimum Vital Income:

- Non-contributory Social Security benefit.
- Legal residence in Spain
- Covers the difference between the sum of the economic resources of the person/unit of cohabitation and the amount of guaranteed income for different cases.
- The duration of the assistance lasts as long as the situation of economic vulnerability persists and the requirements that gave rise to the right to receive it are maintained.
- It is compatible with earned income.
- It is compatible with the income guarantee programs of the autonomous communities.
- The amount is variable: for 2020 the guaranteed income in the case of an individual is 5,538 euros. This amount increases according to the size and structure in the case of cohabitation units,
- It is linked to job search and social inclusion programs.
- It establishes groups of special protection: victims of gender violence, people who have to leave their home due to the dissolution of the couple, evicted people. Single-parent households.

⁹¹ See https://eapn.es/ARCHIVO/documentos/noticias/1553262965_estrategia_prev_y_lucha_pobreza_2019-23.pdf

⁹² See <https://www.madrid.es/portales/munimadrid/es/Inicio/El-Ayuntamiento/Informacion-y-medidas-especiales-durante-el-tiempo-del-Coronavirus/Disposiciones-municipales/Disposiciones-del-Area-de-Gobierno-de-Familia-Igualdad-y-Bienestar-Social/?vgnnextfmt=default&vgnnextchannel=120b81d7c58e0710VgnVCM2000001f4a900aRCRD>

The implementation of this measure got off to a difficult start. The government's plan was to intervene on households in severe poverty, 2.5 million people in 850,000 households. However, the coverage reached in February 2021 is 160,000 households, barely 19 percent. The minimum living income was launched in a rushed manner, resulting in an avalanche of hundreds of thousands of applications that overwhelmed the Security's management capacities, in addition to being resolved through a highly complex procedure. The government, through the Minister of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration, has acknowledged to the media that the design needs to be reformed, the reasons why two out of every three applications submitted are rejected, and the management systems need to be improved if the initial objective is to be achieved⁹³.

On February 2, 2021, (Royal Decree-Law 3/2021), some of the conditions that made it difficult for households to access the minimum living income despite being in a situation of need were eliminated and, given the difficulty for potential users to manage the process, the figure of minimum living income mediating entities was created, which will be in charge of preparing the reports and documents required to justify the right to the benefit.

As stated before, Spain has a complex system of competence attribution, so local entities, Autonomous Communities and the national government have competences to fight vulnerabilities. This changed reproducing the general pattern discussed in section 5. In general, decision-makers are aware that vulnerable population should have had more attention. They usually justify this because of the urgency in which measures had to be approved, and also that health related vulnerabilities and economic related vulnerabilities were completely different:

“Yes, there were measures. For example, I remember everything that had to do with homeless people, people who usually live on what others give them, and if there is no one on the street, explain to me who gives them... And yes, measures were put in place, both by the army and at the social level, in collaboration with the communities, they were put in place. Also everything that had to do with gender violence, that is, let's think about locking up a person in a situation of gender violence and leaving the victim and the aggressor locked up for days and days at home, in other words, it can be a real hell. And there was a detection, as I was saying, within the country to stop, to say "okay, and now how this affects certain vulnerable groups on which ordinary public policies focus and that obviously now we have to see how this situation we are experiencing impacts” (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

“I also feel that I experienced the first stages in terms of the definition of vulnerability in February, March, January, February, March of (inaudible), it was mainly age. But it is true that seen in perspective I believe that there are certain groups such as transplant recipients, groups with disabilities, and later on, family groups that are related to them could have perhaps been prioritised, determined as a vulnerable population, that given that an initial generational criterion was established, they were not included, later on they were, and now this has been established” (Spain_URJC_WP4_3_DM).

“Older people, people with pathologies, people with tumour diseases and so on. Which, well, that's fine, but even the ministry itself in its organisation of the vaccination campaign, it organised several

⁹³ See: https://www.eldiario.es/economia/escriva-adelanta-cambios-ingreso-minimo-vital-contrario-no-llegara-lejos-objetivo-850-000-familias_1_6478441.html

levels and it also included "socio-economic vulnerability", people with socio-economic vulnerability. But then this has not been transferred, this decision matrix was there, and then it has been left out of the practicalities of who we are going to vaccinate, right? For example, people who have difficulty accessing the health system or people who have more difficulty due to their work activity to be able to carry out an isolation, a quarantine, people who work are more easily able to carry out a quarantine, "no, look, I have been in contact" because I am quarantined, because I work from home and I can continue with my life and they will not throw me out of work, however, a person who is also in a job that has been very face-to-face, is more likely to have been in contact and is less able to carry out a quarantine because they can be thrown out of work. And this has not been taken into account as much in vaccination programmes" (Spain_URJC_WP4_1_DM).

Decision-makers are aware that decide implies prioritise policies, and health issues became more salient that the economic or social ones in terms of vulnerability.

3.10 Wales

3.10.1 Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on TO general population)

Wales is a devolved nation within the United Kingdom since 1998. Devolution granted the National Assembly for Wales the power to decide how the Westminster government's budget for Wales is spent and administered. In 2006, the National Assembly for Wales was given legislative powers, resulting in the creation of a Welsh Parliament and a Welsh Assembly Government, comprising of a Prime Minister for Wales (currently Mark Drakeford), Welsh ministers and deputy ministers. From May 2020 onward the National Assembly for Wales is called the Welsh Parliament in English and Senedd Cymru in Welsh.

Wales has its own National Health Service (NHS Wales). NHS Wales now delivers services through seven Local Health Boards and three NHS Trusts in Wales. The seven Local Health Boards (LHBs) in Wales now plan, secure and deliver healthcare services in their areas. The 3 NHS Trusts operate in Wales alongside the Local Health Boards are the Welsh Ambulance Services Trust, Velindre NHS Trust, and Public Health Wales (PHW)

In the UK, COBR (Cabinet Office Briefing Rooms) meetings started on January 24, 2020, and although the participants of these meetings are not made public, they comprise of key ministers and officials. COBR is a 'crisis management facility [...] activated in events of national significance' (Kapucu, 2009); it is an important component of crisis management as authorities come together to identify appropriate responses to a crisis (ibid.). The UK-wide Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE) is led by the government chief scientific adviser (GCSA), Sir Patrick Vallance, and the chief medical officer (CMO), Chris Whitty. SAGE is an ad hoc committee that brings together government scientists and officials with external experts.

In March 2020, COBR was the main forum for decision making in relation to COVID in the UK and included the devolved nations in these meetings from early March (Haddon and Ittoo, 2020). SAGE meetings were also held during that time and served to inform and advise all devolved nations. While SAGE meetings provide scientific advice to guide policy and regulations, in practice, authorities agree on the best approach to handle the pandemic during COBR meetings. SAGE meetings therefore inform decisions taken during COBR meetings⁹⁴ and between January 22, 2020 and February 25, 2021, SAGE held 82 meetings⁹⁵.

The Wales Resilience Forum is the highest authority for crisis management and emergency planning in Wales and works in cooperation with local resilience forums and other agencies. Wales as a devolved nation follows advice from their Chief Medical Officer (Frank Atherton in Wales) and Chief Scientific Adviser (Rob Orford in Wales). The Chief Medical Officer works

⁹⁴https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/900432/sage-explainer-5-may-2020.pdf

⁹⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/scientific-evidence-supporting-the-government-response-to-coronavirus-covid-19>

with the Welsh Government on policy for public health⁹⁶, and the Chief Scientific Adviser advises the Welsh Government on matters related to health science⁹⁷.

On March 18, 2020, Wales initiated its own health protection regulations. In Wales, the Coronavirus Restrictions were approved by the Welsh Parliament on March 25th, giving Wales the power to manage the pandemic independently of the other British nations. The Welsh Government is comprised of several departments, with Public Health Wales that manages health emergencies. Emergency planning in Wales is consistent with the United Kingdom's Civil Contingencies Act 2004, but it includes the Welsh Government's involvement and the participation of operating organisations unique to Wales.

As addition to the UK-wide SAGE group, Wales created a Technical Advisory Cell (TAC) and a Technical Advisory Group (TAG) to support SAGE in advising the Welsh Government and Public Health Wales⁹⁸. TAG – SAGE experts, alongside the Chief Scientific Adviser for Health Rob Orford met three times a week to discuss the progress of the pandemic. TAG-SAGE experts inform the ministers, which in turn present changes to the regulations to the Welsh Cabinet for consideration. The Cabinet makes the final decision which is communicated to the ministers.

The Welsh pre-pandemic preparedness strategy is aligned to the overarching UK-wide strategy. The main Welsh document that resembles a pandemic response plan or strategy is the *Wales Framework for Managing Infectious Disease Emergencies 2005*. It “sets out national arrangements for managing major infectious disease emergencies, including national co-ordination, operational responsibilities of NHS organisations and the role of partner agencies” (Welsh Assembly Government 2007: 3). Wales also has a more pandemic-specific response plan; the 2007 *Pandemic Influenza Guidance Planning* was established before the 2009 influenza pandemic. For emergencies in general, Wales has the *Pan-Wales Response Plan*, that entails the “command, control and co-ordination urgent response structure for national emergencies and includes activation levels and multi-agency responsibilities” (Welsh Government, 2021: p2).

3.10.2 Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

Prior to the pandemic Wales had a different approach to the implementation of law than England, which allowed more different kinds of measures to be imposed in Wales, whereas they were absent in England. Therefore, interviewed MP1⁹⁹ who represents a Swansea City Region constituency reminds us that:

“In Wales, you can actually use force of law. And then in terms of traveling around – as mentioned earlier – in Wales, they said, you can only – the advice, that strong guidance, ‘you should only be traveling as far as five kilometres’, but in England, it was like unlimited. So, there were spectacles of Bournemouth, that’s 10,000 people, averaging. ‘How could I

⁹⁶ <https://gov.wales/dr-frank-atherton>

⁹⁷ <https://gov.wales/dr-rob-orford>

⁹⁸ <https://gov.wales/technical-advisory-cell/terms-reference>

⁹⁹ MP = Member of Parliament; they represent their local constituency before the UK Government in the House of Commons

know that everyone was going to turn up on a very sunny day in Bournemouth?’. So thanks to devolution, we’re able to have a more cautious approach.”

He argues in favour of the multiple ways in which the Welsh government could respond to the pandemic and that this level of governmental freedom has been helpful in keeping numbers down in comparison to England; in particular in the first year when Wales made use of more protective measures than England. In addition to the 5-mile rule that was in place in Wales during the first wave (stretching further in remote places where shops, GP surgeries, and pharmacies are sparse).

Wales differs from England on socio-political and economic terms as well, which merited a different approach to the pandemic, as interviewed MP2 explains:

“What’s interesting about Wales compared to England, is that the demography of Wales is essentially – you look at the numbers – of an older, sicker, poorer population. And so therefore, other things being equal, you just thought that the death rate would be higher. But the last rates I heard – and you do need to confirm and check these rates – were that the death rates over the five-year average in Wales was 13%, over the five-year average, and in England, it was 20% over. And that is a sort of testimony to the more cautious approach Wales took and specifically, we’re talking about years, the legislation for two-meter social distancing as opposed to the guidance of one-meter social distancing.”

The MP’s statement thus suggests how the Welsh Government took population-level statistics into account about how to adopt the pandemic mitigation recommendations from the WHO.

Additionally, Wales had the ‘firebreak’ lockdown in Autumn 2020. This lockdown was announced shortly before it began on 6pm on Friday 23 October and had a planned end date on Monday 9 November, which differentiated from other lockdowns in as not being open-ended, avoid a surge in infections with the Kent variant, and was shorter than other lockdowns¹⁰⁰. No other devolved countries employed this form of lockdown at any time during the pandemic, and it was criticised heavily by the UK government and in the UK media as well. MP1 explains:

“Boris Johnson obviously likes to be popular and had previously proclaimed that he wanted to push forward with herd immunity. And the strategy – as you remember – was to infect as many people as possible in order to give them immunity, which was assumed that they get immunity from this particular virus. As it goes like flu, the variants are changing, subject to the NHS not being overwhelmed. So what was happening is, is that allow that virus to grow and come back all the time, and keep the NHS a nearly breaking point, that was the UK strategy, which obviously is farcical.”

The firebreak lockdown went against the ideology that underpinned the policy approach from the UK, and reflects Wales’ more cautious approach, heeding public health preventative principles more strongly than the UK government.

Regarding change of COVID responses, Wales only ever did one Firebreak lockdown, however, as did it only implement the 5-mile rule once. With the expansion of vaccine uptake in Wales, the Welsh government more or less stopped implementing unique measures, and more regularly replicated the

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.gov.wales/national-coronavirus-fire-break-to-be-introduced-in-wales-on-friday>

UK-wide policies, albeit often for longer periods, for instance, mask-wearing in public transport and testing commercially after having come back to Wales from international travel.

Later in the pandemic response phase that entailed protective measures requiring the general public to comply with, the cautious approach Wales had taken became more difficult to uphold. A national politician from an opposition party remarked that the Welsh government was scrutinised heavily for maintaining the pandemic measures that were considered for abandonment in England. He recalled a moment that this approach was not necessarily offered to the public in genuine sense:

“[Government official] would look at the graph [displaying infection and hospital rates over a period] and was like; ‘see, things are as bad as we predicted’ And I went, ‘No, that’s not what that graph says’. And I was right. We were we were coming out of the Omicron wave quicker than government was telling us. We were, and they were they were playing the ‘let’s keep on scaring the public’-hand a little bit too hard on that occasion.”

As a result, in the spring of 2022, Wales changed its set of regulations from relatively strict in the UK context to none at all over a short time. This was mainly due to the combination of hitting a mark on vaccination degree of the Welsh population or number of doses administered, the Omicron variant emerging as less likely fatal after infection than earlier variants, and the likelihood of better weather¹⁰¹.

Much can be said about the ways in which the public in Wales reacted to the crisis management and its changes in the regulations. The public in Wales seemed to adhere well to the requirements the Welsh government implemented. MP2, who also represents a Swansea City Region constituency, argues that this can be explained by the social histories of the mining and steelwork industries and their enforced closure in the 1980’s. He noticed the difference particularly evidently when crossing the border between England and Wales in January 2022:

“But yesterday, coming back from London, I had a mask on, and nobody had a mask on. And then they did say something over the tannoid like ‘wear a mask’ and a couple of people started wearing a mask. And when you got into Wales more people were wearing masks. So it’s just a matter of telling people what to do and policing it and providing social pressures.”

Nonetheless, MP1 remarks that arguments against restrictive pandemic measures entailed the supposed encroachment of the human rights of the individual. Both MP1 and MP2 are wary of this line of argument for its easy applicability to a wide variety of situations. Both mention the proposals for COVID passes and check at the door of hospitality establishments (e.g. pubs and restaurants) being shot down for being pitted against the right of individuals not to get vaccinated or not to show medical information to be allowed access to a place:

“The discussion on human rights has been so hijacked (...) And, to a certain extent, this is imported from the far right in the United States. And it appears to be done in a sort of random way, but it’s being done in this systematic way to undermine things. (...) One way of course of undermining human rights is claiming that you’ve got human rights. We don’t have them, in particular – “my right to go to the pub, without a mask without a vaccine.

¹⁰¹ <https://www.gov.wales/coronavirus-regulations-to-end-in-wales>

*I've got this right. It doesn't matter about your health. I don't believe you've got that right.”
(South-Wales MP1)*

Members of the public in Wales who do not want to comply with the regulations seem to use the arguments for state-based rights for protection against the virus that are underpinned by *collective* notions for arguments for rights based on *individualised* notions of protection. The latter seems misplaced in the eyes of this interviewee and others; also, because prioritising the rights of the individual over the collective sets a precedent for normalising the individualisation of the pandemic response.

Other changes in the crisis response included new ways to pre-empt different virus variants and vaccine hesitancy to consider where and how vaccine fatigue would occur and in what kind of communities. A senior policymaker explained the following:

“So we have the UK health security agency that tracks global trends. (...) So they may look at variants circulating in some of the countries with surveillance mechanisms. Obviously, you'd be sure of countries with advanced surveillance systems. So looking at what was coming over the hill, in terms of variants is really important. I think another thing is social insight work with your populations back home. So that you know that perhaps this vaccine fatigue or perhaps, you know, the antivaxx movement is affecting certain parts of the population more than others. You might find that, you know, parents are actually put off from it. If a parent has become very anti in their stance to vaccination themselves. And, you know, we do see it sometimes with certain groups of people. So certain groups of people who are more anti-establishment. So they made to say that perfectly great educational system, the Steiner Schools, very creative, very artistic, very led by the child. (...) So, mistrust of government and systems and poor experience, maybe as well. And then, you know, you will find that, you know, some communities will have much lower levels of uptake. (...) And they tend to be intelligent people, you know, so they've read a lot, but they can read a lot of misinformation as well. And so what we're worried about as well is whether an anti-vaccine sentiment would spill over into people denying their baby say, diphtheria, tetanus, polio injections.”

Whilst the senior pandemic policymaker did say that they looked for new variants, the advice did not necessarily change; accordingly, the 2-meter distance remained at the same reach, even though the Delta variant was clearly more infectious, which would perhaps have warranted 3 meters distance. At the time of the interview, Omicron had not yet emerged. Also, remarkable from the quotation is the concern that this intelligent parent group that did not want the vaccine would also change their mind about other infectious diseases. Elsewhere in the interview she mentions measles having returned to Wales, likely because of these parent groups. As such, they “kept tabs” on these groups to address them specifically if a group was found to underperform in the stats.

Furthermore, addressing the many unknowns and uncertainties required an ethical view on the situation. A retired top policymaker explained how the different viewpoints of the different ideologies, moral frameworks, and cultural backgrounds that typify Wales were brought together in an ethics panel. She explains the origin and reasons for this governmental ethics advisory panel:

“So there wasn't the evidence, the evidence developed, and as it as it came forward, you're able to make better and better clinical decisions. (...) So lots of the clinical stuff got

thrashed out by the Chief Medical Officers, either in their discrete group, because they would then advise the Health Ministers directly or in this collaborative group that I was involved in. And then, you know, it would be cascaded within the country. But in Wales, we had some particular concerns about how come more Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic workers were dying? And should we be doing something to protect them, and often, people from that background in society are in lower paid jobs which have higher contact. We were concerned about Do Not Resuscitate orders. (...) So the Minister agreed that we set up a particular panel, it was chaired by one of the doctors within the Welsh Government. And they pulled in experts from outside, so that there was a proper debate. I did not sit on that committee, I've merely sort of was asked questions to feed into it. (...) So you actually had a group of people you could go to, with ethical and moral dilemmas and issues. And it was from their group, that they developed a tool to actually help with the safety of workers. So the evidence, which was showing that if you had certain factors, so if you came from a Black or Asian background, you were overweight, you were male, you're an older age, you had heart disease or something, you can rank it and put a scoring on a chart, and it said, if you got to a certain level, you should not be having close contact with people with COVID, you should actually be moved to a different type of working environment."

The tool this top advisor speaks of was a calculation of a combination of the characteristics of people's bodies (age, disease presence, etc) and their job (working with others present, possibility to keep a distance from others, possibility to work from home, etc). It had thresholds that related to the need to protect workers. As such, this ethical advisory panel was successful in bringing in new connections between the population and clinical information that could be used to differentiate the pandemic responses for different social groups in Welsh society.

3.10.3 Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

Vulnerability seemed to be a straightforward categorical concept to determine the differential likelihood of infected people to suffer more severe illness and have a higher chance to be hospitalised or die than the average person. The principles that determined what was understood and operationalised as vulnerability that ended up in the pandemic response policy documents reflect this apparent simplicity. However, the reasoning behind these principles seem to be much more nuanced and intricate as appears from the interviews. An important decision maker on healthcare policy in the Welsh government explained how the pandemic changed the way policies were made to address people differently:

"We think of people and then we think pathways don't really think oh, yeah, the cardiovascular groups, and then diabetic people. And we don't really stratify people in other groups. But I think in the pandemic, we started to stratify people for vulnerability, what were their social vulnerabilities? What were their mental health vulnerabilities? What were the physical vulnerabilities? And, and the policy started to be developed in that manner, which was the first time I've seen that sort of emergence of thinking, which is quite a maturation in a system, which I think what I assumed was mature in the sort of national scale thinking before, this was a different type of idea. And what it showed us in the population is that those with social deprivation, those that have the social determinants, that impact with social terms are not as positive and will impact health,

people have far more vulnerabilities and those vulnerabilities are not one, they will come in a mass.”

Clearly, the concept of vulnerability in the way she explained it to be used to guide pandemic responses rooted in biomedical categorisations. However, she argued that different forms of vulnerability, including social vulnerability, became rapidly part of the governmental debates on how to keep the infection, illness, hospital bed occupation, and death rates down. This focus was corroborated by another senior policymaker in the Welsh pandemic response. She explained that she was recruited into the Welsh Government for her specialism in equality matters:

“So inequalities was, was something that I was very interested in. Within three months of being in Welsh Government, the pandemic had been announced. (...) The anxiety at the end of December (2019) and by January (2020), we're in it. So I was put fulltime onto supporting the response for the initial wave. (...) In the sort of May-June (2020) time, I felt that, you know, we really needed now to have somebody an advance party, if you like, looking at the vaccinations, making links with foreign nations partners here in the UK. And so I went fully over to the vaccination program in July (2020). (...) And then we basically got together and established a program board with all of the health boards on it. And with a stakeholder group with many of the third sector partners on it, representing groups that would be interested in the vaccinations. And also a kind of the lens of the third sector for homelessness, asylum seekers and refugees, people whose mother tongue was not English, people who had a learning disability, or any disability. So it was a very broad ranging stakeholder group.”

Her experience remarks on the early active engagements with different marginalised people in Welsh society who were considered vulnerable in the context of the pandemic. A return to social group based thinking around vulnerability does come through in the equity efforts in the vaccination strategy development, which is potentially unavoidable in a representative democracy, such as Wales. Such efforts revolve around the experience in healthcare provision that certain social groups are not addressed in ways that encourage them to take up vaccines, which requires the development of a vaccination strategy that addresses *all* rather than the dominant social groups efficiently. Examples of such efforts in Wales include information in multiple languages, spoken information on websites, discrete vaccination booths with female staff, and vaccines being offered and administered at the place of work for sex workers in the evening. With time passing, the development of the vaccination equity strategy changed with more social groups being added that had particular issues in accessing the vaccine.

How the measures created new vulnerable groups was monitored via statistics and representative of certain occupations and unions that raised alarms with the Welsh government. A senior pandemic policy advisor gave an example of a new vulnerable group that they addressed with their vaccination strategy:

“And the other thing is using community voices, if you have somebody who has died of COVID, you know, amongst the taxi drivers in Merthyr Tydfil, as they did, that you use the other taxi drivers to spread the word through their work colleagues, that the vaccine is safe is effective, you know, because many people were not respecting wearing masks in cars, or these people need to make a living; they can't insist too much, because people will

say, 'don't bother, and I'll get the next one, I'll get the next taxi', they're a bit more understanding. People who are drunk might not be taking the best precautions, they may have gone out, even though they're feeling unwell, because it was a party or whatever, they're young; it's not really going to affect them badly. But we did lose taxi drivers in Merthyr Tydfil. And we had representations from the Transport Workers Union; 'could we prioritize them as an occupational group?', but we couldn't prioritize the police or the fire people or anybody, because the age parameter for prioritization had been decided nationally. And that was what we had to stick to."

She argues that it was impossible to prioritise occupational groups as they were bound to UK-level regulations set by the Joint Committee on Vaccination and Immunization. Therefore, it seemed like the more cautious approach in Wales that sought to further differentiate its responses amongst particularly vulnerable social groups could not be delivered in the way the Welsh Government wanted to.

Key Findings

Several lessons can be learnt from the main findings in the previous sections. Firstly, the way the Welsh pandemic response defined vulnerability and was organised around addressing the needs of vulnerable people may have set it up for failure. Employing vulnerability as characteristic of a group of people on the grounds of shared biological potential for the virus to wreak havoc on is problematic without committing to intervene in *all* social processes that could lead to infection. Following from the interviews, MP1 notes how the caution principles were unlikely to work adequately in the government's attempts to separate vulnerable people from the virus:

"And again, in the case of children, as I'm talking out of line here, but from the start, it was like 'we haven't got concrete evidence on this'. And they don't take the precautionary principle which is rather dull. It was very self-evident that obviously if you get all the children to school, they're going to be back to the transmitters. And they're going to go home to grandma or whatever and kiss her. Pretty obvious stuff really"

The lesson from this could entail that treating social groups as bodies with particular characteristics (e.g. age, sex, clinical conditions) decontextualises them and likely left gaps in the pandemic response. In effect, such a focus loses sight of the social processes in which these people are embedded. Therefore, pandemic measures that had a stronger focus on social processes, for instance households mingling over religious celebrations (e.g. Christmas or Eid) complementing body-based rules would have addressed the spread of the virus more thoroughly.

Secondly, whilst the protective pandemic measures that restricted people's possibilities of contact with others were not particularly differentiated between different social groups aside from shielders and non-shielders, other aspects of the pandemic response; in particular the Welsh vaccination programme did. It seems that offering people something new or encourage them to adopt the COVID-19 vaccines as something new in their lives requires the vaccine to be specifically tailored to people's lives. Measures that take away from people's lives, such as testing to travel by boat or plane, picking up one's children in a specific timeslot at the local primary school, or restricted access and freedom of movement in supermarkets more strongly reflect the requirements of the institutions, organisations, and businesses involved. Indeed, these restrictions are much less adapted to social difference and do not reflect people's lives. Fostering a higher level of compliance and a less distressing pandemic

experience could have been achieved by explanations and regulations that fits better around people's lives.

Thirdly, a lesson learnt from the arguments presented by people who resisted the pandemic regulations is to take care of the potential for the measures to sound unreasonable from the perspective of individual human rights. Providing explanations for these measures that ensure no human rights are harmed could have accompanied these measures. In addition, powerful explanations of the benefit to human collectives at different scales could have accompanied the measures.

4. Analysis

The following findings section presents the basis for the analysis of the COVID-19 crisis management from the perspective of WP4: government response. This overall aim will be to critically and holistically reflect upon all data collected in the context of WP4 and summarise the main findings. These country reports will be explored in further detail in the D4.8 deliverable to answer the overarching research questions in a cross-country analysis and synthesis.

Below are the five dimensions covered in the D4.7 report. Each of the dimensions were taken into consideration when devising the D4.7 guideline questions, and throughout this report, there will be a presentation of commonalities across all the COVINFORM countries under study. The dimensions are as follows:

- 1) Pandemic planning and preparedness;
- 2) Governmental approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability;
- 3) COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance;
- 4) Economic and social welfare responses to COVID-19;
- 5) Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and response;

Pandemic planning and preparedness

All the COVINFORM target countries are welfare states, meaning the governments of each country play a crucial role in safeguarding and promoting its citizens' economic and social welfare. All countries had relevant pandemic-related documents to deal with pandemics and crisis pre-COVID. The documents that existed across all the COVINFORM countries can be categorised as follows:

Plans

Germany had the 2017 National Pandemic Plan, a successor to an earlier pandemic plan launched in 2005, which was modified in part to integrate lessons learned during the 2009 influenza (H1N1) pandemic (RKI, 2017, pp. 5–6). **Portugal** had the National Emergency Plan (released in 2009, updated in 2015 by the Portuguese Civil Protection Authority). As for **Wales**, and emergencies in general, the country has the Pan-Wales Response Plan, that entails the “command, control and co-ordination urgent response structure for national emergencies and includes activation levels and multi-agency responsibilities” (Welsh Government, 2021: p2). In **Greece**, pre-existing strategies and policies which related to influenza cases were in place prior to the pandemic (Ministry of Health, 2020). Such strategies and policies include the National Pandemic Action Plan.¹⁰² In **Sweden**, and in 2005 in particular, the National Board of Health and Welfare (NBHW) was commissioned by the Government to produce a national pandemic plan that included plans for national interventions. The pandemic plan was revised again in 2019.

Many countries had an influenza plan pre-COVID-19, specifically Austria, Germany, Portugal, Italy, England, Wales, and Greece. The details are as follows:

- **Austria** – Influenza Pandemic Plan ([Influenza Pandemieplan – Strategie für Österreich](#)), which includes a strategy for the country to cope with the Influenza virus. The document was

¹⁰² <https://extranet.who.int/sph/influenza-plan-greece>

published in 2006 by the former Federal Ministry for Women and Health and is still in use today.

- **Germany** – The 2007 German Influenza Pandemic Preparedness Plan.¹⁰³
- **Italy** – the “[Piano nazionale di preparazione e risposta a una pandemia influenzale](#)” (National influenza pandemic preparedness and response plan) was drawn up according to the 2005 WHO guidelines, updated and it replaced the previous Italian Multiphase Plan for and Influenza Pandemic, published in 2002.
- **Portugal** – [National Plan for Pandemic Influenza](#): The Directorate-General of Health (DGS) released the plan in 2007 and revised it in 2014.
- **United Kingdom** – The UK had a [2011 UK Influenza Preparedness Strategy](#).¹⁰⁴ In addition to the afore-mentioned UK Influenza Preparedness Strategy, Wales had the 2007 Pandemic Influenza Guidance Planning was established before the 2009 influenza pandemic.
- **Greece** – The 2009 [National Action Plan toward the Influenza Pandemic](#).

Acts and laws

Germany has the 2001 Protection against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG). **Austria** has the Epidemiegesetz (Epidemic Law), which was last updated in 1950. This was the base for the pandemic management in early 2020, and the document which outlines that the Health Ministry oversees the pandemic response. Within the context of pandemics and health crises, **Spain** has the State of Alarm. The State of Alarm allows the central government to assume the direction of policy areas although regions keep on managing the services, providing new regulations that must be respected and observed by the regions, (Aba Catoira 2011; Vidal Prado and Delgado Ramos 2011). During the pandemic, three decrees of the State of Alarm were approved by the Government and ratified by the Spanish Parliament. Each one foresaw different measures in terms of the right restrictions, but also in terms of economic and social responses to face the economic paralysation caused by them.

Task forces

Austria has a designated Crisis and Catastrophe Emergency Task Force (Staatliche Krisen- und Katastrophenschutzmanagement, SKKM) which comes into action in emergency situations.

Strategies and Frameworks

Portugal has a crisis communication framework in place, which comprises a national emergency plan and a communication strategy. While the Directorate-General for Health (DGS) supervises the communication of health-related information to the public and healthcare rules. **Belgium** had a crisis management structure for potential pandemics before the COVID-19 pandemic. In line with the International Health Regulations (IHR) of the World Health Organisation (WHO), Belgium had set up a National Focal Point (NFP) over the course of 2007 and 2008. With a focus on documents relating to risk, **England** has a national risk register that provides an overview of the risks of huge emergencies that could potentially affect the UK, looking ahead two years at a time.¹⁰⁵ Updated every two years,

¹⁰³https://www.rki.de/EN/Content/infections/epidemiology/inf_dis_Germany/influenza/influenza_germany/Report_Influenza.html.

¹⁰⁴https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/213717/dh_131040.pdf.

¹⁰⁵Office, C. (2020, December 18). National Risk Register 2020. Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-risk-register-2020>.

the last register was updated in 2020. Pandemics were rated as the highest likelihood and impact (ibid). As mentioned in the D4.1 report, the Civil Contingencies Act and accompanying measures provide the framework for civil protection in the UK, including the activities that relative entities (Category 1) such as the Police, National Health System (NHS) and Fire Department must implement in an emergency. In **Wales**, the Wales Framework for Managing Infectious Disease Emergencies 2005 “sets out national arrangements for managing major infectious disease emergencies, including national co-ordination, operational responsibilities of NHS organisations and the role of partner agencies” (Welsh Government 2007: 3).

Government Structural Changes

Portugal, Austria, England, Wales witnessed no governmental structure changes from the periods of T1 and T2.

Across the COVINFORM countries under study, Germany, Sweden, Italy, Greece, and Spain underwent government structural changes from the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic and first lockdown until vaccination influenced measures (T1). In **Italy**, for example, the end of the first phase of the pandemic coincided with the formation of a new government headed by Mario Draghi, on 13 February 2021. In **Germany**, a federal parliamentary election was held on 26 September 2021, which led to a change in government.¹⁰⁶ In **Sweden**, the new Prime Minister Magdalena Andersson reorganized the government chancellery and moved responsibility for crisis management closer to the Cabinet office (Statsrådsberedningen).¹⁰⁷ In **Greece**, a new government was formed in September 2021 following cabinet reshuffle.¹⁰⁸ In **Spain**, and on 10 July 2021, Spanish Prime Minister Pedro Sanchez announced a government reshuffle.¹⁰⁹ In **Belgium**, a new government was formed in September 2020. Previously titled Caretaker Finance Minister, Alexander De Croo was named as the new Prime Minister.¹¹⁰

Regarding government changes during the timeframe of when Omicron first emerged in each of the COVINFORM countries up until now (T2), **Italy** underwent additional governmental structure changes, while the remaining COVINFORM countries remained the same. During the T2 timeframe, Italy had a general election, and a new government was formed. A new centre right government, led by Giorgia Meloni, took office in Italy in October 2022.¹¹¹

COVID-19 responses

Generally speaking, all COVINFORM countries experienced government enforced restrictions during phase T1. The restrictions introduced aimed to reduce the spread of the COVID-19 virus. During the T1

¹⁰⁶ Nienaber, M. (2021). Scholz takes over as German chancellor, ending merkel era. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/social-democrat-olaf-scholz-elected-german-chancellor-2021-12-08/>

¹⁰⁷ (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.regeringen.se/tal/2021/11/regeringsforklaringen-den-30-november-2021/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://greekcitytimes.com/2021/09/01/new-greek-government-formed-following-cabinet-reshuffle/>

¹⁰⁹ Spanish prime minister Pedro Sanchez announces government reshuffle. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2021/07/10/spanish-prime-minister-pedro-sanchez-announces-government-reshuffle>.

¹¹⁰ Strauss, M., & Blenkinsop, P. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/article/belgium-government-idINKBN26L1C8>

¹¹¹ Fella, S. (2022). Italy: 2022 general election and new government - House of Commons Library. Retrieved from <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-9629/>

phase, England and Sweden had a more relaxed approach in terms of response to the pandemic. In **England**, the initial T1 approach was the adoption of “herd immunity”. Herd immunity translates to indirect protection from an infectious disease that happens when a population is immune either through vaccination or immunity developed through previous infection.¹¹² It was only until simulations were carried out by the Imperial College COVID-19 response team that England decided to introduce social distancing measures in March 2020 (ibid). The simulations indicated that hospitals would be severely overwhelmed, if necessary, measures were not put in place (ibid). On 23 March, **England** applied its first ever national lockdown.¹¹³ By February 2022, all domestic legal restrictions ended and by March 2022, all remaining COVID-19 travel restrictions were removed for incoming international travellers to the UK.

During the T1 phase in **Wales**, the country only ever did one Firebreak lockdown (otherwise known as a short lockdown) and the implementation of the 5-mile rule. With the introduction of vaccines in Wales, the Welsh government stopped implementing unique measures, and more regularly replicated the UK-wide policies, albeit often for longer periods, for instance, mask wearing in public transport and testing commercially after having come back to Wales from international travel. Later in the pandemic response phase that entailed protective measures requiring the general public to comply with, the cautious approach Wales had taken became more difficult to uphold. During an expert interview, a national politician from an opposition party remarked that the Welsh government was scrutinised heavily for maintaining the pandemic measures that were considered for abandonment in England. The interviewee recalled a moment that this approach was not necessarily offered to the public in a genuine sense:

“[Government official] would look at the graph [displaying infection and hospital rates over a period] and was like; ‘see, things are as bad as we predicted’ And I went, ‘No, that’s not what that graph says’. And I was right. We were we were coming out of the Omicron wave quicker than government was telling us. We were, and they were they were playing the ‘let’s keep on scaring the public’-hand a little bit too hard on that occasion.”

As a result, in the spring of 2022, Wales changed its set of regulations from relatively strict in the UK context to none at all over a short time. This was mainly due to the combination of achieving a meaningful degree of population vaccination in Wales. Also, the Omicron variant emerging as likely less fatal after infection than earlier variants, and the likelihood of better weather.

Furthermore, in **Sweden**, the initial COVID-19 response revolved around “nudges” rather than strict measures. The decisions to keep society open, with no closed borders and kindergartens and schools open, made Sweden stand out internationally. It was only after the second wave, which hit Sweden

¹¹²(2020). Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/herd-immunity-lockdowns-and-covid-19#:~:text=What%20is%20%27herd%20immunity%27%3F,immunity%20developed%20through%20previous%20infection>.

¹¹³Strain, D., & Mohan, K. (2023). Lockdown, three years on: What have we learnt and what next?: BMA Blogs. Retrieved from <https://www.bma.org.uk/news-and-opinion/lockdown-three-years-on-what-have-we-learnt-and-what-next#:~:text=Three%20years%20ago%20today%2C%20on,health%20emergency%20of%20international%20concern>.

late fall 2020, that the country adopted the Temporary Act to prevent the spread of COVID-19. The legislation is intended to give the government the authority to adopt more binding communicable disease control measures than was previously possible. By 8 February 2022, the Swedish government agreed to remove most of the COVID-19 restrictions, such as limitations for public gatherings and events, such as social distance requirements, mandatory seating, and group size in restaurants and pubs. By April 1st, COVID-19 was no longer classified as a socially dangerous disease, which meant it was no longer subject to the Infection Protection Act. Note that the Pandemic Act was eventually removed.

Portugal gradually lifted restrictions, eventually removing the state of emergency in May 2021. With the emergence of the Omicron variant in late 2021, however, there was a resurgence of COVID-19 cases in Portugal and other countries. The government and health authorities responded by reintroducing some measures, such as mask mandates and capacity restrictions for public spaces. In **Germany**, the initial response to the COVID-19 pandemic was the rollout of hygiene regulations developed by the Robert Koch Institute, such as compulsory mask-wearing in public, as well as the definition of a risk communication strategy based on the slogan “Through the year with AHA” (“Mit AHA durchs Jahr”),¹¹⁴ which established the so-called AHA-Formula (AHA-Formel) to publicise basic risk mitigation measures and promote their acceptance:

- 1) „Abstand halten“ – “keep a safe distance”
- 2) „Hygiene-Maßnahmen beachten“ – “pay attention to hygiene measures“
- 3) „Alltagsmaske tragen“ – “wear a mask on an everyday basis”¹¹⁵

As the pandemic progressed during this time period, the implementation of lockdowns depended on the severity of infection and death case rates. For example, on a federal level, the first hard lockdown was phased out on 19 April 2020. Social distancing measures, however, remained in place. During summer 2020, restrictive measures were adopted flexibly on a state-by-state level in response to local infection rates. Then, in October 2020, when both case rates and deaths began to increase, the federal government implemented a second hard lockdown on 2 November, which extended until 19 December.

Moving on to the period of T2 in Germany, elevated infection rates – and to a lesser extent, death rates – continued well into 2022.¹¹⁶ It was only in April 2022 that many of the remaining restrictive measures, such as the requirement to wear masks in shops, were lifted (however, masks remained mandatory in hospitals and on public transportation). Note that a wave of increased infection and death rates in June 2022 did not substantially affect federal policy: while some new rules were implemented on a state-by-state level, most were minor. By Winter 2022, the consensus among public-facing experts such as virologist Christian Drosten was that COVID-19 had evolved into an endemic (rather than pandemic) disease (ibid). In **Spain**, the initial response to the COVID-19 pandemic during the T1 phase was the implementation of the State of Alarm. From May to June 2020, the spread of COVID-19 decreased, and the State of Alarm started reducing the intensity of some limitations. By June

¹¹⁴https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/fileadmin/Dateien/5_Publikationen/Gesundheit/Flyer_Post_er_etc/Corona/AHA-Formel_Blau-Rot_barr_V2.pdf

¹¹⁵ (N.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.infektionsschutz.de/coronavirus/alltag-in-zeiten-von-corona/>

¹¹⁶ Deutsche Welle. (2022a). Retrieved from <https://www.dw.com/en/top-german-virologist-says-covid-19-pandemic-is-over/a-64214994>.

2020, the State of Alarm came to an end, which meant that the restoration of fundamental rights implied that regions recovered full control of their competences. At this point of time, the Spanish parliament approved a law that fixed some limitations to assure social distancing after the State of Alarm, in a period labelled as “new normality”: the reduction of capacity in shops, bars and restaurants, the mandatory use of masks, and some rules about physical distancing inside buildings. Like Germany, tightening of restrictions were only considered depending on the spread of COVID-19. For example, a third state of alarm was declared on October 7, 2020, due to the second wave of COVID-19 in Madrid.

In **Belgium**, the initial response during the T1 phase included necessary lockdowns, measures, and the adoption of the ‘corona barometer’, which supported policy preparation and communication. The barometer consisted of three phases: code yellow, orange and red. During the T2 phase, the change in response was that COVID-19 measures were gradually relaxed and lifted. In **Greece**, the response during the T1 phase also included lockdowns and measures required to slow down the spread of the COVID-19 virus. Interestingly, the response was tailored and immediate and included measures that were especially targeted towards vulnerable populations. Additional tailored responses and measure adjustments were also considered to address the Omicron variant of COVID-19. That said, although the majority of the population had already gone through the necessary doses of the vaccine, the relevant campaign was not projecting a strict message as the previous ones. In **Italy**, Conte’s government posed all attentions to contain the spread of the COVID-19 virus. It was in December 2021, which falls under the T2 phase, where the country began its vaccination campaign, and the government was starting to open up activities that were severely restricted.

Secondary and WP4 Expert Interview reflections on pandemic management

This section will provide commonalities in terms of positive and negative reflections noted in the previous deliverables D4.1 and D4.5, and the WP4 expert interviews conducted across all the COVINFORM countries under study. The reflections mainly concern pandemic management and its changes throughout the different time phases this deliverable is interested in. In addition, some issues and successes from the reflections will also be pointed out.

Findings from the WP4 expert interviews

Governance Systems

In **Sweden**, the national crisis management, according to a high-profile regional politician interviewed, was considered ineffective. SALAR (the Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions) was viewed as an important body in coordinating crisis management between the national and regional/local level of governance, but the ability for crisis management on the national level was questioned and arguments were raised for centralizing crisis management to the national level. Politicians and government agencies on regional and local levels also addressed critique against what they saw as inefficient crisis management, where government agencies were given tasks, of which they had no previous experience. A regional politician interviewed noted:

“The National Board of Health and Welfare, was no particular supportand the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency were probably mostly invisible. There is probably a need for a crisis management organization in the state that is more well-trained and well-trimmed, that has greater powers, right?”

In **Belgium**, the “complex” COVID-19 governance system was also criticised. One expert indicated that the collaboration went well in situations where the responsibilities were clear, and different

actors/representatives had similar responsibilities and interests. However, when different people sitting around the same table had very different responsibilities, this complicated decision-making. In addition, an interviewee pointed out the tensions in the coordination between federal and regional levels of decision-making, which the interviewee thought was often related to financial considerations. The interviewee added:

“There is also definitely a tension between federal and regional. And that is mostly to do with money, I feel. Who takes care of what funding? And then, of course, there is also a little bit of power involved, so then you notice that politics also uses that, like – ‘I’m going to grant you this, but then I want that in return’. And then you see that those political agendas no longer match the scientific agendas. And then there is both a tension federal-regional, but also between the administrations and the cabinets. Where normally the Agency for Care and Health [at the Flemish level] should have the same voice as the Beke cabinet, you notice that a political and a scientific agenda are opposing each other there. And that also makes it kind of difficult. There were many different layers in the policy, and many different players, with many different agendas, where health was not the only one” (Government_3, Belgium).

In **Austria**, concerns were mainly related to the idleness of decision making in the Austrian democratic system and federalism. An interviewee commented:

[...] I'm not criticizing the democratic system. As a democratic republic with all the things it takes to get a law going, we are very, very sluggish in managing a crisis that requires immediate action. Because the decision-making process in our state sometimes takes years. If you look at major legislative projects, and I think that's a good thing. It is also good that all stakeholders have the opportunity to get involved in the discourse. It's also good that you take the time to discuss this with people and listen to the needs of groups that may not be present all the time and don't have a super good lobby. But that means that these processes all have and must have a very low stepping speed, yes. Because otherwise I can't (hear) them all. It is of course difficult in such a situation to enact rules very quickly in a very rapid and dynamic situation....to enact these rules for everyone in such a way that they are always up to date [Government_1 Austria].

The slow decision-making process led to a rather undynamic crisis response while the Austria's federal system led to confusing multitude of rules and regulations in the various Austrian states. In the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, the crisis was only managed by the national government. Over time, this changed and those political areas, where the state government has power over, were more and more decided on a local state level than on the national one. This was influenced by different political leadership as well as differing epidemiological developments. In the beginning, one interviewee commented:

“[...] everyone was very happy, I think, that there were corresponding requirements and corresponding legal measures at national level. And then ultimately the federal states, but also the social partners, the emergency organizations, had a rather positive connotation that there is now strong leadership. That there are clear instructions, and that it was also clear to the residents that... how to behave. In a later episode, however, that's yes, it developed differently, didn't it? On the one hand, this leadership is no longer so clear, there

have been many political disputes. Suddenly, very recently, there have been so many developments in the last few months where the federal government, i.e. the national level, has handed over this control sovereignty and, in the spirit of federalism, has transferred it to the federal states, which then acted at their own discretion which meant that it was different between the countries, uh, that there was more debate about it in public and that the systems are no longer completely harmonized" (Government_2 Austria).

In **Portugal**, an interviewee commented that as the pandemic progressed, the level of governmental trust among immigrants increased. The only critique towards the government was the lack of coordination between different levels of government, with some experts noting that local governments were often left out of decision-making processes or asked for involvement very late in the process. However, and even though articulation with local authorities was sometimes absent, it is important to underline that local authorities rapidly intervened to deal with the more vulnerable people. An interviewee explained:

"We found young people who were working in renowned restaurants but who did not have regular employment contracts, the day after confinement they ended up on the street, (...) it was necessary to respond very quickly to all these people and all the measures that were built in terms of food, shelter, protection and later also vaccination, we created a program with the general health department and the regional health administration of Lisbon and Vale do Tejo to vaccinate all homeless people. (...) fact that the yearly vaccination against the flu in the homeless population helped decrease the suspicion and resistance to the COVID-19 vaccination" (expert 5).

COVID-19 policy

In **Spain**, COVID-19 policy was seen as positive. The general consensus was that Spain responded quickly to the pandemic in spite of the complex context in which decisions had to be made. One interviewee commented:

"Well, starting with the consequences, we can begin with the economic ones, which are the ones that I say are clearest, and here I do believe that the response that was taken, agile, rapid, at the time of decreeing the confinement, was fundamental (...) Well, I think that a crisis like this one, in which you have to be very agile and quick in your decisions, obviously the system of governance, as it was put in place with the State of Alarm, showed that it could respond as it has been to a crisis situation like this one" (Spain_URJC_WP4_5_DM).

Belgium, on the other hand, faced critique in terms of COVID-19 policy. According to experts interviewed, Belgium's COVID-19 policy was seen as reactive and short-term, lacking transparency, and long-term planning. One expert interviewed stated:

"People should see it as an opportunity, as a wake-up call. We need to ensure that we have ties to the communities. We should not have blind spots about our people, our citizens. We have to go more into the communities through trusted figures, and go through community organizations, and be present. To give information in a good and appropriate way, through people who have street credibility and who are trustworthy to the people involved" (Government_2, Belgium).

Non-pharmaceutical interventions

In **Italy**, successes in pandemic management concerned the implementation of lockdowns. On the topic of lockdowns, one of the interviewees said:

“Although the decision for a national lockdown was the most difficult and painful, because of its economic and social consequences as well as the consequences on individual lives, it proved to be the most effective in limiting the spread of the virus. The vaccination campaign has also proved to be an effective solution, as shown by data on admissions to intensive care of covid patients, currently divided into two distinct groups: those who are not vaccinated and those who are vaccinated but have by pre-existing vulnerable health conditions.” (Government_2, Italy).

In **Belgium**, it was identified that as the pandemic progressed, the government did well in terms of focusing more on contact tracing efforts.

In contrast, Greece, Wales, Austria, and Sweden faced critique. Interviews conducted in Wales, Greece, and Austria address the issue of lockdown. In **Greece**, social isolation (i.e., lockdowns) was critiqued in terms of the negative impacts that lockdowns had on society, the national economy, and the mental health of citizens. At the same time, however, it was acknowledged that lockdowns did bring some good, such as the mitigation of the virus and saving the lives of many citizens. In **Wales**, the “restrictive pandemic measures” were critiqued in terms of freedoms. According to two of the interviewees, the measures entailed the supposed encroachment of human rights of the individual. Both mention the proposals for COVID passes for entry to hospitality establishments (e.g., pubs and restaurants) as being de-valued on the basis that they infringe an individual’s right not to get vaccinated, or not to show medical information to be allowed access to a place:

“The discussion on human rights has been so hijacked (...) And, to a certain extent, this is imported from the far right in the United States. And it appears to be done in a sort of random way, but it's being done in this systematic way to undermine things. (...) One way of course of undermining human rights is claiming that you've got human rights. We don't have them, in particular – “my right to go to the pub, without a mask without a vaccine. I've got this right. It doesn't matter about your health. I don't believe you've got that right” (South-Wales MP1).

In **Austria**, with the pandemic ongoing, some segments of society became dissatisfied with the government’s pandemic management. Particular issues were ongoing lockdown and the mandatory vaccination¹¹⁷. In **Sweden**, critique mainly concerned the wearing of face masks. The PHA, for example, argued there was no scientific proof showing they would limit the spread of COVID-19.

Difficulties in reaching specific groups within society

Although vulnerabilities in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic will be addressed later in the report, the interviewees reflections on pandemic management with regards to specific groups within society, is presented. In **Belgium**, experts interviewed expressed their concern that there is still much unknown

¹¹⁷ <https://www.derstandard.at/story/2000131674525/zehntausende-demonstrierten-in-wien-gegen-impfpflicht-und-gegen-lockdown>

about how to reach specific groups in society, and this dilemma is related to the collection of disaggregated data. Disaggregated data, such as data by migration background, would provide more insight into how some groups are disproportionately affected, yet there are fears that such data collection may lead to further stigmatization and discrimination. This was mentioned by an interviewee:

“The data story is also a very important one. [...] You give a mandate to the field where they have to start designing actions and interventions for sensitization to specific groups, almost on an individual level, but there wasn’t the data infrastructure to supply those teams with enough data.” (Government_6, Belgium).

As the pandemic progressed, the government did start to focus more on vulnerable groups. Similarly, in **England**, an interviewee mentioned that at a governmental level, it was difficult to provide aid to vulnerable groups. Difficulties mainly stemmed from managing issues centrally. As time passed, however, one interviewee noted that it was eventually realised that issues should be managed at the local government level. In terms of addressing and identifying needs in England, an interviewee explained:

“We were able to implement a plan of action and care, but overall it shows the increased in deprivation.”

On a more positive note, **Portugal** recognised that the government temporally normalised “all immigrants’ granting full access to public services, namely public health services (free medical care upon covid-symptomatic suspicion, vaccination and testing)” (Expert 2).

As stated by the interviewee:

“This helped to cease discrimination against immigrants who do not have their situation regularized in Portugal and hence do not have financial means to receive the appropriate assistance, as well as contributed to a greater sense of safety of the Portuguese population who now had immigrants by their side receiving the same treatment and vigilance as any other Portuguese citizen” (expert 2).”

Governmental approaches to COVID-19 communication

A number of interviewees expressed concerns for how communication was handled by the government during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Regarding communication in **Italy**, the interviewee commented:

“both for the (often confusing) information given by governments to citizens, and for the increasing scandalous tone of several newspapers, as well as the overexposure in the media of some virologists and other health professionals who have not provided constructive contributions. In particular, it should be the responsibility of the government to provide clear information, even in cases where this information is not reassuring. It is therefore necessary to avoid giving partial or incomplete information, which has often proved contradictory (as in the case of the Astra Zeneca vaccines) and weakens public confidence.” (Government_2, Italy).

Communication was also critiqued in **Germany**. Throughout the period of T1, the federal and state government were often criticised for inconsistency in issuing and communicating new restrictions.

Interviewees in the sub-national research site of Mannheim sometimes indicated that this could be confusing for not only the general public, but also local administrators and front-line workers, and that efforts were made to introduce more clarity by adapting higher-level communications on the local level:

“Federal and state policy again and again also contributed to the fact that the decrees sometimes came at very short notice and that the orders or the communication took place in a language that was not understandable for many. I don't exclude myself at all at certain points [...] We have tried to find ways at the municipal level, but perhaps we'll come to that later” (senior administrator, Mannheim Office for Health and Youth).

Reflections on communication in **Belgium** mainly concerned limited resources and capacity to carry out tailored approaches for the population. One interviewee highlighted:

“At a certain point you obviously get saturated and you're left with numbers of people where that [personalised approach] hardly works. At the peak of this fourth wave, some people simply cannot be called anymore [in contact tracing] and they are sent text messages instead. You can easily understand that this is of far lesser quality than a careful conversation over the phone, or seeing people in person. Quantity takes priority over quality at a certain point otherwise you miss 95% of people.” (Government_5, Belgium).

In **Sweden**, critique was also addressed toward national government agencies for collecting a lot of data without any feedback of how they were used. This issue is for example addressed by a regional politician interviewed in COVINFORM, who pointed out the following:

“They gave the county administrative board a mission to collect a lot of information. They didn't have an organization for this. It got messy and created some irritation with us and our employees.”

Unlike the afore-mentioned countries, in **Portugal**, communication from the government and health authorities was praised by a number of experts interviewed as being clear and consistent by experts, particularly during the early stages of the pandemic. Particular praise was given to the expansion of ICU capacity and the use of telemedicine to support patient care.

Vaccination

In **Germany**, particularly during 2021 and 2022, the most critical element of German COVID-19 response policy was vaccination. To elaborate further, decision-makers in Germany at both federal and state levels have been, and continue to be, critiqued for their vaccination communication (BMG 2022: 57). Furthermore, a controversial measure implemented in Germany during the first and second quarters of 2021 were “2G/2G+/3G” regulations, which meant that only vaccinated, recovered, and/or tested persons could get access to restaurants, events, or other services. These sorts of measures were authorised under the COVID-19 Protective Measures Exemption Ordinance (COVID-19-Schutzmaßnahmen-Ausnahmenverordnung) and implemented mostly on a state-by-state rather than federal level. In Austria, mandatory vaccination was seen as an issue. The polarisation of the people in Austria (around vaccination) was also fuelled by the FPÖ. From the beginning, the party opposed the government's measures and participated in demonstrations against the government. Because of the FPÖ leader Herbert Kickl, many half-truths and fake news about Coronavirus made its way into parliament. For example, on May 26, 2021, Kickl, in Parliament, made the claim:

"Governments and agencies are coercing their healthy citizens to be participants in a huge genetic engineering experiment - outcome uncertain."

Technology

In **England**, reflections around communication mainly concerned difficulties during the beginning of the pandemic in terms of shifting from face-to-face interactions to virtual interactions. The interviewee mentioned that they needed four to six weeks to comprehend what worked and what did not with new technology.

One of the interviewees explained:

"The big thing that changed was the way to assess care because we had to do in a virtual way and it was a challenge for me."

In **Portugal**, it was reported that technological developments during the pandemic were a success. One interviewee stated:

"The transition to telework was successful allowing a team of 12-14 people to switch to working remotely without loss of productivity. It was possible to improve the monitoring and reporting of the various entities under the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action" (expert 4).

Furthermore, another interviewee from Portugal added:

"The pandemic and all that's entailed created potential opportunities like teleworking, distant learning, news strategies to deal with vulnerable groups, and major connection between politicians and experts" (expert 1).

Government approaches to defining and addressing vulnerability

Across all the COVINFORM countries, the start of the pandemic presented an opportunity to the government to recognise the different vulnerabilities emerging from the COVID-19 pandemic and how to respond to them. Vulnerabilities did change over time (over T1 and T2), and new vulnerable groups were acknowledged. In **Greece**, vulnerability was mostly associated with those who were elderly. Healthcare-related vulnerabilities included those with heart diseases and respiratory conditions. As the pandemic progressed, socio-economic vulnerabilities were also recognised and taken into consideration by the Greek response mechanism throughout the COVID-19 pandemic phases. In **Sweden**, the PHA identified groups with low socio-economic status as being vulnerable, but migrants with low trust and non-Swedish speaking inhabitants were also recognised as being more vulnerable. As the pandemic progressed, other groups were identified as being more vulnerable. For example, this included those classified as disabled, chronically ill, obese, and pregnant. The elderly were also identified as being more vulnerable from the beginning. Moreover, medically defined groups were also seen as risk groups. In **Germany**, the German federal government's initial definition (at T1) of "at-risk groups" focused on factors that increased the chance of a severe progression of COVID-19. As 2020 passed into 2021 (T2), official definitions of at-risk groups shifted to encompass factors that increased the chance of exposure to the SARS-CoV-2 virus as well. Specifically, six priority groups are identified based on several risk clusters, specifically: Persons with an elevated risk of infection in front-line occupations, first responders and transportation workers, persons with an elevated risk of infection

due to other circumstances, such as residents and workers in homeless shelters and persons with precarious work and living situations.

In **Italy**, an interviewee noted:

“On a national level, the government and the Scientific Technical Committee have not identified any specific vulnerable population, they just did “a general reference to fragility” in their papers. This was a major problem for the Stakeholder as data showed that covid-19 has killed mostly elderly people with an average of three comorbidities, however, no specific measures have been implemented to protect this target” (Government_3, Italy).

It was only when lockdowns (both during and after) were implemented that vulnerabilities were recognised. During the T1 phase, vulnerabilities included women who were at greater disadvantage than men. Vulnerabilities for women included the sharp decline in work activities, women being confined in their houses and suffering violence, and witnessing harassment by their partners. Besides vulnerabilities among women, other vulnerabilities included children and adolescents forced into distance learning and social isolation, people with physical and mental disabilities deprived of support from institutions other than family support, migrants (especially those with irregular status), and people in closed residential communities (e.g., prisons).

In **Spain**, initial vulnerabilities recognised included minors under the age of 14, elderly people (particularly those who lived in residential homes or were disabled), people who required housing assistance, people who were labelled as consumers (i.e., those left in a position of not being able to access food or other basic products or services), and women that may be suffering gender or domestic violence at home. As the pandemic progressed, economic vulnerabilities were recognised. Groups highlighted include informal workers, part-time workers with temporary contracts, workers with wages below the minimum wage (this was often linked to sectors such as construction, hospitality, retail, domestic work, immigrant workers, single-parent households, etc). In addition to these profiles, the pandemic added others: households whose main income earner is a self-employed worker, family micro-enterprises (bars, small restaurants, local stores) that maintained a precarious balance between income and expenses, those with no savings to face the crisis, those who have been forced to ask for social assistance, and maintenance of household members.

In **Portugal**, and at the governmental level, specific communications for vulnerable populations were not identified. Although, the government frequently communicated (via news on the website and in coordination with local authorities) that:

“will remain attentive to the needs of the most vulnerable populations in the face of the pandemic, among which are some Roma communities, and will provide the necessary measures to help these vulnerable communities” (ARS, 2020).

A statement advertising a youth volunteering initiative to help disadvantaged communities was also identified:

“In order to support, strengthen and qualify the community support responses carried out by Portuguese parishes during the isolation period, the Portuguese Institute of Sports and Youth (IPDJ), in partnership with the National Association of Parishes (ANAFRE), promotes the volunteering action “Greater Support” (Government of Portugal, 2020).

Once the pandemic started in Portugal, the Portuguese government acknowledged and addressed several vulnerabilities among different groups, including the elderly, healthcare workers, homeless people, immigrants, and refugees. Over time, new vulnerable groups were defined and acknowledged. This included low-income workers, children and youth, and people with disabilities.

In **England**, vulnerable groups recognised were those over the age of 70, people below the age of 70 with an underlying health condition and pregnant women.¹¹⁸ As already discussed in the D4.1 deliverable, however, research on COVID-19 and vulnerable groups on the UK parliament website provided additional results regarding vulnerability. When the COVID-19 pandemic first emerged, vulnerabilities included those with limited knowledge of digital services while it was additionally acknowledged that this group may not possess the required equipment or monetary funds to own digital equipment. Mental health among the youth, people originating from ethnic minorities, and the homeless were also recognised as vulnerable groups. Further into the COVID-19 pandemic timeline, and especially during the year of 2022, vulnerabilities concerning those with access to the COVID-19 booster vaccine was noted. The February 2022 Living with COVID-19 Plan reported UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) data on vaccine booster uptake recording outstanding disparities. At the time of reporting, it was noted that booster uptake was lowest among the Black and Pakistani adult populations (below 35%) with disparities also recorded between the least deprived (84%) and most deprived areas (53%), as well as low uptake among 18–24-year-olds (39%) (HM Cabinet Office, 2021). Regarding those aged 12-15, there were also large disparities noted concerning initial vaccine doses; the lowest numbers in the Gypsy/Roma, Irish Traveller, Black Caribbean, and Black African groups (ibid). Finally, the UKHSA, on 13 May 2022, noted that black pregnant women had one or more vaccine doses compared to 58% white pregnant women and with women from lower areas of impoverishment (38.9% of pregnant women in most impoverished areas had one or more doses in contrast to 71.1% in least deprived areas (UK Health Security Agency, 2022)).¹¹⁹

In **Wales**, the concept of vulnerability was rooted in biomedical categorisations. However, social vulnerability, became rapidly part of the governmental debates on how to keep the infection, illness, hospital bed occupation, and death rates down. In **Austria**, the government understood vulnerable groups as those who are at higher risk of suffering from severe symptoms and to whom the disease could potentially be life-threatening. This included people aged over 65 years as well as people with (chronic) pre-existing conditions of all ages. Eventually, additional vulnerable groups identified were those who felt the negative social impact of COVID-19 more strongly. Over time, children became part of the public discourse as a vulnerable group due to school closures. Finally, many stakeholders acknowledged the negative secondary effects such as loneliness that were created through lockdowns and social distancing measures.

In **Greece**, the focus of the Greek response mechanism was mainly orientated towards healthcare-related vulnerabilities, whilst socio-economic measures were also implemented to address the impact

¹¹⁸The Health Protection (Coronavirus, Restrictions) (England) Regulations 2020. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2020/350/2020-06-13?view=plain>.

¹¹⁹Agency, U. H. S. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-health-security-agencylaunches-with-a-relentless-focus-on-keeping-the-nation-safe>.

that COVID-19 had on citizens and businesses impacted by the pandemic and relevant measures, as stated in D4.1, expert interviews, D4.4, and D4.5. To that end, the government issued specific financial support measures during the pandemic waves, to assist groups such as persons with disabilities, single-parent families, families with four or more children, immigrants, asylum seekers, unaccompanied minors, and the elderly among citizens categorised by socioeconomic and health-related vulnerabilities. In **Italy**, measures were put in place to support the elderly and their caregivers, workers, families, and low-income citizens, migrant population, women who were victims of domestic violence, children and teenagers, people with disabilities, people in prisons, and healthcare providers. In **Sweden**, vulnerable groups were supported through “customized communication” which included tailored messages and channels for specific target groups. To customize the pandemic communication, the PHA (Public Health Administration) translated material into different languages, tailored messages to different groups and cooperated with civil society organisations (churches and mosques) to get in contact with migrant dense communities. Government agencies, regions and municipalities also used health communicators, and vaccine communicators to communicate with people living in migrant dense areas. In December 2021, the government released a plan for improving communication to the public, especially where vaccination rates were lower compared to the average population. In **Germany**, special measures were taken to support health vulnerabilities. The broader set of governmental measures explicitly and/or implicitly targeted a wide range of population groups and institutions. These included population groups and institutions/sectors.

In **Spain**, interviewees reported that measures were put in place both by the army and at the social level, in collaboration with communities. In **Portugal**, and in the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in particular, the government implemented measures to support vulnerable groups, such as the elderly, people with pre-existing medical conditions, and those with low incomes. These measures included the distribution of protective equipment to nursing homes, the provision of financial assistance to low-income households, and the expansion of telemedicine services for individuals with chronic health conditions. In addition, the government launched a campaign to promote awareness of the risks of COVID-19 among vulnerable groups and to encourage adherence to public health guidelines. This campaign included targeted messaging and information dissemination through social media and other communication channels (WHO, 2020). As the pandemic progressed, new measures were initiated to support vulnerable groups further. In November 2020, for example, the government announced the launch of a program to support homeless individuals during the pandemic, providing them with temporary housing, food, and medical assistance (Reuters, 2020). Furthermore, asylum seekers with residence permit requests pending at SEF (Portuguese and Border Service) were in a regular situation until 30 June 2020 and could have access to the same rights and support that Portuguese citizens have, including health, social support, employment, and housing.

In **England**, interviewees reported that the immediate response to supporting vulnerable groups was providing food to the most vulnerable. In **Wales**, examples of efforts to support vulnerable groups include information in multiple languages, spoken information on websites, discrete vaccination booths with female staff, and vaccines being offered and administered at the place of work for sex workers in the evening. As time passed, the development of the vaccination equity strategy changes with more social groups being added that had particular issues in accessing the vaccine.

In **Austria**, examples of measures to support vulnerable groups include the protection of high-risk groups, which was regulated through the social insurance law (Sozialversicherungsgesetz). The measures taken to protect these groups encompass home office, paid leave, protective gear and so

forth. Another health-related measure was aimed at protecting pregnant women from the risk of infection at their workplace. Similarly, employees were granted additional four weeks of paid time off work between the 1st of November 2020 and the 9th of July 2021 if they have caretaking responsibilities towards children under 14 or people living with disability or relatives in need of care. Additionally, already in March 2020, the Austrian government provided a first aid package (€38 Billion) to battle the negative economic outcome of the COVID-19 virus and related lockdown as well as other measures¹²⁰. This included the short work scheme where employers remove employees from their payroll and have their wages subsidised by the government, financial hardship fund (Härtefallfond) for small enterprises and one person companies, a Corona fund and a fixed expenses subsidy program (IHS 2020 May, Desson 2020). The Härtefallfond ended in May 2022 and the fixed expenses subsidy program already ran out in August 2021. With a focus on measures to support children, the Ministry of Education, in particular, addressed the extent of school closures, deciding that restrictions would be reduced to an absolute minimum and would be in line with regulations in other areas of life.

In **Austria**, it was reported that lockdowns and social distancing measures contributed towards loneliness. Similarly, in **Belgium**, the emotional impact of lockdowns heightened feelings of loneliness. One interviewee commented:

“... especially during lockdown periods, [living alone] was not easy. Because as a couple or when you live together as a family, you still have those contacts. But when you live by yourself you have nothing or no one, no shoulder to cry on or someone you can share something nice with or arms to comfort you if something happens, or whatever.”
(Government_4, Belgium)

Furthermore, the loss of the social aspect of education due to school closures had a big impact on the mental wellbeing of children and young people. In **Wales**, a senior policy advisor interviewed noted that occupational groups were new vulnerable groups that were addressed within their vaccination strategy. The policy advisor noted that taxi drivers were vulnerable because some people using their services would not wear face masks. In **Greece**, the daily influx of COVID-19 information, in combination with measures such as social isolation and prolonged lockdowns, was identified as having a role in the declining psychological wellbeing. These isolating measures also had a contributing role in increased cases of domestic violence in the average population, including vulnerable groups. According to relevant sources, cases of domestic violence in Greece have quadrupled since the COVID-19 outbreak (Chatzisyemonidis and Kioskli, 2023), (Chioni-Chotouman, 2020), (Kitsantonis, 2022), (Spiliopoulou and Anagnostopoulou, 2023).

In **Germany**, BMG Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies not only critiqued of the lack of attention given by policymakers to certain vulnerable groups, but also identified instances in which existing vulnerabilities were exacerbated or new vulnerabilities created. For instance, it cited several international studies on the psychological and social impact of pandemic response measures on women and younger people and recommends offering improved digital therapeutic resources and ensuring a minimum level of social contact. The Evaluation emphasises the impacts of school closures on children and youth and balances the clear evidence of such impacts against the lack of decisive evidence on the effectiveness of school closures as a non-pharmaceutical

¹²⁰

<https://www.bundeskanzleramt.gv.at/bundeskanzleramt/nachrichten-der-bundesregierung/2020/hilfspaket-von-bis-zu-38-milliarden-euro-zur-bewaeltigung-der-coronavirus-folgen.html>

intervention. The Evaluation also states that certain measures may have aggravated gendered vulnerability, confirming the importance of protecting women against domestic violence and noting that in some cases, the pandemic appears to have led to the “re-traditionalization” of gender roles and retrenchment of gendered economic inequality (e.g., as certain economic support mechanisms appeared to primarily benefit male workers).

In **England**, measures affected victims of domestic abuse, homeless people, children, and disabled people. With a focus on victims of domestic abuse, England strengthened its response to this issue when, as stated in D4.1, the House of Commons Women and Equalities Committee performed an inquiry into the effect that COVID-19 and the measures to combat the virus were having on people with protected characteristics under the 2010 Equality Act. Regarding homeless people, the government teamed up with charity organisations to provide people who were sleeping on the streets with accommodation during lockdown.¹²¹ A scheme called ‘Everyone In’ was created, and this involved the government writing to all local authorities in England asking them to provide shelter to people sleeping rough, including those staying in hostels and night shelters (ibid). As for children, there were a few concerns brought up about the possible impact of coronavirus mitigation measures, such as school closures and social contact rules, on young people’s lives.¹²² This included potential negative effects on educational attainment, mental health, and on children from disadvantaged backgrounds. Disruptions for children have concerned education and skills, health and wellbeing and poverty and inequality (ibid).

Regarding disabled people, a 21 February 2021 *The Health Foundation* article titled ‘The Forgotten Crisis: Exploring the disproportionate impact of the pandemic on disabled people,’¹²³ reported that UK COVID-19 restrictions have had a disproportionate effect on aspects of disabled people’s lives (ibid). In one interview conducted with a Government Official, it was disclosed that measures were put in place to help disabled communities. The interviewee explained:

“One example is that of the City Deaf Institute whereby universal messages were given and translated into sign languages in a number of languages. Q&A sessions were also established in different languages (e.g., Somali, Romani, Mandarin). Furthermore, there were targeted sessions for children and young people by using a different language than adults. In this way, tailored messages were delivered. The interviewee also released live on Instagram, while the organization commissioned partners to run Tik Tok campaigns.”

In **Spain**, it was reported that decision makers were aware about the consequences of limiting the free mobility of individuals. The lockdown implied that many individuals could not work, such as those employed in the service sector not related to alimentation, or similar. Some initiatives to help those affected by economic vulnerabilities included the ERTE programme (relevant to the T1 phase) which

¹²¹https://www.feantsa.org/public/user/Resources/magazine/2020/Full_Magazine_Autumn_2020.pdf.

¹²²Covid-19: Impact on child poverty and on Young People’s education ... (n.d.). Retrieved April 24, 2023, from <https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/covid-19-impact-on-child-poverty-and-on-young-peoples-education-health-and-wellbeing/>.

¹²³Sayce, L. (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.health.org.uk/news-and-comment/blogs/the-forgotten-crisis-exploring-the-disproportionate-impact-of-the-pandemic>

implied a wage replacement for those employees who could not work. Support to irregular migrants also saw cooperation with NGOs to provide food and supplies. For individuals that had an insufficient wage or were unemployed (but were in regular conditions in Spain), the government approved the Minimum Living Income, a type of universal wage for people that have low salaries or are looking for employment. For all citizens with low incomes, the government approved an electric bonus, that implied a reduction of the cost of electricity and gas.

In **Sweden**, it was recognised that there were problems with overcrowding, dependence on public transportation and working in settings where social distance was problematic. In health care, measures were introduced to protect staff, and these were later also introduced to elderly care. No measures were introduced to limit the spread due to overcrowded conditions, and physical illness was also discussed even if no specific measures were taken to deal with these problems.

In **Portugal**, new campaigns and initiatives were set up to address the mental health toll of the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, measures were implemented to support remote learning and provide financial assistance for families to purchase technological equipment, especially for children from disadvantaged backgrounds affected by the pandemic's impact on education. Domestic violence was another concern during the pandemic, and civil society organisations launched campaigns to raise awareness and provide support for victims. Overall, the Portuguese government, public health system, civil society organisations, and crisis communication efforts acknowledged and addressed vulnerabilities related to various groups at different stages of the pandemic, adapting to address new vulnerabilities as they emerged. The economic impact of the pandemic also affected low-income families and people in precarious jobs, leading to food insecurity and difficulties in paying for basic necessities such as rent and utilities. Similarities can also be noted in Greece. In Greece, governmental agencies often in collaboration with non-governmental organisations, would provide psychological support and services. To mitigate the negative impact of COVID-19, dedicated communication lines were established to accommodate the needs of citizens whereas the Hellenic Association of Psychologists, offered free of charge psychological sessions for citizens. In relation to education on a remote basis, the governmental mechanism offered vouchers so that students could be equipped with the technological means to study from home.¹²⁴¹²⁵¹²⁶

Furthermore, in Portugal, people with chronic illnesses have had difficulty accessing healthcare services due to overwhelmed hospitals and clinics. The pandemic has also had an educational impact, particularly for children from low-income families and those with special needs. School closures and online learning have created new challenges for these groups, leading to a widening of educational inequalities. Host schools were established to receive children and young people unable to take online classes at home.

¹²⁴ (N.d.). Retrieved from <https://eody.gov.gr/tilefoniki-grammi-psychokoinonikis-ypostirixis-10306-gia-ton-koronoio/?print=print>

¹²⁵ (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.newsit.gr/ellada/koronoios-dorean-psyxologiki-ypostir/2996936/>

¹²⁶ Newsroom, A. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://www.alfavita.gr/ekpaideysi/ypoyrgeio-paideias/339933_tilekpaideysi-voucher-200-eyro-se-mathites-gia-agora

COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance

This section will highlight some of the key COVID-19 responses on multiple levels of governance, and will be taken up in further detail in D4.8. Some of the key takeaways are presented below.

Across all the COVINFORM countries under study, a few examples of how crisis response was implemented at the beginning of the pandemic included the following:

- New COVID-19 Laws (e.g., permitting the execution of fines and penalties)
- Implementation of Test and Trace
- Mandatory COVID-19 testing
- COVID-19 Vaccine certificates
- Non-pharmaceutical interventions
- Economic supports
- Investment in healthcare, e.g., personnel, medical supplies, and PPE
- Implementation of state of calamities, state of alarms, state of emergencies
- Purpose and expert-driven taskforces and committee
- Government interventions to address misinformation

On the topic of how those in charge initially reacted to the COVID-19 pandemic, commonalities can be noted among the COVINFORM countries under study. Apart from Wales, England, and Sweden, the remaining COVINFORM countries (Italy, Austria, Spain, Greece, Germany, Wales, Belgium, and Portugal) reacted promptly to put in place relevant and strict measures that would help contain the COVID-19 virus. In **Sweden**, the initial reaction was relaxed. This was partly due to lack of legislation not making lockdown an option, but the Swedish government and its expert agencies also made somewhat different analysis of the situation compared to other (Nordic) countries. With a particular focus on **England's** reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic, the initial reaction was one of optimism. During an opening statement from a press conference (19 March 2020) on Coronavirus, former Prime Minister Boris Johnson said:

“I do think, looking at it all, that we can turn within the next 12 weeks. And I am absolutely confident that we can send coronavirus packing in this country but only if we take the steps, we all take the steps we have outlined...”¹²⁷

In **Greece**, although it was reported that there were no significant changes in crisis response, all necessary measures were adopted by the emergency acts of legislative content. **Germany** also did not introduce many policy innovations on COVID-19.

Sweden, Portugal, England, Wales witnessed changes in crisis response. In **Sweden**, changes to the crisis response mainly concerned the adoption of the temporary Act to prevent the spread of COVID-19. In **Portugal**, the crisis response evolved to adapt to changing circumstances and challenges. The response initially focused on controlling the spread of the virus through measures such as lockdowns and business closures, but as the COVID-19 vaccine became more available, the focus shifted to managing the impact of the virus on healthcare and the economy. One significant change was the introduction of the digital COVID-19 certificate, which allowed individuals to prove their vaccination

¹²⁷Walker, P. (2020). Boris Johnson: UK can turn tide of Coronavirus in 12 weeks. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/19/boris-johnson-uk-can-turn-tide-of-coronavirus-in-12-weeks>.

status, negative test results, or recovery from COVID-19, facilitating travel within the EU and reopening sectors such as tourism and hospitality (European Commission, 2021). The integration of the National Civil Protection Authority within the Ministry of Internal Administration in September 2021 was a change in the allocation of responsibilities for crisis management, seen as a move to strengthen the government's response to crises (Government of Portugal, 2021). However, challenges in securing personal protective equipment and testing kits, as well as concerns about the capacity of the healthcare system to handle a surge in cases, remained (Our World in Data, 2022). In **England**, the government did not implement the formerly mentioned Civil Contingencies Act. Instead, the Coronavirus Act 2020 was used.¹²⁸ In **Wales**, changes in crisis responses included new ways to pre-empt different virus variants and vaccine hesitancy to consider where and how vaccine fatigue would occur and in what kind of communities. A senior policymaker interviewed explained the following:

“So we have the UK health security agency that tracks global trends. (...) So they may look at variants circulating in some of the countries with surveillance mechanisms. Obviously, you'd be sure of countries with advanced surveillance systems. So looking at what was coming over the hill, in terms of variants is really important. I think another thing is social insight work with your populations back home. So that you know that perhaps this vaccine fatigue or perhaps, you know, the antivaxx movement is affecting certain parts of the population more than others. You might find that, you know, parents are actually put off from it. If a parent has become very anti in their stance to vaccination themselves. And, you know, we do see it sometimes with certain groups of people. So certain groups of people who are more anti-establishment. So they made to say that perfectly great educational system, the Steiner Schools, very creative, very artistic, very led by the child. (...) So, mistrust of government and systems and poor experience, maybe as well. And then, you know, you will find that, you know, some communities will have much lower levels of uptake. (...) And they tend to be intelligent people, you know, so they've read a lot, but they can read a lot of misinformation as well. And so what we're worried about as well is whether an anti-vaccine sentiment would spill over into people denying their baby say, diphtheria, tetanus, polio injections.”

Whilst the senior pandemic policymaker did say that they looked for new variants, the advice did not necessarily change accordingly; the 2-meter distance remained at the same reach, even though the Delta variant was clearly more infectious, which would perhaps have warranted 3 meters distance. At the time of the interview, Omicron had not yet emerged. As can be noted in the statement, there is concern that this intelligent parent group that did not want the vaccine would also change their mind about other infectious diseases. Elsewhere in the interview, the interviewee mentions measles having returned to Wales, likely because of these parent groups. As such, they “kept tabs” on these groups to address them specifically if a group was found to underperform in the stats.

In **Belgium**, and specifically two years into the pandemic, the so-called ‘federal phase’ of governance of the COVID-19 pandemic in Belgium finished in March 2022. This meant that regional authorities, governors, and local administrations are now legally in charge again of managing the pandemic (Nationaal Crisiscentrum, 2022). As in many other countries, the Belgian government had to perform a balancing act between protecting public health and protecting economic interests. The Belgian

¹²⁸<https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/2459/documents/24384/default/>.

economy experienced significant decreases in turnover across various sectors, but signs of recovery have emerged (FOD Economie, 2022). Job losses were relatively low, and positive trends were observed in the employment situation (ibid).

In **Spain**, it was noted that during the first stages of the pandemic (T0 and T1), the responses to deal with the pandemic focused on protecting health and life, and deploying responses to replace wages for citizens that were not able to go to work. Workers and the elderly were the main target population, and members of society who received the most relevant attention and economic effort. During the second stages of the pandemic (mainly T2), there was a multiplication of targeted groups.

In **Italy**, the main changes in crisis response concerned the introduction of measures such as suspensions, extensions, and postponements of payments for companies and professionals; cancellation and reduction of taxes; incentives and grants; and support for capitalisation. Other important measures released by the Government concerned the empowerment of digitization.

Generally speaking, similarities in terms of barriers and problems that occurred across all the COVINFORM countries is the occurrence of anti-lockdown and anti-vaccination protests.

Economic and social welfare responses to COVID-19

With a focus on the T1 phase, all COVINFORM countries, besides Sweden, introduced the implementation of lockdowns and social distancing. Furthermore, in Austria, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, England, and Wales, public spaces were closed. Finally, in Austria, Italy, Portugal, Spain, England, Wales, Greece, and Sweden, there were travel bans. To view the additional social measures introduced in each of the countries, please refer to the annex where all SES frameworks have been incorporated.

From an economic perspective, a range of different economic measures were introduced across the COVINFORM countries. In **Austria**, the country implemented the COVID-19 Crisis management fund (various funds for different areas), Gesetzliche Budgetprovisorium 2020 (Statutory budget provisional), Arbeitsmarktpolitik-Finanzierungsgesetz (Labor Market Financing Act), short-time work, and support for businesses.

In **Greece**, economic measures included the implementation of actions for financially supporting business owners and employees, granting special leave of absence, and providing teleworking for protection of employees. **Italy's** economic measures included governmental economic support, introduction of Moratorium on the payment of corporate debt, liquidity shortages and facilitating access to financing central guarantee funds, measures to support export, internalization and investment by business, support production and supply of medical devices and PPE, suspension of industrial and commercial activities, enhanced transparency in “listed companies” and disclosure requirements, start-ups, state guarantees for newly issued bonds, state aid to facilitate the orderly compulsory administrative liquidation of small banks, participation in European Investment Bank's Pan-European Guarantee Fund and New European Scheme, bolstering of support for innovative start-ups, support from regional and other local authorities, measures pertaining to supporting and relaunching the economy, and extension of grace period for SMEs.

In **Portugal**, economic measures included financial support to companies, namely with loans with state backup, launching of long-term and short-term programs, and boosting of support towards the tourist industry, while also ensuring relevant tourist restrictions are in place. In **Spain**, economic measures included the introduction of economic aid measures, social housing, community assistance, minimum income guarantee programs, food distribution, measures to protect mortgage decisions, and the ERTE

Furlough Scheme. In **England**, examples of economic measures introduced include the Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme ('Furlough'), Self-Employment Income Support Scheme (SEISS), Self-Isolation Payment support, the COVID-19 Statutory Sick Pay Enhancement Scheme, Kickstart Scheme, Restart Scheme, Bounce Back Loan Scheme (BBLs), Waive business rates for hospitality and retain businesses and nurseries, Cash grants for small businesses and firms in retail, Hospitality and Leisure sectors, Local Restrictions Support Grants Scheme, and the Eat out to Help Out scheme. In **Wales**, economic measures included the COVID-19 Non-Domestic Rates (NDR) Grant Scheme, Business Rates Relief, Furlough Scheme, Economic Resilience Fund, support administered by local authorities, and COVID-19 Wales Business Loan Scheme. In Belgium, measures included OCMW (Belgium's public welfare centre) providing financial supporting during the pandemic. In **Sweden**, economic measures were introduced to support affected sectors of society. There were also limitations on business operation, and the elimination of the qualifying day for sick leave. In **Germany**, economic measures included short-time work benefits (Kurzarbeit), support measures for MSMEs and the self-employed, special funding available for cultural institutions, relaxed billing audits for hospitals treating COVID-19 patients, and the provision of financial assistance for nursing and long-term care.

Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing government preparedness and response

In **Spain**, socio-logical factors that influenced government preparedness and response include:

- Population density and radial communications: Spain has a concentrated population in Madrid and along the coast.
- Housing structure: A vast majority of the Spanish population live in flats and apartment buildings.
- Ageing population
- Elderly care and protection systems for ageing population that need to be improved.
- A familiar welfare state, which implies high interactions between grandparents, parents and children.
- International tourism, which implies an intense movement of people from different parts of the world
- Cultural aspects, e.g., social interactions

Politically, a modest parliamentary majority to support the first coalition government of Spanish democracy, a fragmented parliament, intense polarisation, with an opposition that used this issue to attack the government and the model of governance, which is decentralised, caused discoordination between regional, central, and local governments that provoked a delay in some responses.

In **Portugal**, the socio-political, legal, and ethical factors that influenced the government's preparedness and response to the pandemic include the country's decentralised healthcare system, which allowed for greater flexibility in decision-making at the local level. The strong sense of community and solidarity among the Portuguese people also contributed to compliance with the restrictions and measures implemented by the government (DGS, 2020). Additionally, the government had to balance the need to protect public health with the need to maintain the tourism industry's viability, which was a delicate and difficult balance to achieve (Governo de Portugal, 2020). The legal framework in Portugal, which includes a constitution that guarantees citizens' rights and freedoms, also played a role in the government's response (ibid) since it had to balance the need to protect public health with the need to respect citizens' rights, such as the freedom of movement and the right to

work (ibid). In sum, the Portuguese government's response to COVID-19 pandemic was a complex and multifaceted effort, influenced by various socio-political, legal and ethical factors (DGS, 2020).

In **Italy**, the factors that influenced the policy choices stemmed from the need to contain the spread of the virus and reduce hospitalizations. Initially, the delayed response to the pandemic brought the entire health care system to a standstill: doctors and health care personnel were untrained and lacked protective devices; civil society was afraid of being infected. Subsequently, when the situation came back under control, the government began working toward reopening, both because civil society was showing weariness with the lockdowns and to also boost the country's economy. Despite scepticism, the desire to resume normal life and some restrictions imposed by government prompted many people to get the COVID-19 vaccination. The number of hospitalizations rather than the number of people infected guided the government's choices about the re-openings.

In **Greece**, expert interviews touched on socio-political and legal factors. It was realised that COVID-19 was an unprecedented challenge, thus the need to tailor both governmental response, legal framework and executive, administrative bodies was underlined. This proactive modus operandi, according to the expert interviews, would also be a main indicator of the successful response towards COVID-19 in Greece, particularly during the first phase, despite healthcare system capacity and capability challenges, which was also likely negatively impacted by the prolonged financial crisis. In addition, due to the unknown nature of COVID-19 and the negative impact of the pandemic, widespread fear prevailed among the general population, which may have contributed on measure compliance rates. From a socio-political and ethical standpoint, the Greek governmental mechanism and response was guided based on the recommendations and expert advice of highly qualified healthcare professionals such as renown epidemiologists, particularly in relation to the implementation of non-pharmaceutical interventions such as social isolation.

In **Wales**, it was noted that the country differed from England on socio-political and economic terms. As an interviewee explained:

“What’s interesting about Wales compared to England, is that the demography of Wales is essentially – you look at the numbers – of an older, sicker, poorer population. And so therefore, other things being equal, you just thought that the death rate would be higher. But the last rates I heard – and you do need to confirm and check these rates – were that the death rates over the five-year average in Wales was 13%, over the five-year average, and in England, it was 20% over. And that is a sort of testimony to the more cautious approach Wales took and specifically, we’re talking about years, the legislation for two-meter social distancing as opposed to the guidance of one-meter social distancing.”

The MP's statement thus suggests how the Welsh Government took population-level statistics into account about how to adopt the pandemic mitigation recommendations from the WHO.

In **Belgium**, legal factors shaped the government response. Measures affecting fundamental rights were implemented through a ministerial decree based on the 2007 Civil Security Act, designed for acute emergencies but not long-term health crises (Verbergt, 2020b). The caretaker administration in Belgium was granted special powers to address the pandemic's impact (Rankin, 2020). Economic considerations further complicate decision-making. The Economic Risk Management Group plays a role in monitoring the impact, ensuring business continuity, and coordinating measures to mitigate economic consequences (NBB, 2020).

In **Austria**, social factors which may have influenced the course of the pandemic are predominantly cultural factors such as a relatively low level of intergenerational contact and cohabitation. This may have helped to isolate elderly vulnerable groups.¹²⁹ Additionally, a high general scepticism of the Austrian society against surveillance and tracking apps due to privacy concerns influenced the low uptake of the ‘Stopp Corona’ App, a contact tracing app.¹³⁰ In terms of legal factors, some aspects of the government’s COVID-19 response came under critique. For example, conducting a review of the government’s ordinances in relation to the COVID-19 management the Constitutional Court, it came to the verdict that some of the government’s ordinances banning visits to private households during the first lockdown were unconstitutional. The most prominent case took place on the 22nd of July 2020, when the Austrian Constitutional Court decided that some of the COVID-19 orders issued during the first wave violated the Austrian constitution. Orders affected were, for example, the general social restrictions in the months of March and April as well as fines issued in relation to breaking these social restrictions. There was no legal base for such far reaching rules. The Health Ministry was legally only allowed to issue such restrictions for particular places rather than imposing general social restrictions.¹³¹ This ruling influenced the government’s response during the second and third wave. For example, the verdict led to an amendment and in some parts clarification of the COVID-19 policy law (COVID-19 Maßnahmen Gesetz) in September 2020.¹³²

With a focus on ethical factors, in **England**, it was acknowledged that the right to life (Article 2 European convention on Human Rights (ECHR)) has been, and must remain, central to the Government’s response to COVID-19.¹³³

In **Germany**, the German government did not publicly identify the factors or indicators on which specific decisions were based, aside from 7-day COVID-19 incidence rate. However, official evaluations and studies offer insight. Some factors that likely influenced and/or constrained government preparedness and response included:

- Socio-political: the University of Erfurt COSMO COVID-19 Snapshot Monitoring study indicates that during the initial phase of the pandemic, the public expressed relatively high initial trust in public health institutions and government among, along with relatively high acceptance of the measures adopted (Universität Erfurt et al., 2022).
- Legal: the BMG assesses the 2001 Protection against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG) as “designed entirely for outbreaks of a rather local nature and of quite limited duration. It was therefore a formidable challenge to base virtually all (area-wide and covering the entire population) measures to combat the long-lasting Corona pandemic on this law.

¹²⁹ Desson, Z., Lambertz, L., Peters, J., Falkenback, M., & L. Kauer (2020) Europe’s Covid-19 outliers: german, Austrian and Swiss policy responses during the early stages of the 2020 pandemic, Health Policy and Technology 9, pp. 405-418.

¹³⁰ https://digigov.univie.ac.at/de/projects/solidarity-in-times-of-a-pandemic-solpan/solpan-blog-deutsch/blog-posts/news/ueberwachungsinstrument-oder-heilsbringer-warum-werden-contact-tracing-apps-nicht-reger-genutzt-e/?tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&cHash=e8b484d72a350b65d841528457344838.

¹³¹ https://www.diepresse.com/5842782/hochstrichter-corona-ausgehregeln-waren-gesetzeswidrig?utm_medium=Social&utm_source=Facebook&xtor=CS1-15#Echobox=1595405240.

¹³² https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2020_I_104/BGBLA_2020_I_104.pdfsig.

¹³³ <https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/2649/documents/26914/default/>.

Policymakers have attempted to accomplish this task primarily through numerous, not always fortunate, amendments and additions to the IfSG, with little evidence of a consistent overall approach. Rather, the IfSG has meanwhile developed into a rather confusing and unsystematic web of regulations” (BMG 2022, pg. 103). This constraint led to significant confusion when it came to communication of changing measures and the rationale behind them, which eventually fed back in the form of decreasing public acceptance.

- Ethical: the 2017 National Pandemic Plan assumes an ethical obligation to protect medically vulnerable population groups as a core element in pandemic management; the general population were accordingly expected to sacrifice certain rights and freedoms in order to enable authorities to fulfil this obligation.

Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors if they are relevant to the changes that occurred

This question has applied to the following countries: In **Spain**, it was acknowledged that during the first stages of the pandemic (T0 and T1), the responses to deal with COVID-19 focused on protecting health and life, and on deploying responses to replace wages for citizens that were not able to go to work. Workers and the elderly were the main target population, and the ones who received the most relevant attention and economic effort. During the second stages of the pandemic (mainly T2), there was a multiplication of targeted groups.

In **Greece**, expert interviews identified that in order to fortify the healthcare system and address social needs, there would be a requirement to hire additional healthcare experts. Interviewees identified that approximately 2,500 experts were employed, whereas due to the lack of specialised manpower, healthcare experts in key positions would be assigned with additional administrative duties, which would add pressure on their daily lives. Moreover, a significant number of legislative acts and ministerial decisions emerged on a weekly basis, which would regulate business and educational facilities operation, as well as other spheres of governmental responses such as the management of migration.

Governmental responses were influenced by the status quo of the healthcare system and the degree of negative impacts that the prolonged financial crisis had on society as well as the capacity and capabilities of the healthcare system. Moreover, despite apparent legal, socio-political and ethical considerations, governmental responses were guided mainly by the national scientific committee of healthcare experts, who would also take into account that non-pharmaceutical interventions such as social isolation might be ethically and legally challenging. Nonetheless, the government provided recommendations based on their expert knowledge, international guidelines and standards as well as prioritizing the objective of maintaining good health standards of the general population on average. According to expert interviews, healthcare experts indicated that the management of the pandemic was assessed to be satisfactory, while highlighting that the employment of healthcare personnel was crucial to the effectiveness of the healthcare system. Moreover, at a later stage, specifically in September 2020, the government response mechanism created a new tool which would assist with crisis management. The epidemiological map was introduced which incorporated a multi-level classification of the COVID-19 health-related hazard threat. This system would classify municipalities and local communities in accordance with the infection fluctuation rates and particular local characteristics such as human density, age groups, vaccination rates, emergence of variants and healthcare system capacity, displaying each target area with a colour which would indicate the severity of infections. Additionally, experts underline the dual role of the General Secretariat of Civil Protection

in crisis management, which was the creation of contemporary facilities which engage with the general public. This did not exist prior to the pandemic. With this in mind, responses were tailored based on the holistic approach in strategic planning, that drew data from status quo healthcare characteristics in each area. This approach would lead to the generation of measures that would be adopted by both private and public stakeholders.

In **Portugal**, socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influenced crisis response. The country's decentralised healthcare system allowed for greater flexibility in decision-making at the local level, allowing for a shift towards a more localised approach to crisis management. Measures to apply at the local level were established, considering the incidence, and it is determined that in the case of low-density territories, twice the values applied for the rest of the country are considered as reference values for the incidence. This way, having restrictions targeted to areas with higher incidence rates rather than nationwide measures (Observador, 2022) was one of the main changes in crisis response. Additionally, the fact that the two autonomous regions have regional health authorities and autonomy lead to different evolutions and responses to the pandemic. For example, even though both regions follow the states of emergency proclaimed at the national level, while Azores has 5 degrees of risk and different measures for each of them, Madeira does not distinguish between municipalities (even when it had one of the municipalities with higher accumulated incidence in the country) (Observador, 2021). Both Azores and Madeira registered a very low number of cases in the first months of the pandemic, an increase in incidence only around October/November 2020 and then again around January 2021. However, while in Madeira the decrease happened around March, in Azores, there was a decrease earlier, in February, but then a new increase in April 2021 (CNS, 2022). In terms of ethical factors, there was some public debate regarding COVID-19 vaccination (e.g., should vaccines be mandatory or not; should children be vaccinated or not, etc.) associated with the fears felt by the population. However, given the high adherence to COVID-19 vaccination by the Portuguese population, the question of making the vaccines mandatory did not arise and there was no need to discuss it by the government (so it did not influence crisis response) (RTP, 2021).

In **Wales**, ethical considerations are relevant. It was noted that addressing the many unknowns and uncertainties required an ethical view on the situation. A retired top policymaker explained how the different viewpoints of the different ideologies, moral frameworks, and cultural backgrounds that typify Wales were brought together in an ethics panel. The interviewee explained the origin and reasons for this governmental ethics advisory panel:

“So there wasn't the evidence, the evidence developed, and as it as it came forward, you're able to make better and better clinical decisions. (...) So lots of the clinical stuff got thrashed out by the Chief Medical Officers, either in their discrete group, because they would then advise the Health Ministers directly or in this collaborative group that I was involved in. And then, you know, it would be cascaded within the country. But in Wales, we had some particular concerns about how come more Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic workers were dying? And should we be doing something to protect them, and often, people from that background in society are in lower paid jobs which have higher contact. We were concerned about Do Not Resuscitate orders. (...) So the Minister agreed that we set up a particular panel, it was chaired by one of the doctors within the Welsh Government. And they pulled in experts from outside, so that there was a proper debate. I did not sit on that committee, I've merely sort of was asked questions to feed into it. (...) So you actually had a group of people you could go to, with ethical and moral dilemmas

and issues. And it was from their group, that they developed a tool to actually help with the safety of workers. So the evidence, which was showing that if you had certain factors, so if you came from a Black or Asian background, you were overweight, you were male, you're an older age, you had heart disease or something, you can rank it and put a scoring on a chart, and it said, if you got to a certain level, you should not be having close contact with people with COVID, you should actually be moved to a different type of working environment."

Similar to Greece, Wales also had a tool to help manage the COVID-19 virus. The tool provides a calculation of a combination of the characteristics of people's bodies (age, disease presence, etc) and their job (working with others present, possibility to keep a distance from others, possibility to work from home, etc). It had thresholds that related to the need to protect workers. As such, this ethical advisory panel was successful in bringing in new connections between the population and clinical information that could be used to differentiate the pandemic responses for different social groups in Welsh society.

Key Findings

The key takeaways in terms of findings for this report include the following:

- General pandemic planning documents to deal with health emergencies were not adequate to allow flexibility, provide direction or translate to unknown crisis.
- All COVINFORM countries responded promptly to put in place measures that would help curb the initial wave of the COVID-19 virus. Sweden, England, and Wales were noted as countries that were relaxed in their response measures to the virus. Wales, for example, only ever did one "firebreak lockdown" and England, despite adopting the 'herd immunity' approach, eventually followed the example of other COVINFORM countries in terms of curbing the spread of COVID-19 (e.g., implementation of lockdowns);
- When reflecting on the COVID-19 pandemic, some of the interviewee commentary critiqued COVID-19 management. Critique mainly centred around governance systems in terms of responding to the COVID-19 pandemic, non-pharmaceutical interventions such as lockdowns, and the wearing of face masks, difficulties reaching hard-to-reach groups, the way COVID-19 communication was communicated, vaccination rollout, and the use of technology, e.g., transitioning from face-to-face to virtual interactions.
- Across the COVINFORM countries, crisis management focused on introducing necessary measures and policies to curb the spread of the COVID-19 virus. This included the introduction of new COVID-19 Laws, implementation of Test and Trace, creation of applications, creation of COVID-19 vaccine certificates, new committees, hiring of more staff, implementation of state of calamities, state of alarms, state of emergencies, new taskforces, new ministers, creation of passes to access business and services, execution of lockdowns, government interventions to address misinformation, and mandatory COVID-19 testing in workplaces.
- All countries recognised that the COVID-19 pandemic would affect acknowledged vulnerable groups in their respective countries. Addressing existing and new vulnerabilities was not ignored, and necessary support measures were put in place to help address the specific needs that vulnerable groups required to get through the pandemic. COVID-19 measures such as lockdowns contributed towards heightened loneliness. Measures such as lockdowns

also put victims of domestic abuse, homelessness, and those with disabilities in precarious situations.

- COVID-19 measures introduced created new vulnerabilities. Examples include heightened loneliness, deterioration of mental health, negative effects on education attainment/educational inequalities, poverty, food insecurity, financial difficulties, and overcrowding.

Public reactions to the crisis management and its changes

Across all the COVINFORM countries, the following public reactions are relevant:

- Emergence of anti-lockdown and anti-vaccination protests. In Sweden, this was limited. Protests mainly came from restaurant businesses and sports-/entertainment business against restrictions. Wales also had limited protests.
- Declining levels of governmental trust
- General acceptance of measures
- High trust in authorities
- Critique against visiting bans in elderly homes
- Debate about some groups (especially younger people) not following recommendations
- People becoming more susceptible to misinformation
- Disputes around those who should be working from home and be on site for work
- Protests against mandatory protests
- Formation of anti-vaccination parties

Conclusion

In summary, this report has presented an update of the different dimensions of government response to the COVID-19 pandemic across all the COVINFORM countries under study. The report extracted information from previous deliverables D4.1 and D4.5, and expert interviews conducted with experts and stakeholders up until May 2023. The report highlighted similarities in terms of pandemic preparedness and planning, vulnerabilities identified, COVID-19 responses, economic and social welfare responses, and socio-political, legal, and ethical factors that might have played a role in government preparedness and response. All the dimensions touched upon covered three different phases of the pandemic and they are: (1) pre-COVID-19, 2) the start of COVID-19 up until vaccination, and 3) the emergence of the Omicron variant and onwards. Some key findings relating to the dimensions covered include the following: (1) Different phases of the pandemic (i.e., T0, T1, and T2) saw changes in terms of which groups in society were considered to be vulnerable, (2) most countries did see the evolution of their crisis response as the COVID-19 pandemic progressed and (3) Economics measures introduced were crucial to helping those severely impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic financially.

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Annex 1

D4.7 Standardised Questionnaire

2.1.1. Baseline conditions government prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T0 general population)

How is your government/the public health system/the civil society ecosystem/the crisis communication structured (We want to know the structure: who is responsible, what kind of resources are available, ...)?

How was the response in your country planned (we are looking for documents on how to deal with pandemic/crisis pre COVID)?

2.1.2. Changes and other developments throughout the COVID-19 pandemic (based on T1 and T2 general population)

How was the crisis management implemented at the beginning of the pandemic? (What happened when the pandemic hit? How did the government/ people in charge/authorities responsible for crisis management react? What documents did they follow? Who held the responsibility?) Please, also add relevant socio-political, legal, and ethical factors in your country that influenced government preparedness and response

What were barriers to implementation of what was planned?

How did these (referring to question 1-2) change over time (2 points in time: 1.) COVID-19 beginning and first lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures, 2.) Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022)

What changes in crisis response occurred and why? (We are looking for barriers, problems, structural change/change of responsibilities, occurrence of multiple crisis, positive developments, solutions that made measures obsolete, (lack of) support of measures, content with government) (here also add insights from the Expert interviews) Please, here too, mention Socio-political, legal, and ethical factors if they are relevant to the changes that occurred.

Reflections on pandemic management taking changes into consideration

Highlight issues or successes and talk about reflections based on the expert interview

How did the public react to the crisis management and its changes? (Describe important social outcomes of the pandemic situation if data available)

2.1.3. Conditions for vulnerable groups within the governmental crisis management

What vulnerabilities were acknowledged and addressed by the government/the public health system/civil society organisations/in crisis communication in the beginning of the pandemic? How did this change over time (over T1 and T2), were there new vulnerable groups defined and acknowledged in the course of the pandemic?

How was the response in relation to vulnerable groups implemented at the beginning of the pandemic? How were vulnerable groups supported? How did it change over time, especially if new vulnerable groups were acknowledged?

Describe briefly how did measures affect vulnerable groups or created new vulnerabilities? (e.g., lockdown affected domestic violence victims, people living in overcrowded conditions, chronically ill people, ageing people living alone etc.).

Annex 2

The Ostrom model consists of five sub-systems below which we have operationalised as follows:

Resource Systems and Units (RSU) – describes the resources available to in a country and to manage a (health) crisis

Governance Systems (GS) – describes the basic structure of how a country is governed in relation to a (health) crisis

Actor System (AS) – describes who is responsible for (health) crisis management in a country

Outcomes (O) – describe the impact of the governmental crisis response

Interaction Area (I) – describes the interaction between the RSU and the GS. In this concrete case it mostly describes measures taken to manage the health crisis (e.g., lockdowns, etc.).

Austria

Model TO

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:
 - all sectors Lockdown
 - Social sphere
 - COVID-19-Maßnahmengesetz
 - Execution of lockdowns and social distancing
 - Closing of public spaces
 - Travel bans
 - Health sphere
 - COVID-19-Maßnahmengesetz (COVID-19 Measure Law)
 - Increase resources for health sector fighting COVID-19
 - Spending for hospitals
 - Testing infrastructure (free)
 - Vaccination (free)
 - Economic sphere
 - COVID-19-Crisis management fund (various funds for different areas)
 - Gesetzliche Budgetprovisorium 2020 (Statutory budget provisional)
 - Arbeitsmarktpolitik-Finanzierungsgesetz (Labor Market Financing Act)
 - Short-time work
 - Support for businesses

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?
- Epidemic Law
- Several COVID-19 laws new ones
- Health Ministry on base of Epidemic Law with ordinances
- Other ministers
- SKKM came into action as nation wide crisis coordinator
- COVID-Taskforces new
- COVID-19 law (base for lockdowns, social distancing) new
- Novelle des COVID-19 to fix mistakes
- Corona Commission
- Execution of not following measures such as lockdown
- Measures
 - Lockdowns
 - Social distancing
 - Mask wearing
 - Testing

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?
- No relevant data is available
- Changes to preparedness plans , jurisdiction ?
 - Covid-19 Law
 - Ordinances
 - The COVID-19 Pandemic: Stocktaking and Framework for Action
 - Who held the responsibility?
 - Health ministry
 - SKKM
 - Interior ministry
 - Chancellery
 - Finance ministry
 - Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government
 - Younger people with chronic disease, pregnant women, older people in general

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
 - Rudolf Anschober, Health Minister
 - Sebastian Kurz, Chancellor
 - Alexander Schallenberg, Chancellor
 - Karl Nehammer, Chancellor
 - Gerhard Karner, Interior Minister
 - Magnus Brunner, I
 - ORF
- Who/what were the expert sources?
 - WHO
 - National experts from different fields
 - COVID Taskforces
 - Vaccination Board
 - Corona Commission
 - Health professionals (mental and physical)
 - Austrian Red Cross
 - AGES
- Who are the main target populations?
 - General population
 - Elderly
 - People with chronic illness and comorbidities

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)
 - Migration index (% migrant population)
 - Age index, gender - % female
 - Trust in government
 - Housing concentration
 - GDP
 - Unemployment rates
 - Poverty index
- How did the population react?
 - Protests against the government from people against the measures and vaccination
 - Anti-vaccination party was found

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
In Austria this would be November 2021

Model T2

Germany

Model T0

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- [What kind of resources were in different sectors of the country?](#)
- Social/social welfare sphere: federal social insurance system covering many of the below domains (e.g., health, economic)
- Health sphere: federal statutory public health insurance system, supplemented with optional private instance; long-term care insurance system
- Economic sphere: federal unemployment system insurance and pension/social security system; federal means-tested benefits system for those with special economic needs, including income support, housing support, child benefits
- Legal sphere: with regard to criminal cases, free public defense representation for low-income individuals; with regard to all cases, federal legal consultation assistance, procedural cost assistance, and legal fee reductions for low-income individuals; voluntary private legal expense insurance

[Please write a short paragraph about the most important facts about your country's governance.](#)

Germany is a federal parliamentary democracy, with distinct legislative, executive, and judicial branches. The national parliament (Bundestag) is responsible for electing a Federal Chancellor, who proposes a cabinet comprising the federal executive branch (*Regierung* or "Government"). Germany is comprised of 16 states, which enjoy significant administrative autonomy. Generally, the states are responsible for internal security, education policy, and cultural policy, as well as infrastructure and day-to-day administration. State governmental structures generally mirror the federal structure. Governmental structures vary slightly on the municipal level as well, but general adhere to certain patterns (e.g., a mayor and municipal council system).

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic: up until January 2020

Interaction Area (I)

No relevant data is available

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (from WP2):
 - Migration index (% migrant population)
 - Age index, gender - % female
 - Trust in government
 - Housing concentration
 - GDP
 - Unemployment rates
 - Poverty index

[For more information, look at the COVINFORM Dashboard](#)

Governance Systems (GS)

- [How is the government structured?](#)
- Federal Parliamentary Democracy. Executive branch comprising Federal President, Federal Chancellor, and Cabinet; executive decisions are made by Head of Government and Cabinet. Legislative Power – National Parliament (Bundestag) and Federal Council (Bundesrat).
- 16 German states = administrative autonomy
- Who is responsible for the management of a health crisis?
- Ministry of Health / Ministry of the Interior Crisis Task Force (BMG/BMI Kristenstab) and RKI intensively monitor the situation and advises the federal government, which issues baseline regulations and recommendations
- Most measures are interpreted and implemented by the 16 states.
- [What preparedness plans & legislation already existed?](#)
- 2001 Protection Against Infection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz – IfSG)
- 2017 National Pandemic Plan (Pandemieplan)
- Other laws and guidelines
- 2015 Crisis Management Strategy: procedure for establishing a crisis task force (Kristenstab)
- Vaccination guidelines periodically issued by the Robert Koch Institute Standing Committee on Vaccination (Ständige Impfkommission am Robert-Koch-Institut, STIKO)
- State of Emergency not declared; rather, Protection Against Infection Act invoked and amended as needed
- [What were the general vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government?](#)
- With regard to pandemics in specific, the National Pandemic Plan establishes that anti-pandemic measures, including risk communication measures, should account for certain "at-risk [population] groups" (Risikogruppen). However, it delegates the definition of at-risk groups to the STIKO.
- With regard to other social factors, German social welfare policy implicitly acknowledges a wide range of health and socioeconomic vulnerabilities – however, these are not directly addressed in the Pandemic Plan.

Actor Systems (A)

- [Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?](#)
- Federal President (Head of State); Federal Chancellor (Head of Government – primary executive)
- Federal cabinet and federal ministries, esp. Federal Ministry of Health (BMG), Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI)
- Robert Koch Institute (RKI), esp. RKI Standing Commission on Vaccines (STIKO); Paul Ehrlich Institute
- Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Response (BBK); Federal Agency for Technical Relief (THW); Joint Reporting and Situation Center (GMLZ)
- State executive branches and ministries of health and interior affairs
- [Who/what were the expert sources?](#)
- Not applicable (interviews conducted during T1 & T2)
- [Who are the main target populations?](#)
- General population
- "At-risk groups" as defined by STIKO

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Social Sphere

- Border controls imposed
- Modification of pre-existing acts and codes to improve lab testing and (influenza) vaccination processes

Health Sphere

- Free testing
- Vaccines as of January 2021

Economic Sphere

- Short-time work benefits (Kurzarbeit)
- Support measures for MSMEs and the self-employed
- Special funding available for cultural institutions
- Relaxed billing audits for hospitals treating COVID-19 patients
- Provided financial assistance for nursing and long-term care
- Expansion of 1st and 3rd act

Legal Sphere

- Covering costs of European nationals
- Offered recognition to the role of culture and the arts

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?
- Federal lockdown 1: from 16 March until 19 April; restrictive measures continue to be adopted flexibly on state-by-state level in Q2, Q3, Q4
- Federal lockdown 2: from 2 November until 19 December, then extended on state level through early January 2021
- Adoption of three Acts on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance (see Governance Systems)
- Adoption of policies to protect children in need and see continuation of their education
- Provisions to strengthen the healthcare workers (Hospital Future Act)
- Weekly COVID-19 tests mandatory in workplaces
- Free Corona "citizen tests" re-introduced

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)
- How did the population react?
- COVID-19 protests against lockdowns imposed by government
- New anti-vaccination group formed called The Querdenken movement.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?
- February 2020: Joint BMG/BMI crisis task force created
- Changes to preparedness plans, jurisdiction, legislation, etc.?
- 04 March 2020: RKI publishes supplement to National Pandemic Plan
- 28 March 2020: First Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance
- 14 May 2020: Second Act for the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance
- 18 November 2020: Third Act on the Protection of the Population in the Event of an Epidemic Situation of National Importance
- 16 December 2020: German Recovery and Resilience Plan (Deutscher Aufbau- und Resilienzplan, DARP)
- Who held the responsibility?
- Existing state institutions plus BMI/BMG crisis task force (Krisenstab BMI/BMG)
- Many regulations were interpreted and implemented on the state, rather than federal level
- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

Health perspective

- Elderly and those with pre-existing medical conditions / disabilities

Intersecting health and social perspective

- Healthcare workers
- Residents in collective accommodations
- Low-wage and temporary-contract workers

Economic perspective

- Economically vulnerable workers (e.g., self-employed, cultural workers)

Social perspective

- Those experiencing domestic violence and negative psychological effects

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/who are the key professionals?
- Feb 2020: Joint BMI/BMG crisis task force (Krisenstab BMI/BMG)
- Otherwise, as before pandemic: relevant ministers; RKI, esp. STIKO; PEI; BBK, THW, GMLZ
- Who/what were the expert sources?
- Due to reluctance to discuss pandemic management among representatives of governmental organisations in Germany, it was not possible to conduct interviews in T1. All interviews were conducted in T2, after the topic had become less controversial.
- Who are the main target populations?
- General population
- "At-risk groups" as defined by STIKO: primary focus in T1 remains on health vulnerabilities

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures

- In Germany, January 2020 until January 2021

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Health Sphere

- Vaccines
- Mobile air purification devices purchased
- Restrictive measures re-introduced
- Communication aid app "aidminutes.rescue" added vaccination mode
- Exemption from COVID-19 Protective Restrictions was granted to vaccinated and recovered persons
- Booster Vaccines

Economic Sphere

- Continuation and gradual phasing-out of economic support measures

Legal/Jurisdictional Sphere

- Exemption from social distancing for vaccinated/recovered (2G) or vaccinated/recovered/tested (3G)

World events affecting environment of countries

- Fourth wave of COVID-19 underway
- Refugee crisis from Ukraine war

Interaction Area (I)

- Changes in response implementation? (measures)
- Implementation of protection measures
- Compulsory testing for nursing homes
- Increasing pace of secondary booster vaccination
- Corona supplements continued to be paid
- Short-time allowances extended into 2022
- Changes in people in charge reaction?
- Shift from lockdowns to vaccination
- Shift from general lockdowns to targeted containment measures (testing, tracing, and quarantine; exemption from social distancing for vaccinated/recovered/tested [2G/3G]).
- Recognition of need to balance health protection with protection of other quality-of-life factors
- Recognition of seriousness of non-health vulnerabilities
- Changes in crisis management
- Incorporation of more interdisciplinary perspectives via the Coronavirus Expert Council of the Federal Government and the Committee of Experts

Outcomes (O)

- Changes in country status/ indicators:
- What barriers, problems were encountered?
- Ongoing protests
- Continuing spread of misinformation
- Aggravated social consequences of COVID-19 for marginalized migrant groups in Germany
- Expert knowledge about appropriate forms of risk communication not fully utilized and scientific uncertainties not addressed openly
- Absolute number not always put in relation to the reference population

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government structure?
- November 2021: Change of government following federal parliamentary election held on 26 September.
- Changes to preparedness plans, legislation, etc.?
- 30 January 2021: Corona Quarantine Ordinance (Corona-Quarantäneverordnung)
- 30 June 2022: BMG publishes comprehensive report *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies*, which included a critique of the implementation of the National Pandemic Plan.
- Changes to responsibility?
- December 2021: An interdisciplinary Coronavirus Expert Council of the Federal Government (Corona ExpertInnenrat der Bundesregierung) was convened to issue guidelines on rotating topics
- 2022: A Committee of Experts (Sachverständigenausschuss) was convened to comprehensively evaluate responses in accordance with § 5 Paragraph 9 of the Protection Against Infection Act (IfSG); half of the experts were appointed by the Federal Government and half by the national parliament (Bundestag). The Committee drafted the *Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies* (see above)
- Changes in vulnerabilities
- New focus on:
 - Unvaccinated elderly
 - Children and the youth
 - Socially and economically vulnerable groups
 - Persons under the poverty line (less than 60% of median income)
 - Persons with low socio-economic status
 - Refugees and other migrants (including labour migrants)
 - Homeless/houseless people
- The *Evaluation* criticised communications toward vulnerable groups as insufficiently well-targeted and too one-sided (i.e., not based on dialogue with vulnerable persons themselves)

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
- As in T1: relevant ministers; RKI, esp. STIKO; PEI; BBK, THW, GMLZ
- However, note change of government
 - November 2021: new government: SPD, Greens, FDP coalition, led by Chancellor Olaf Scholz
 - New Health Minister: epidemiologist Karl Lauterbach
- Who/what were the expert sources?
- R1: senior civil servant in social welfare department on Mannheim municipal level; R2: senior civil servant responsible for COVID-19 management on Baden-Württemberg state level; R3: senior civil servant responsible for integration policy on Mannheim municipal level; R4: leader of neighbourhood management association in a vulnerable neighbourhood in Mannheim; R5: ministerial communications official on Baden-Württemberg state level; R6: communications official on Mannheim municipal level
- Changes in main target populations?
- January 2021 STIKO "Decision of the STIKO on the 1st update of the COVID-19 vaccination recommendation" broadens range of "at-risk groups" to include intersecting health and social vulnerability
- June 2022 BMG "Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies" improves focus on those living under the poverty line (less than 60% of median income), low socio-economic status persons, refugees and other migrants (including labour migrants), and homeless/houseless people, and children/youth

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown

T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022 (or earlier depending on data collection for iteration)

Portugal

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

Social/Social Welfare Sphere: existence of hundreds of social non-profit organizations that, with the help of the state, provide social and health support.
 Health Sphere: Public National Health System and private health units/
 One of the trademarks of Portugal's political organisation is the independent bodies, authorities, in terms of Health (DGS), economic activity (ASAE), civil protection, etc. This sometimes introduces tension, particularly in the extended crisis situations since the active policies and rules have to be articulated between the authority and the government. Furthermore in normal situations those authorities give technical details and provide analysis that are easily controlled, with objections limited to experts and without low resonance in public opinion.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Up until January 2020

Interaction Area (I)

Implementation of rules, regulations and measures, on a nationwide scale and UE

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (from WP2):
 - Migration index (% migrant population): 2019 - 8.6%; 2020 - 9.1%; 2021 - 9.4%
 - Age index: 2019 - 129.8, %; 2020 - 132.1%; 2021 - 134.1%
 - Gender % female- 2019 - 51.6%; 2020: -2020 female - 51.7%;, 2021% female - 51.8%
 - Trust in government: 2019: ; 2020 (26% expressed high or very high trust in the national government) (Eurobarometer survey, 2020) ; 29% of respondents expressed high or very high trust in the national government (Eurobarometer survey, 2021)
 - Housing concentration
 - GDP: 2019 - €212.5 billion; 2020 - €195.1 billion; 2021 - €208.8 billion (Eurostat)
 - Unemployment rates: 2019 - 6.5%; 2020 - 6.9%; 2021 - 6.4% (INE)
 - Gini coefficient 2018 - 31.9%; 2019 - 31.9%; 2020 - 33.0% ; 2021 -32%; 2022: Data not yet available (Source: INE)
- Poverty index:
 - After social transfers - - 2019- 16,2 %%; 2020- 18.4%; 2021 - 16.4%
 - Before social transfers - 2019- 43,5 %; 2020- 43,5%; 2021 - 7% (Source: INE)
 - crime rate: 2019 - 32,3% ; 2020: 28,7%; 2021 - 28,9%; 2022 - 33%
 - Inflation rate:2019-0,3%;

Governance Systems (GS)

- How is the government structured?

Semi-presidential democratic republic, where the government have the executive power and with 2 autonomous regions (Madeira and Azores).
 Main legislative body is the Assembly of the Republic
 Government, council of ministers, 5 regional technical bodies, municipalities and several independent powers like the judicial, the health (DGS) etc.

- Who is responsible for the management of a health crisis?
 The DGS (Directorate-General of Health) it's a national public health agency, It is an independent agency that is described as the National Health Authority, this agency is the one that has autonomy to declare a pandemic state.
 The prime minister, the Health Minister and the Civil Protection.

- What preparedness plans & legislation already existed?

Flu pandemic plan
 General National Emergency Plan

- What were the general vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government?

- Imigrants
- Domestic violence victims
- Older adults living alone
- Homeless

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

President head of state
 Prime Minister Head of Government - Antonio Costa
 Health minister: Marta Temido
 DGS director : Graça Freitas

- Who/what were the expert sources?
- DGS and the National school of public health
- Who are the main target populations?

General Population and people with specific ailments that brings differential probability of death or recurrence use of the Health system (before covid-19)

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

All sectors lockdown

Social Sphere

- Restriction of movements
- Curfews
- Travel Bans
- Retail and Leisure businesses suspended
- Work and studying from home enforced during lockdown, except core services like production and distribution
- Ban on circulation between municipalities on weekend March 20th and 21th 2021 and during Easter (between March 26th 2021 and April 5th 2021).
- Suspension of air traffic

Health Sphere

Support of all necessary health-related personnel.

Economic Sphere

Financial support to companies, namely with loans with state backup
Launching of long-term and short-term programs
Boosting of support tourist industry while also ensuring relevant tourist restrictions are in place

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
In Austria this would be November 2021

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?
- Structure of Monitorization of the State of Emergency created
- New committees created to tackle different multi-layered problems the COVID-19 pandemic caused
- Hiring of more healthcare personnel & purchasing medication and equipment (e.g., ventilators)
- State of Calamity declared
- State of Emergency declared

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)
 - How did the population react?
- Protests against lockdown measures
Demonstration against vaccine certificates (both with a limited expression).
Differences in with the professions that had to still working and the ones that work from home was possible

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?
Elections take place:
(a) Presidential election Jan 2021
(b) Local elections Sep 2021
- Changes to preparedness plans , jurisdiction ?
Government presented the **Deconfinement Plan** that provides for a gradual easing of the restriction measures, between March 15th 2021 and May 3rd 2021
- Who held the responsibility?
DGS
Health Ministry
Ministry of Internal Affairs
- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government
- Financially disadvantaged, launch of National Strategy to Combat Poverty.
- Safeguard elderly, living in care facilities, and support for health-care personnel working in those establishments. Done via close monitoring, daily testing and by creating a rear support structure to accommodate the infected elderly that were not in need of hospitalization.
- Students and families
- Support for migrants that have direct access to health care without need of checking the legal situation
- Foreign citizens
- People with disabilities

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
- Graça Freitas, head of DGS
- Antero Luis Assistant Sec of state Home Affairs & Patricia Gaspar as sec of state for internal administration
- Minister of Justice (Francisca Van Dunem) also Minister of Internal Administration on December 4th 2021
- Who/what were the expert sources?
The extension of the crisis saw the appearance of concurrent epidemiological models that appear in different research centres and health related interests that start to be vocal. That compels the government to start monthly meetings with an enlarged set of experts in open meetings that change the nature of knowledge transfer.
- Who are the main target populations?
General Population
Elderly Health care workers People suffering of cronic deseases

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

The previous measures of economy support were progressively lifted.

- World events affecting environment of countries

Covid-19-related variants
Russia-Ukraine War

Interaction Area (I)

- Changes in response implementation? (measures)
 - Validity of Order No 11820-B/2021 extended until 9 Feb 2022
 - Renew the declaration of the **State of Alert** throughout mainland Portugal and maintain the set of measures still applicable in the context of combating the pandemic
 - Declaration of the State of Alert in the context of the COVID 19 disease pandemic was extended until 23h59 of May 31st2022
- Changes in people in charge reaction?
 - Change from lockdown to vaccination
 - Slow easing of restrictions
- Changes in crisis management
- An attempt of be more inclusive in the discussion of different perspectives on the understanding of the pandemic unfolding were put in place

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government structure?

Election takes place:

(c) Legislative elections Jan 2022

- Changes to preparedness plans?

Consistency in the vaccination rollout. The structural change was the way the hospital responded to the pandemic.

- Changes to responsibility?

None

- Changes in vulnerabilities

None

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
- Portuguese government led by Prime Minister António Costa, working with health authorities such as the National Health Service (SNS) and the Directorate-General for Health (DGS).
- New government maintain the same health minister and the DGS director is independent after nomination. In 30th of August the minister ask to be dismissed and a new minister was nominated: Manuel Pizarro. The head of DGD also ask for retirement. But she was not replaced until the present day.
- Who/what were the expert sources?

Due to appearance of different epidemiological models the government promoted a monthly meeting, where the different parties and the president of the Republic were present, where the different institutions and universities presented their conclusions about the pandemic and the studies they were doing about the behavioural measures acceptance

- Changes in main target populations?
- Changed from finding and isolating infected people to immunizing at-risk populations including healthcare professionals, the elderly, and people with underlying medical issues. In a nutshell no changes from the previous identified vulnerable groups

Outcomes (O)

- Changes in country status/ indicators:
 - Inflation rate:- 2020 – 0,0%; 2021 – 1,3%; **2022 : 7, 8%**
 - Maternal mortality rate per 100,000 live births – (2019: 10,4%; 2020 : 20,1%)
- What barriers, problems were encountered?

Despite high vaccination rate, Portugal still suffers from pandemic impact

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown
T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022 (or earlier depending on data collection for iteration)

Spain

Model T0

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Economic Sphere

Introduction of economic aid measures
 Social housing
 Community assistance
 Minimum income guarantee programs
 Food distribution
 Measures to protect mortgage debtors
 ERTE Furlough Scheme

Judicial Sphere

State of Alarm ruled as unconstitutional – July 2021

Health Sphere

Free Vaccinations
 Free Testing

Social Sphere

Travel bans
 Closure of public spaces
 Lockdowns and social distancing

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?

New COVID-19 laws

Penalties for not following COVID-19 rules

- Important responses include:

March 14 2020: the Spanish Government approved Royal Decree 463/2020, which declared a State of Alarm for the management of the health emergency caused by COVID-19; the State of Alarm had to be validated every 15 days by the Spanish Parliament

Strict confinement measures were installed

April 28 2020: the Plan for the Transition to a New Normality was approved by the Council of Ministers
 June 2020: the strict confinement started to be more flexible depending on the health situation of each autonomous community

June 21 2020: State of Alarm was ended

A de-escalation plan was created by the Single Authority

End of October 2020: a new State of Alarm was declared

Testing & tracing efforts: different interpretations in different regions, and considerable differences in regions' testing agility

COVID Radar app: only half of the autonomous regions used the application

Measures:

- Lockdowns
- Social distancing
- Mask wearing
- Testing

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?

Single Authority (also labelled as Single Command) & increase in the frequency of meetings of the Interterritorial Health Committee (Interterritorial de Sanidad). Joint buying of supplies through the Ministry's structures although not every region participated to the same extent.

- Changes to preparedness plans, jurisdiction ?

Plans had to be adequated from previous pandemics to the specificities of COVID as knowledge was acquired

- Who held the responsibility?

Prime Minister Pedro Sanchez

Health Minister Salvador Illa

Ministry of Defence: Margarita Robles

Ministry of Interior: Fernando Grande Marlaska

Transport Ministry: José Luis Ábalos

- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

Economic vulnerable citizens: informal workers, part-time, temporary contracts, wages below the minimum wage

Youth

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

Law enforcement officials

Military officials

Minister of Defence Margarita Robles

Minister of Interior

Minister of Transports

- Who/what were the expert sources?

Scientific Committee of COVID-19

Center for Coordination of Health Alerts and Emergencies (CCAES)

Member of the Advisory Committee of the European Center for Disease Prevention

Control Fernando Simón

- Who are the main target populations?

General Population

Disabled people

Immigrants & Elderly

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)

- Migration index (% migrant population)
- Age index, gender - % female
- Trust in government
- Housing concentration
- GDP
- Unemployment rates
- Poverty index

- How did the population react?

- Anti-lockdown protests
- Anti-vaccine protests
- Spain has a low level of interpersonal trust but places a high importance on the values of conformity and obedience, because of that, is suggested that policies should focus on improving credibility and education.

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
 In Austria this would be November 2021

Model T2

England

Model TO

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Social sphere

Self-isolation
Tier system introduced
Execution of lockdowns and social distancing
Travel bans
School closures
Closure of public spaces
Restriction of gatherings
Travel ban
Events cancelled
Rent freezes

Economic sphere

Individual Support

Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme ('Furlough')
Self-Employment Income Support Scheme (SEISS) (ends in Sept 2021)
Self-Isolation Payment Support
The COVID-19 Statutory Sick Pay Enhancement Scheme
Kickstart Scheme
Restart Scheme

Business Support

Bounce Back Loan Scheme (BBLs)
Waive business rates for hospitality and retail businesses and nurseries
Cash grants for small businesses and firms in retail, hospitality and leisure sectors
Local Restrictions Support Grants Scheme
Eat out to Help Out scheme

Health sphere

Free Vaccination
Free Testing
Additional Funding towards NHS

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?
 - New COVID-19 laws (for implementation of lockdowns, restrictions, etc.)
 - New COVID-19 task forces
 - Execution of fines and penalties for breaking lockdowns
 - Lockdowns imposed when case rates increased
 - Creation of new Ministers
 - Coronavirus Act 2020
 - Government interventions to address misinformation
- Measures:
- Lockdowns
 - Restrictions
 - Reintroduction of tiered system
 - Mask wearing
 - Testing
 - UK Aid for misinformation

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)
 - n/a
 - Changes to preparedness plans, jurisdiction?
 - Coronavirus Act
 - Coronavirus Action Plan
 - Introduction of COVID-19 Response: Autumn and Winter Plan.
- Who held the responsibility?
 - UK Government
- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government
 - 80 or older, males more than females, those living in deprived areas, BAME groups, General Youth, School children, victims of domestic abuse, homeless, ethnic minorities, clinically extremely vulnerable

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
 - Boris Johnson, Rishi Sunak, Sajid David, Nadhim Zahawi as the new UK vaccines minister
- Who/what were the expert sources?
 - Moral and Ethical Advisory Group
 - Professor Chris Whitty (Chief Medical Officer for England)
 - Sir Patrick Vallance (Government Chief Scientific Advisor)
 - Vaccination Board
 - Health Professionals, e.g., NHS and NICE
 - Ministerial-led taskforces
 - Department of Health and Social Care
 - Experts and Scientific Advisory Groups, e.g., The Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE)
 - Sub-groups of SAGE, e.g., New and Emerging Respiratory Virus Threats Advisory Group, Scientific Pandemic Insights Group on Behaviours, Scientific Pandemic Influenza Group on Modelling, PHE Serology Working Group, COVID-19 Clinical Information Network, New and Emerging Respiratory Virus Threats Advisory Group, Environmental Modelling Group, Children's Task and Finish Working Group, Hospital onset COVID-19 Working Group, Social Care Working Group, Ethnicity Sub-Group.
 - Cabinet Office Briefing Rooms (COBR)
 - Technical Advisory Cell (TAC) and Technical Advisory Group (TAG)
- Who are the main target populations?
 - General public
 - Specific vulnerable groups

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)
- How did the population react?
 - Anti-lockdown protests
 - Anti-vaccine movement

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
In Austria this would be November 2021

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Health Sphere

Vaccines (including boosters)
Restricted COVID-19 testing
Drop of ICU hospital beds

Social Sphere

Implementation of Plan B following Omicron and subsequent NHS pressure
March 2022, travel restrictions removed
Lockdowns begin to ease
April 2022 – free lateral flow tests no longer available
Removing guidance that staff and students in education should be testing

Legal/Juridical Sphere

Legal requirements around self-isolation would be replaced by guidance

Economic Sphere

Self-isolation support payments ceased from Feb 2022
Removal of COVID-19 provisions in statutory sick pay and employment and support allowance regulations
World events affecting environment of countries

Omicron
War in Ukraine
Brexit

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown
T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022 (or earlier depending on data collection for iteration)

Interaction Area (I)

- Changes in response implementation? (measures)
Feb 2022, all domestic legal restrictions ended.

Includes ending legal requirement to self-isolate following positive COVID-19 test. Replaced by guidance to stay at home for 5 days.

Removal of requirement for employers to consider COVID-19 in health and safety risk assessments.

March 2022, all remaining COVID-19 travel restrictions removed for incoming international travelers to the UK.

Launch of COVID-19 Inquiry

- Changes in people in charge reaction?

Transition from lockdowns to vaccination
Effective reduction of infection rates due to booster rollout

Changes in crisis management

Introduction of COVID-19 response autumn and winter plan
2022 Living with Covid Plan introduced

Outcomes (O)

- Changes in country status/indicators:
- What barriers, problems were encountered?

Government scandals regarding COVID-19 contracts

Spread of misinformation, e.g., vaccines

Ongoing protests, especially ongoing anti-vaccine protests

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government structure?
n/a
- Changes to preparedness plans?
n/a
- Changes to responsibility?

July 2022, Sajid David Sec of State for Health and Rishi Sunak becomes Chancellor of Exchequer

September 2022, Rishi Sunak replaced by Nadhim Zahawi as Chancellor of Exchequer Sajid David was the former Chancellor of Exchequer from 2019-2020, and Rishi Sunak former Chief Secretary to the Treasury (2019-2020).

- Changes in vulnerabilities

Identification of vaccine vulnerability – low booster uptake among black and Pakistani communities, 18-24 year olds, 12-15 year olds, Gypsy/Roma, Irish Traveller, Black Caribbean and Black African groups.

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

Boris Johnson, Rishi Sunak, Sajid David

- Who/what were the expert sources?
- Professor Chris Whitty (Chief Medical Officer for England)
- Sir Patrick Vallance (Government Chief Scientific Advisor)
- See other experts cited in T1 model

Changes in main target populations?

- Targeted communications to increase vaccine uptake in Bangladeshi, Muslim, Indian, Black and migrant communities. Pregnant women also targeted. This is for increased vaccine uptake.

Belgium

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What kind of resources were in different sectors of the country?

Various economic measures implemented including in March 2020 where the furlough scheme was applied. This meant that workers are entitled to 70% of salary

Please write a short paragraph about the most important facts about your country's governance. See country report: Belgium already had a crisis management structure for potential pandemics before the COVID-19 pandemic. Distinct levels of governance.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Up until January 2020

Interaction Area (I)

No relevant data is available

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (from WP2):
 - Migration index (% migrant population)
 - Age index, gender - % female
 - Trust in government
 - Housing concentration
 - GDP
 - Unemployment rates
 - Poverty index

For more information look at the [COVINFORM Dashboard](#)

Governance Systems (GS)

- How is the government structured?

Federal political system

Five autonomous regions with own parliament/unicameral council

Constitutional representative monarchy

Executive branch = Head of Government & Council of Ministers & State Secretaries.

Chamber of Representatives

- Who is responsible for the management of a health crisis?

NFP

The Risk Assessment Group

The Risk Management Group

The Economic Risk Management Group

The Expert Strategy Exit Group, then, in August 2020, replaced by Celevel

Sciensano

Expert Committee on Management Strategy

- What preparedness plans & legislation already existed?

Belgium has a National Pandemic Influenza Plan from 2006, with an advisory report from 2009.

- What were the general vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government?

National Pandemic Influenza plan emphasized emphasizes tailored communication strategies for different audiences, yet the plan lacks specificity on vulnerable populations, recovery, and evaluation of mitigation measures

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

Minister of Security and Foreign Affairs

National Crisis Centre

Local Governments

Special Departments, e.g., Flemish Department of Welfare, Public Health and Family

- Who/what were the expert sources?

Group of Experts for an Exit Strategy, consisting of 10 medical experts, economics, and top managers.

Other experts include Marc Wathelet, Professor in Microbiology, Herman Goossens, Professor of Virology Marc Van Ranst amongst others.

- Who are the main target populations?

General Population

To be defined vulnerable populations

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Social/Social Welfare Sphere

Severe COVID-19 consequences on the disadvantaged and strengthened social inequality
High death rates in poor areas
Lockdowns affected children from families with limited resources
Restrictions in gatherings fuelled limitations for certain religions, e.g., Jews and Muslims

Economic Sphere

Big financial hit due to pandemic, e.g., 10% loss of revenue due to the health crisis.
OCMW provided financial support during the pandemic

Legal Sphere

Criticism towards Belgian Governments regarding suspensions of fundamental rights, e.g., education, religion, and assembly in conjunction with the curfew and limitations of movement.

Health Sphere

Vaccine administration

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
In Austria this would be November 2021

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?

Non-pharmaceutical interventions

Curfew measures

Vaccination measures

Introduction of Covid Safe Ticket ('CST')

The European digital Corona Certificate, accompanied with scheme to receive two PCR tests reimbursed if could not be vaccinated yet

Hospitality measures

Number of people per table limited to 6

Discos and dance halls closed

Indoor public events only allowed to take place while seated with CST and mouth mask

Cultural interventions

Restore conditions for cultural sector and by extension the cinemas the events sector, to those of 3 December: seats only, with mouth mask, use of CST from 50 visitors, and maximum of 200 visitors.

General

By March 2022, loosening of measures, e.g., CST no longer required, no more PLF within EU, no more testing and quarantine with COVID certificate.

May 2022, further measure relaxations, e.g., lifting of mouth mask

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)

- How did the population react?

Anti-lockdown protests

Protests against vaccine mandate

Extremist groups spread COVID-19 misinformation

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?

Wilmes administration special powers renewed for another three months
Creation of Corona Commission

- Changes to preparedness plans, jurisdiction?

Belgium Recovery and Resilience Plan
Adoption of Pandemics Law

- Who held the responsibility? Distinct levels of governance -there was a lot confusion about the responsible actor and the level of governance.
- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government
- Belgium widens the vulnerability spectrum to not only combat health and employment parameters, but also migration status, sex workers and homelessness.
- Besides financial aid, also included psychosocial support and shelter for the homeless, leniency towards undocumented migrants and food-aid to those living the poverty threshold.
- Also safeguarding pregnant women, single parents, unemployed, students, with paid leave, funds and digital equipment.

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

Sophie Wilmes (first female PM, then replaced by Alexander De Croo)
Prime Minister Alexander De Croo
Health Minister Frank Vandenbroucke

- Who/what were the expert sources?

Group of Experts for an Exit Strategy, consisting of 10 medical experts, economics, and topmanagers.
Marc Wathelet
Professor in Microbiology, Herman Goossens
Professor of Virology Marc Van Ranst

- Who are the main target populations?

General Population + more targeted to vulnerable groups as pandemic progressed

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Health Sphere

Vaccines (COVID-19)
Limited ICU beds
Ending of COVID-19 testing from 2022

Economic Sphere

No changes, support systems for businesses that experienced hardship during the pandemic

Legal/jurisdictional Sphere

March 2022 Belgium removes almost all COVID-19 restrictions, ending requirement to wear masks in almost all places and scrapping need to show COVID-19 pass for indoor venues.

World events affecting environment of countries

War in Ukraine
New COVID-19 variant

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown
T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022 (or earlier depending on data collection for iteration)

Interaction Area (I)

- Changes in response implementation? (measures)
 - Adoption of the 'corona barometer' (red, orange and yellow hierarchy)

Switch from **Code Red** to **Code Orange**

Relaxations, e.g., hospitality sector closing hour lifter, reopening of nightlife, public events available indoors and outdoors, teleworking and masks for children up to 12 years old becomes optional

Switch to **Code Yellow**

Covid Safe Ticket in hospitality sector and events lifted
Mask wearing compulsory only in care sector and public transportation

Lifting of testing

Quarantine obligations with COVID certificate and use of PLF

By May, most travel restrictions and mask obligation on public transport lifted.

- Changes in people in charge reaction?
- Changes in crisis management : constant changes which made it hard to follow for policy makers and the general audience

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government structure?

Federal phase of governance finished in March 2022.

Regional authorities, governors and local administrations would be in charge of managing pandemic.

- Changes to preparedness plans?
- Changes to responsibility?

WG SIC established Spring 2020

Taskforce for Vulnerable Groups

GEES replaced by CELEVAL in August 2020. Consultation Committee took over federal responsibility for COVID-19 response in October 2020

RAG tasked with submitting recommendations in November 2020

Mid-december 2020, GEMS, advisory group of 24 medical experts established to coordinate the different groups and committees involved in the COVID-19 government responses. Corona Commissariat, led by "Corona Commissioner" Pedro Facon, was established in September 2020 to coordinate these efforts and was formally rescinded in April 2022.

- Changes in vulnerabilities

The long term effects for many vulnerable groups and the general population are not yet recognised and difficult to grasp.

Outcomes (O)

- Changes in country status/ indicators:
- What barriers, problems were encountered?

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
- Who/what were the expert sources?
- Changes in main target populations?

WGSIC documented impact sex workers, disabled people, job students, those with precarious employment, artists, families with children etc.

Examples identified by the Vulnerable Group Taskforce include homeless people, people with precarious jobs, prisoners, single-parent families, children from vulnerable families, sex workers, people with no or limited access to the internet, undocumented migrants, and persons with disabilities.

Italy

Model TO

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Health Sphere

Vaccination infrastructure (free)

Testing (free)

Healthcare spending

Social/Social Welfare Sphere

Lockdowns and social distancing

Travel Ban

Closure of public spaces

Economic Sphere

Governmental Economic Support

Introduction of Moratorium on the payment of corporate debt

Liquidity shortages and facilitate access to financing

Central Guarantee Fund

Measures to support export, internalization, and investment by business

Support production and supply of medical devices and PPE

Suspension of industrial and commercial activities

Enhanced transparency in "listed companies" and disclosure requirements

Start-ups

State guarantees for newly issued bonds

State aid to facilitate the orderly compulsory administrative liquidation of small banks

Participation in European Investment Bank's Pan-European Guarantee Fund and New European Scheme

Bolstering of support for innovative start-ups

Support from regional and other local authorities

Measures pertaining to supporting and relaunching the economy

Extension of grace period for SMEs

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning (end of February 2020) and First Lockdown (March-May 2020) until November 2021

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?

Decrees: Cure Italy, Liquidity, Relaunch, Simplification, August, Legislative, Law, Reopening, August
New Ministers

New COVID-19 TaskForces

Passes to access businesses and services

Issue of punishments for not following specific COVID-19 measures

Measures: State of emergency and the division of Italian regions by four different colours

Economic: Suspensions, extensions, and postponements of payments for companies and professionals

Cancellation and reduction of taxes

Incentives and grants

Support for capitalization

Shift to digitization

Economic bonus

Monetary benefits

Health

Working from home

Distance learning

Lockdowns

Social distancing

Mask wearing

Testing

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)

- Migration index (8,6% migrant population)[ISTAT]

- Age index, gender – 51,15 % female [ISTAT]

- Trust in government

- Housing concentration

- GDP:-9%(2020);6,7% (2021) [WB]

- Unemployment rates: 9,2%(2020); 9,5% (2021) [WB]

- Poverty index: in 2021, 7,5% households and 9,4% individuals in absolute poverty; in 2021 the relative poverty raise to 11,1%(from 10,1% in 2020).[ISTAT]

- How did the population react?

Protests against mandatory health passports for workplaces.

Protests against COVID restrictions

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government (structure)?

Establishment of Draghi government Feb 2021

- Changes to preparedness plans , jurisdiction ?

Submission of new pandemic preparedness plan

- Who held the responsibility?

Civil Protection Department

Ministry of Health

Technical and Scientific Committee

Task forces

Control Room of the Health Ministry

Domenico Arcuri & Francesco Paolo Figliuolo, Extraordinary Commissioners

- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

People with disabilities

Older people

Socially disadvantaged groups

Victims of domestic abuse

Children and Teenagers

Students and Teachers

Migrant groups and minorities

Healthcare workers and caregivers

Prisoners

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

Prime Minister Giuseppe Conte

Minister of Health Roberto Speranza

Minister of Economy and Finance Roberto Gualtier

From March 2021

Prime Minister Mario Draghi

State/Regions Conference

Minister of Health Roberto Speranza

Minister of Economy and Finance Daniele Franco

- Who/what were the expert sources?

Psychological Psychotherapeutic experts

COVID-19 Scientific Committee in Italy

Technical and Scientific Committee (CTS)

Civil Protection Department and Board of Health

Special Covid Commissioner Domenico Arcuri (till February 2021) then

Francesco Paolo Figliuolo (till end of March 2022)

The Control Room of the Health Ministry

The Economic and Social Council (CES)

- Who are the main target populations?

General Population

Elderly Health care workers People suffering of chronic diseases

Model T2

Sweden

Model T0

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Social Sphere

Restraining constitutionally protected public gatherings
Setting attendance limits
Social distancing
Restrictions on restaurants, sport and cultural activity organisers
Remote teaching (high school and university)
Travel bans (prohibited entry to Sweden)
Limited amount of customers in stores
Recommendation of face mask use in public transportation
Recommendation of remote work
Visiting ban in elderly homes

Health Sphere

Free Vaccination
Free testing

Economic Sphere

Economic measures to support affected sectors of society
Limitations on business operation
Elimination of the qualifying day for sick leave

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?

The Swedish strategy was to use voluntary measures and recommendations. Few mandatory measures were used during 2020, No hard lockdown implemented at any point.

EU vaccine certificate was introduced
New COVID-19 laws

Measures:

Social distancing
Testing
Home offices - working from home
Distant teaching at high schools and universities
No lockdowns
Voluntary mask wearing, but recommended in public transports from 2021

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)
- How did the population react?
High trust in authorities (especially health care) - rally effects
Limited lockdown and restriction protests
Protests from restaurant business and sports- /entertainment business against restrictions
Critique against the visiting bans in elderly homes
Debate about some groups (especially younger people) not following recommendations

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?
Reorganized the government chancellery and moved responsibility for crisis management closer to the Cabinet office
- Changes to preparedness plans , jurisdiction ?
Pandemic Act/Infection control legislation
COVID-19 Act Jan 2021
- Who held the responsibility?
Ministry of Health and Social Affairs
The National Board of Health and Welfare
The Public Health Agency
Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency
- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government
Migrants and marginalized populations
Victims of domestic abuse
Vulnerable children
Homeless people
Undocumented immigrants
Health care workers
Elderly in care homes
People with underlying diseases

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
Prime Minister Stefan Lofven, then preceded by Prime Minister Magdalena Andersson
Minister of Health and Social Affairs Lena Hallengren
- Who/what were the expert sources?
State Epidemiologist Anders Tegnell
- Who are the main target populations?
General Population
Elderly
Migrant population

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Health Sphere
Vaccines
Removing free COVID-19 testing, Feb 2022

Economic Sphere
All business restrictions were removed February removed

Legal/Judicial Sphere
December 2021, considerations for stricter restrictions were changed to swapped for gradual reopening of society (Feb 2022)

The temporary COVID-19 Act was abolished March 31th, 2022

All travel bans were abolished April 2022

- World events affecting environment of countries

Omicron
Variant outbreaks

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown
T2: Omicron until now (November 2021) up until September 2022 (or earlier depending on data collection for iteration)

Interaction Area (I)

- Changes in response implementation? (measures)
Gradually abolishing of all restrictions
- Changes in people in charge reaction?

From July 2021 until December the same year, COVID-19 seemed almost to be over from a Swedish perspective.

- Changes in crisis management
Abolishing restrictions:
Opening up workplaces
Allowing sports and entertainment activities
Students back to universities

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government structure?
N/a
- Changes to preparedness plans?
- Changes to responsibility?
General Director of the PHA, Johan Carlsson, was replaced (retirement), by Karin Tegmark Wisell
- Changes in vulnerabilities
None

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
Prime Minister Magdalena Andersson, then preceded by Ulf Kristersson
Minister for Health and Social Affairs Ardalan Shekrabi, then preceded by Jakob Forssmed
- Who/what were the expert sources?
State Epidemiologist Anders Tegnell, then preceded by Karin Tegmark Wisell,
- Changes in main target populations?
None

Outcomes (O)

- Changes in country status/ indicators:
COVID-19 epidemiologic data
- What barriers, problems were encountered?
Polarisation of population around vaccination, but rather limited
Students as vulnerable groups through school closure came into public discourse
Isolation in home offices brings on psychological problems.
Exhausted health care workers, strains on health care system.
Misinformation/desinformation on social media, especially related to vaccination

Wales

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What kind of resources were in different sectors of the country?
Social/Social Welfare Sphere
Health Sphere
Economic Sphere

Please write a short paragraph about the most important facts about your country's governance.

Nation from the UK with devolved government that has 20 areas of government that have its own decision-making power since 1998. Health is one of these areas directed by NHS Wales. The National Assembly has legislative powers and the government has consisted of the left-leaning Labour party since the devolution. Wales representatives sit in on the UK-wide Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE). The Wales Resilience Forum is the highest authority for crisis management. In 2022 82% of the Welsh budget came from the UK government. In total, this is around 22bn though Wales has no say over 4bn of it.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Up until February 2020

Interaction Area (I)

No relevant data is available

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (from WP2):
 - Migration index (% migrant population)
 - Age index, gender - % female
 - Trust in government
 - Housing concentration
 - GDP
 - Unemployment rates
 - Poverty index

For more information look at the COVINFORM Dashboard

Governance Systems (GS)

- How is the government structured?
Forms part of the UK
Since 2006, Wales given legislative powers. Led to Welsh Parliament and Welsh Assembly Government.
First Minister for Wales
Welsh Ministers
Deputy Ministers
20 areas of responsibility devolved to National Assembly for Wales
- Who is responsible for the management of a health crisis?
Wales Resilience Forum highest authority for emergency planning
Public Health Department manages health emergencies
Emergency planning consistent with UK's Civil Contingencies Act 2004
Welsh Government involvement and participation of operating organisations as well
- What preparedness plans & legislation already existed?
- Wales participated in UK-level pandemic exercise Winter Willow (2007) and exercise Cygnus (2016)
Led to development of 2007 nation framework for responding to an influenza pandemic
- Framework used to support Welsh government response to 2009 swine flu pandemic
- Wales worked with other UK governments to put in place UK influenza preparedness strategy 2011
- Summary Impact Assessment (SIA)
- What were the general vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government?
Old and younger populations
healthcare workers
hospitals and health institutions as systems

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
Health Minister: Vaughan Gethin
Prime Minister: Mark Drakeford
Chief Medical Officer: Sir Frank Atherton
Chair of Vaccine Strategy Committee: Dr Gillian Richardson
- Who/what were the expert sources?
SAGE
Public Health Wales
Welsh Scientific Advisory Committee
- Who are the main target populations?
General Population

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:

Social/Social Welfare Sphere:

- Execution of lockdowns and social distancing
- Closing of public spaces
- Travel bans and 5-mile rule
- Unpaid carers payments
- Covid-19 Statutory Sick Pay Enhancement scheme
- Tenancy Hardship Grant
- Household bubbles
- care home restrictions tightened and eased

Health Sphere:

- Testing infrastructure (free)
- Vaccination (free)
- Shielding

Legal/Judicial Sphere

- Working from home with tax breaks
- Rent scheme/eviction stop
- group gatherings ban

Economic Sphere:

- COVID passes for hospitality

Financial support has involved:

- COVID-19 Non-Domestic Rates (NDR) Grant Scheme
- Business Rates Relief
- Furlough scheme
- Economic Resilience Fund
- Other support administered by local authorities
- COVID-19 Wales Business Loan Scheme

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination had an effect on measures
September 2021

Interaction Area (I)

- How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?

- New COVID-19 laws (for implementation of lockdowns, restrictions, etc.)
- New COVID-19 task forces
- Execution of fines and penalties for breaking lockdowns
- Lockdowns imposed when case rates increased
- Coronavirus Act 2020

Measures

- Lockdowns
- Social distancing
- Mask wearing
- Testing
- 5-mile rule
- Travel bans

Outcomes (O)

- Country status/ indicators (specify exact timeframe)

- Vaccination rates
- Infection rates (R number)
- Hospital waiting times for non-COVID tests and treatment
- number of people newly added to the universal credit scheme
- business start-ups and closures
- number of homeless people
- number of people in crisis and residential care on mental health issues
- number of anti-depressant prescriptions

- How did the population react?

General acceptance of measures
Anti-vaccine protests (very few)
Anti-government protests (very few)
Anti-lockdown protests (very few)

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government (structure)?

Wales general election May 2021 but Labour remains the leading party and remains as the governing party

- Changes to preparedness plans, jurisdiction ?

The Health Protection (Coronavirus Restrictions) (Wales) Regulations 2020 put in place. Four more replacement regulations sets were put in place (No. 2), (No. 3), (No. 4) and (No. 5).

SIAs developed weekly and later every three weeks

Alert Levels in Wales August 2021 assessment

- Who held the responsibility?

Health Ministry

- Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

- CEV population, including shielders and family

- Keyworkers: in healthcare, education, food provision,

Forgotten populations:

- Homeless people,

- People without sufficient resources to participate in pandemic self-governance (such as Gypsy Travellers)

- People unable to develop sufficient knowledge of risks (such as people with learning disabilities),

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

Health Ministers: Vaughan Gething, First Minister: Mark Drakeford.

- Who/what were the expert sources?

Technical Advisory Cell

Technical Advisory Group

Welsh Scientific Advisory Committee

SAGE

Public Health Wales

- Who are the main target populations?

General Population

Model T2

Greece

Model TO

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What kind of resources were in different sectors of the country?
- Social sphere
- Health sphere
- Economic sphere
- Legal/jurisdictional sphere

Please write a short paragraph about the most important facts about your country's governance.

- Greece as a Presidential Parliamentary Republic adopted a top down, central authority approach and response. The response mechanism key figures did not radically change during the pandemic whereas the response was a joint effort between political, governmental representatives who had decision-making responsibilities and the scientific community, particularly healthcare experts who predominantly had a advisory and crisis communication role.

TIMEFRAME

TO: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic

Up until January 2020

Interaction Area (I)

Implementation of rules and regulations on a nationwide scale

Outcomes (O)

- The migration rate was reduced significantly in Greece at the pandemic outbreak according to [Eurostat](#).
- According to the [European Institute for Gender Equality](#), in Greece the risk of poverty decreased for both male and female citizens, share of women on publicly listed companies increased as did the female parliament members. On the other side, full time employment rate has decreased for both female and male citizens, single parents (both female and male) are at highest risk of poverty while couples with offsprings have a better ratio in full time employment in comparison to couples without children.
- There are no indications that trust in government changed radically if at all during the first phase. According to a research of EKPA (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens), [48% of participants](#) indicate they trust the Government. Similar levels of trust are observed towards the Prime Minister and scientific community.
- A sharp decline in the overall GDP is observed by the data acquired from the [Hellenic Statistic Agency](#).
- Similarly, declining rate of [employment](#) is observed which fluctuated during the later phases.

For more information look at the [COVINFORM Dashboard](#).

Governance Systems (GS)

How is the government structured?

- Presidential Parliamentary Republic, the Head of State is the President, the President of Government, is the Prime Minister.
- The Council of Ministers consists of the Prime Minister, the Deputy Prime Minister, the Ministers, and the Deputy Ministers and is the collective decision-making body that constitutes the Government of Greece. The government Council for Foreign and Defense Affairs (KYSEA) on shaping the country's national defense and security policy. The government comprises of 19 Ministries and the legislative power is exercised by Parliament and the President of the Republic.

Who is responsible for the management of a health crisis?

- A National Crisis Management Mechanism of the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSPP).
- The Deputy Minister for Civil Protection and Crisis Management along with the relevant ministers of the respective ministries (e.g., Health, Education, Internal Affairs, Sports, etc.).
- Ministry of health supervised the National Public Health Organization (NPHO).
- A flexible Government Committee (reporting body – COVID-19 Observatory, is headed by the President of the Council of Economic Experts).
- The Hellenic Ministry of Health, the General Secretary of Civil Protection and the Hellenic Ministry of Citizen Protection.
- The central government.

What preparedness plans & legislation already existed?

- More than **800 Acts of legislative content** (Laws, Joint Ministerial decisions, Ministerial decision, Decrees etc.).

What were the general vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government?

- People with chronic disease and comorbidities (healthcare related vulnerabilities).

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- Prime Minister, Kyriakos Mitsotakis and the Health Ministers
- Tsiodras, Head of the Infection Experts Committee of the Ministry of Health
- Chardalias, Secretary general for civil protection
- Magiorkinis, Doctor specialising in clinical pathology and epidemiology.
- Who/what were the expert sources?
- GSPP, NPHO, Government Committee is headed by the President of the Council of Economic Experts).
- Who are the main target populations?
- General population and to be defined vulnerable groups. Main vulnerable group was defined based on health-related characteristics.

Model T1

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- What were the main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:
 - All sectors during lockdown
 - **Social sphere**
 - Border control methodology of “exhaustive tracking”.
 - Execution of lockdowns and social distancing.
 - Closing of public spaces.
 - Information campaign.
 - Restriction of the mobility.
 - Digital communication means for information exchange and emergency cases.
 - **Health sphere**
 - the implementation of a testing database.
 - organized vaccination mechanism.
 - 64 mobile healthcare units.
 - Vaccination of individuals in psychiatric wards and institutions, refugee facilities and elderly healthcare facilities.
 - Facemasks indoors and outdoors.
 - **Economic sphere**
 - Implement actions for financially supporting business owners and employees.
 - Granting special leave of absence and providing teleworking for protection of employees.

Interaction Area (I)

How was the response implemented when it hit including measures?

- Top-down tailored containment measures and responses, framed by local community characteristics.
- Legislative acts, such as ministerial decisions
- Epidemiological map
- Legislative initiatives

Measures:

Digitalization of services, movement restriction lockdown implementation during the initial phases, employment of healthcare personnel, provision of free antigen COVID-19 test to the public and self-test at schools, information campaign, the implementation of a testing database and the border control, methodology of “exhaustive tracking”, utilization of the algorithm Empathic Visualisation Algorithm (EVA) 72 and the application Product Lifecycle Management (PLM).

Outcomes (O)

The total population according to the Hellenic Statistic Agency was decreased by **3.1%** in comparison to the previous national survey conducted in 2011, a decrease which is also **confirmed** by the World Bank.

In relation to **employment**, a slight increase is observed in comparison to 2020.

In relation to trust in institutions and government, contrary to the positive results of 2020, in 2021 almost half participants (**48%**) present a negative opinion, while 68% suggest that the COVID-19 pandemic impact will be severely negative. In addition, in relation to trust in media, the study presented that citizens have low trust towards both traditional and contemporary means of information.

How did the population react?

- An increased number of citizens are more susceptible to **misinformation** and demonstrate declining levels of trust towards the government..
- Decrease in public tolerance for measure implementation.

Governance Systems (GS)

Changes in government (structure)?

- Government cabinet reshuffling, appointment of new Minister of Health.

Changes to preparedness plans , jurisdiction ?

- State digitization which was prioritized parallel to the containment measures.

Who held the responsibility?

- The National Public Health Organization.
- The National Epidemiological Committee.
- General Secretariat of Civil Protection.

Changes in global vulnerabilities acknowledged and addressed by the government

- Elderly people, citizens with health conditions, inmates in penitentiary institutions, refugees and migrants, homeless citizens, Roma communities, and “isolated” groups that might not have immediate access to healthcare, healthcare professionals, workers in the tourism and hospitality sector.
- Socio-economic vulnerable individuals such as citizens that had their economic activities suspended by the measures and COVID-19, single parent families, homeless people etc.

Actor Systems (A)

Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?

- The presidency of the Government, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Migration, Ministry of Health, General Secretary of Citizen Protection, National Public Health Organization, National Epidemiological Committee, General Secretariat of Civil Protection, Hellenic Police.

Who/what were the expert sources?

- Representatives of Ministry of Public Health
- National experts from different academic fields (i.e. Health, sociology etc), EODY

Who are the main target populations?

- General population
- Elderly, minorities, refugees and migrants, single parent families, citizens with disabilities, socio-economic and cultural vulnerabilities, young citizens.
- People with chronic illness and comorbidities

TIMEFRAME

T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination

Model T2

Resource Systems and Units (RSU)

- Changes in main issues addressed within different sectors of the society:
 - **Health sphere**
 - Vaccines
 - Prioritizing of vaccination for elderly people
 - Tailored communication campaigns along with patients with high-risk diseases
 - **Economic sphere**
 - Tourism financial support of the relative industry, employees and businesses.
 - Seasonal hotels open from June 15th for domestic holidaymakers and campsites were able to open on June 1st.
 - Downscale the relatively high financial state support to venues and other touristic and leisure organisations.
 - **Legal/jurisdictional sphere**
 - Emergency legislative tools. Organisation of the work implied extenuating hours of working, beyond the legal limits.
 - **Social sphere**
 - End of June 2022 almost all restriction except mask wearing in some places were lifted
- World events affecting environment of countries
 - Again new virus variant: Omicron
 - War in the Ukraine

TIMEFRAME

T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic
T1: COVID-19 Beginning and First Lockdown until vaccination
T2: Vaccination until now

Interaction Area (I)

- Changes in response implementation?
 - Restricted the number of attendees to religious worship places during religious events.
 - Mental health support.
 - Facemasks compulsory at work and services as well as in transports.
 - Citizens were required to carry a QR code explaining why they were leaving their homes.
 - Upper secondary schools were able to return to classes from May 11th 2021. Lower grades returned to classes from May 18th.
 - Regional, local or national lockdowns, physical distancing.
 - Curfew from 11 p.m. to 5 a.m. only to the most affected areas.
- Changes in people in charge reaction?
 - Protection of elderly and other identified vulnerable citizens through prioritizing vaccination and tailored communication campaigns. Governmental officials were also vaccinated.
- Changes in crisis management
 - Gradual lift of measures.

Outcomes (O)

- Changes in country status/ indicators:
 - COVID-19 epidemiologic data demonstrated decreased rates of infections throughout the last pandemic phase.
- What barriers, problems were encountered?
 - Demonstrations and public protests against the measures had less support
 - Children as a vulnerable group, through school closure came into public discourse and the impact isolation may have on children.

Governance Systems (GS)

- Changes in government structure?
With the exception of the two governmental cabinet reshuffling that took place in Greece during the pandemic, no further changes were made.
- Changes to preparedness plans?
During the third phase, the Greek government continued to build upon the pre-existing preparedness plans, to combat more effectively the COVID-19 pandemic.

Changes to responsibility?

No changes to responsibilities were observed.

Changes in vulnerabilities

Policies were approved to guarantee acceptable living conditions for people that were experiencing the worst consequences of the crisis caused by the COVID-19, offering them access to housing, schooling, food provision, and job protection.

Actor Systems (A)

- Who are the decision makers/ who is responsible/ who are the key professionals?
 - The presidency of the Government
 - The Ministry of Education
 - Ministry of Migration
 - General Secretary of Citizen Protection
 - The National Public Health Organization
 - The National Epidemiological Committee
 - General Secretariat of Civil Protection
 - Ministries of Finance, Development and Investment, Labor and Social Affairs
- Who/what were the expert sources?
 - Representatives of Ministry of Public Health
 - National experts from the scientific community and EODY.
- Changes in main target populations?
 - No major changes in the main target populations. Vulnerability was defined by health, social, cultural, economic and legal indicators.